

Coding Summary by File

Qualitative Analysis BOR project

02/12/2024 11:27

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Document

Files\\Notes W1 S1 - Fostering a Culture of Open Research

Code

Codes\\Assessment

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On	Description
	0.0076	4	1	JS	24/07/2024 12:16	Making provenance of the research accessible; processes by which results were achieved are ethical and clear, tested and testable
			2	JS	24/07/2024 12:27	Responsible assessment.
			3	JS	24/07/2024 13:44	Responsible assessment (quality of the output) - San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment.
			4	JS	24/07/2024 13:57	Open Research is about trustworthiness, speed and scrutiny.

Codes\\Collaboration

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On	Description
	0.0148	5	1	JS	24/07/2024 12:25	All ideas are refined by different views. There is strength in sharing of ideas.
			2	JS	24/07/2024 12:27	International collaboration; sharing and bringing together diverse views.
			3	JS	24/07/2024 14:06	To properly foster research, even as a small group, needs a collaboration across the entire institution.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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4 JS 24/07/2024 14:18

International collaboration – different strands of perspective to make conclusions more robust.

5 JS 25/07/2024 10:26

There are processes and policies in place. But in classic Imperial fashion, everything is siloed. Data protection team, Contracts team, Ethics team. Lack of interconnectivity. No systematic checking. My worry is that this potentially exposes us to risk.

Codes\\Excellence

No 0.0016 2

1 JS 24/07/2024 11:59

excellence

2 JS 24/07/2024 15:24

"High-quality research doesn't mean impactful research."

Codes\\FAIR principles

Yes 0.0362 9

1 JS 24/07/2024 12:20

Results should be repeatable and testable.

2 JS 24/07/2024 12:20

Making provenance of the research accessible; processes by which results were achieved are ethical and clear, tested and testable

3 JS 24/07/2024 13:59

Some aspects of Open Research may not be always reproducible. If the research can be trusted it might be okay not to be reproducible.

4 JS 24/07/2024 14:15

Research to be reproducible needs data, article results to be trusted – importance to inform tech, policy decisions.

5 JS 24/07/2024 14:31

Reproducibility – climate modelling software has hardware (inherent bug – historical restrictions).

6 JS 24/07/2024 15:13

Excel might not be a standardised tool, but it is an easy tool to use, that's why everyone uses it. Therefore, any standardisation should be accompanied by a tool that is easy and accessible to use.

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7 JS 24/07/2024 15:20

There's a balance between too much and too little restriction on software. For instance, Excel provides a freedom of structure, that is why it's so useful, whilst still being easy to use.

8 JS 24/07/2024 15:28

Scripting of data manipulation should be in the same part of the code for reproducibility. Regardless of the programming language, there might be a problem of longevity of that data manipulation, as old languages become obsolete and are not runnable on the future generation of machines, i.e. future versions being incompatible. Making data and software future-proof.

9 JS 24/07/2024 15:42

"Methods and software are so complex that if the software is not open, released, how can one even say that they disclosed the method? If the method is not fully shown, the research is not reproducible".

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Accessibility

No 0.0094 2

1 JS 24/07/2024 15:13

Excel might not be a standardised tool, but it is an easy tool to use, that's why everyone uses it. Therefore, any standardisation should be accompanied by a tool that is easy and accessible to use.

2 JS 24/07/2024 15:20

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Codes\\FAIR principles\\Reusability

No 0.0267 7

1 JS 24/07/2024 12:20

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2 JS 24/07/2024 12:20

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"Methods and software are so complex that if the software is not open, released, how can one even say that they disclosed the method? If the method is not fully shown, the research is not reproducible".

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.2095 73

1 JS 24/07/2024 12:05

College's mission is excellence for the benefit of society, i.e. Science for Humanity.

2 JS 24/07/2024 12:40

Data and code can be shared without being open.

3 JS 24/07/2024 12:40

Data and code can be shared without being open.

4 JS 24/07/2024 12:40

Readme files;

5 JS 24/07/2024 12:41

FAIR and open data – data can be not open and FAIR as long as you include metadata.

6 JS 24/07/2024 12:41

Guideline - "it's not enough to share the data and code, you have to think about why /how".

7 JS 24/07/2024 12:42

A long-term strategy to support open data – stability of Open Research – the data is gone when the funding is gone.

8 JS 24/07/2024 12:42

Is Open Research being supported? Imperial is paying for open access. Here Imperial is doing the right thing

9 JS 24/07/2024 12:58

Problems with FAIR data: the main concern was people citing your work.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				10	JS	24/07/2024 12:57
Lack of college repository.						
				11	JS	24/07/2024 12:57
Difficulty in making things accessible.						
				12	JS	24/07/2024 12:56
Publicly-funded research data are a public good, they should be made openly available – it is your duty to make it available as quick as possible and as open as possible.						
				13	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
All software has to be open-source – open software.						
				14	JS	24/07/2024 13:00
Confidential, sensitive data.						
				15	JS	24/07/2024 13:00
Processes, working in silos and inconsistencies.						
				16	JS	24/07/2024 13:01
Massive interdisciplinary differences.						
				17	JS	24/07/2024 13:01
Advances in technology and obsolescence.						
				18	JS	24/07/2024 13:49
Open Research starts with the open structure of research culture.						
				19	JS	24/07/2024 13:50
Promotion – "DORA" protocol. Some of the best ideas are not immediately shared by the rest of the community – some research takes time to be recognised.						
				20	JS	24/07/2024 13:51
Commercial competitiveness – we need to put our ideas into open literature. We need to capture the IPs.						
				21	JS	24/07/2024 13:54
GDPR legislation can create obstacles because it is not clear whether we can share the data among researchers even within the department or college. We cannot share all useful information openly (especially in medical research). Privacy creates obstacles, Open Research can be a risk for privacy. Problem appears to lie mainly in the interpretation of legislation rather than the legislation itself.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				22	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
				Acceleration in the pace of research when it is being shared openly. The ability for other people to use the software can be rapid if it is open so the research can impact the society more quickly.		
				23	JS	15/11/2024 15:07
				Not all Open Research is positive – the ability to synthesise biological 'things' from code can produce harm.		
				24	JS	24/07/2024 13:57
				Open Research is about trustworthiness, speed and scrutiny. Combining data from different places is just practical.		
				25	JS	24/07/2024 13:58
				Open Research can multiply the impact. Documentation can have long term impact on training and research.		
				26	JS	24/07/2024 13:58
				There is a huge value in having open data but it can be difficult to license these data as they may originate from private companies.		
				27	JS	24/07/2024 14:07
				There needs to be cooperation with funders and partners to ensure Open Research, but there are loads of challenges (e.g. stock research).		
				28	JS	24/07/2024 14:07
				More governance and regulations would be helpful.		
				29	JS	24/07/2024 14:07
				GPDR and financial risk.		
				30	JS	24/07/2024 14:08
				There are massive disciplinary differences across the College.		
				31	JS	24/07/2024 14:08
				Advances in processes – requirements. How do we ensure that things are future proof.		
				32	JS	24/07/2024 14:08
				Data monetisation is recognised.		
				33	JS	24/07/2024 14:15
				Why care about Open Research? College mission is to benefit society.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				34	JS	24/07/2024 14:16
Open access of publication						
				35	JS	24/07/2024 14:16
Open Research data – process in data collection – decision making during experiments ("metadata" in experiments) - allows results to be assessed (both by an internal and external research group).						
				36	JS	02/10/2024 12:40
How to foster Open Research culture?						
				37	JS	02/10/2024 12:40
Redefine culture to take into account the whole research life-cycle (breaking down degree of openness over range of stages of research).						
				38	JS	02/10/2024 12:40
Needs standardised ways – peer review system needs change – info on groups championing Open Research – needs balance between Open Research and Intellectual Property (IP) – guidance from high level authority in college.						
				39	JS	24/07/2024 14:22
Degree of openness of research group vs. preserving competitive advantage.						
				40	JS	24/07/2024 14:22
Needs uniform definition of openness in research community.						
				41	JS	24/07/2024 14:24
Needs long-term thinking to appreciate and realise benefits of Open Research [eg: data-driven AI].						
				42	JS	24/07/2024 14:25
Public health has good practices but there's a reluctance to publish preprints – incentives structure to publish in journal.						
				43	JS	24/07/2024 14:27
Need facility to collect data/metadata.						
				44	JS	24/07/2024 14:27
No standard way of structuring data between different research groups – lack of college infra structure – current solution of OneDrive.						
				45	JS	24/07/2024 14:28
Research data store (RDS) – to be replaced by Research data facility (RDF) – FAIR data repository – system to publish data to public – OneDrive – RDF [resource Description Framework] archive.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				46	JS	24/07/2024 14:30
				Operational data vs. persistent data – the process of raw data -> persistent.		
				47	JS	24/07/2024 14:32
				IP [Intellectual Property] vs. data – ownership of IP belongs to college but data is not considered IP as unable to extract info/insights - data collection is good start.		
				48	JS	22/11/2024 12:06
				When dealing with human data (sensitive data about behaviour), it is problematic to share.		
				49	JS	24/07/2024 15:15
				Terms and conditions surrounding certain data may limit its utility. For instance, GDPR law makes data from prior to the legislation not useable.		
				50	JS	24/07/2024 15:15
				There are consequences of using data for both researchers and commercialisation.		
				51	JS	24/07/2024 15:18
				Is the generation / input of data standardised in any way? Are there any standards? What is the value-cost proposition of standardising that?		
				52	JS	24/07/2024 15:19
				Capturing the metadata is perhaps a bigger challenge than the data itself.		
				53	JS	24/07/2024 15:23
				The more one can rely on automated data acquisition / analysis, the easier it may become to share sensitive data, if augmented in a certain way to hide away sensitive information.		
				54	JS	24/07/2024 15:23
				There's always a balance between spending time to develop testing frameworks for code and spending time to do the actual research.		
				55	JS	24/07/2024 15:26
				"There's a publication bias, where negative clinical trial results disappear".		
				56	JS	22/11/2024 12:25
				As long as the code is published, somebody will see whether the code is correct or not. Instead of enforcing that the code is correct, [they] use the expert intuition whether the final data makes sense and is reasonable.		
				57	JS	24/07/2024 15:37
				With the example of AI, there are clear monopolies out there with big tech companies, where data is locked in these companies and we, as researchers, are not able to use it.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				58	JS	24/07/2024 15:38
				Standardisation of patient data is a classic problem. People tend to collect a lot of data, but there's not much standardisation – apart from clinical trial data. For instance, data from different countries about the same thing might actually refer to a different thing.		
				59	JS	24/07/2024 15:43
				Data repositories (websites) die over time and data is lost.		
				60	JS	24/07/2024 15:44
				There is a need to build large databases that then help drive further openness of data (e.g. the bioinformatics fields).		
				61	JS	24/07/2024 15:45
				There must be some alternatives to Excel available right now.		
				62	JS	25/07/2024 10:05
				Research cannot always be fully open.		
				63	JS	25/07/2024 10:06
				Additionally, we might want to look at generative AI to overcome the issues with pseudonymised/synthesised data. Even if the data are synthesised and doesn't represent a real individual, there are cases where a group of individuals, particular under-represented individuals, could appear and so privacy is another issue.		
				64	JS	25/07/2024 10:07
				I face more or less the same issues. I work in genomics. I have an obligation to open-source data. Sharing data can become more complex because of the expense. Without data dictionaries, the data can be difficult to validate.		
				65	JS	25/07/2024 10:11
				Well documented, open data is not very common. Some people just put data out there without context and documenting steps.		
				66	JS	25/07/2024 10:12
				Computational finance. Nothing there is open. The data can be proprietary. Stock exchange data is public but the data that is recorded on the servers, where you can check each trade, that is not public. Access is restricted to the regulator.		
				67	JS	25/07/2024 10:13
				Pharmaceutical companies and interests around vaccines.		
				68	JS	25/07/2024 10:13
				What you're saying is that this is bigger than research culture.		
				69	JS	25/07/2024 10:14
				Trusted research environments (TREs) however can apparently be a great way of analysing data without compromising research data privacy.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				70	JS	25/07/2024 10:15
Data dictionaries and metadata need to be there. I can store research data privately on my personal drive and no one would ever know about it or request access to it.						
				71	JS	25/07/2024 10:26
There are processes and policies in place. But in classic Imperial fashion, everything is siloed. Data protection team, Contracts team, Ethics team. Lack of interconnectivity. No systematic checking. My worry is that this potentially exposes us to risk.						
				72	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
My experience of the DART (open-domain structured DATA Record to Text generation) is that it is a bit tokenistic. Lack of governance over it. There needs to be a better understanding of the nature of the data sets that it covers. Datasets sit on someone's hard drive. There needs to be some kind of beefy governance over this. But this also could potentially slow things down. I can relate to the anxiety around risks that could occur.						
				73	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
TREs like the BDAU (Big Data and Analytical Unit) are good because they are being used by multiple schools so they are operating at a high standard.						
Codes\\Open Research\Obstacles to Open Research						
	No	0.0706	26			
				1	JS	24/07/2024 12:58
Problems with FAIR data: the main concern was people citing your work.						
				2	JS	24/07/2024 12:57
Lack of college repository.						
				3	JS	24/07/2024 12:57
Difficulty in making things accessible.						
				4	JS	24/07/2024 13:00
Processes, working in silos and inconsistencies.						
				5	JS	24/07/2024 13:01
Advances in technology and obsolescence.						
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Codes\\Open Research\\Openness						
	Yes	0.1043	33			
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Readme files;						
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Guideline - "it's not enough to share the data and code, you have to think about why /how".						
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I face more or less the same issues. I work in genomics. I have an obligation to open-source data. Sharing data can become more complex because of the expense. Without data dictionaries, the data can be difficult to validate.						
				27	JS	25/07/2024 10:11
Well documented, open data is not very common. Some people just put data out there without context and documenting steps.						
				28	JS	25/07/2024 10:12
Computational finance. Nothing there is open. The data can be proprietary. Stock exchange data is public but the data that is recorded on the servers, where you can check each trade, that is not public. Access is restricted to the regulator.						

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29 JS 25/07/2024 10:13

Pharmaceutical companies and interests around vaccines.

30 JS 25/07/2024 10:14

Trusted research environments (TREs) however can apparently be a great way of analysing data without compromising research data privacy.

31 JS 25/07/2024 10:15

Data dictionaries and metadata need to be there. I can store research data privately on my personal drive and no one would ever know about it or request access to it.

32 JS 28/11/2024 13:42

My experience of the DART (open-domain structured DATA Record to Text generation) is that it is a bit tokenistic. Lack of governance over it. There needs to be a better understanding of the nature of the data sets that it covers. Datasets sit on someone's hard drive. There needs to be some kind of beefy governance over this. But this also could potentially slow things down. I can relate to the anxiety around risks that could occur.

33 JS 28/11/2024 13:42

TREs like the BDAU (Big Data and Analytical Unit) are good because they are being used by multiple schools so they are operating at a high standard.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open access

No 0.0082 4

1 JS 24/07/2024 13:51

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2 JS 24/07/2024 14:16

Open access of publication

3 JS 24/07/2024 14:25

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4 JS 24/07/2024 15:26

"There's a publication bias, where negative clinical trial results disappear".

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open code

No 0.0328 9

1 JS 24/07/2024 12:40

Data and code can be shared without being open.

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				5	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
Acceleration in the pace of research when it is being shared openly. The ability for other people to use the software can be rapid if it is open so the research can impact the society more quickly.						
				6	JS	24/07/2024 15:23
There's always a balance between spending time to develop testing frameworks for code and spending time to do the actual research.						
				7	JS	22/11/2024 12:25
As long as the code is published, somebody will see whether the code is correct or not. Instead of enforcing that the code is correct, [they] use the expert intuition whether the final data makes sense and is reasonable.						
				8	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
My experience of the DART (open-domain structured DATA Record to Text generation) is that it is a bit tokenistic. Lack of governance over it. There needs to be a better understanding of the nature of the data sets that it covers. Datasets sit on someone's hard drive. There needs to be some kind of beefy governance over this. But this also could potentially slow things down. I can relate to the anxiety around risks that could occur.						
				9	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
TREs like the BDAU (Big Data and Analytical Unit) are good because they are being used by multiple schools so they are operating at a high standard.						
Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data						
	No	0.0609	18			
				1	JS	24/07/2024 12:40
Data and code can be shared without being open.						
				2	JS	24/07/2024 12:41
FAIR and open data – data can be not open and FAIR as long as you include metadata.						
				3	JS	24/07/2024 12:42
A long-term strategy to support open data – stability of Open Research – the data is gone when the funding is gone.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	24/07/2024 13:00
Confidential, sensitive data.						
				5	JS	24/07/2024 13:01
Massive interdisciplinary differences.						
				6	JS	24/07/2024 13:57
Open Research is about trustworthiness, speed and scrutiny. Combining data from different places is just practical.						
				7	JS	24/07/2024 14:16
Open Research data – process in data collection – decision making during experiments ("metadata" in experiments) - allows results to be assessed (both by an internal and external research group).						
				8	JS	24/07/2024 14:30
Operational data vs. persistent data – the process of raw data -> persistent.						
				9	JS	24/07/2024 15:23
The more one can rely on automated data acquisition / analysis, the easier it may become to share sensitive data, if augmented in a certain way to hide away sensitive information.						
				10	JS	24/07/2024 15:38
Standardisation of patient data is a classic problem. People tend to collect a lot of data, but there's not much standardisation – apart from clinical trial data. For instance, data from different countries about the same thing might actually refer to a different thing.						
				11	JS	24/07/2024 15:43
Data repositories (websites) die over time and data is lost.						
				12	JS	25/07/2024 10:06
Additionally, we might want to look at generative AI to overcome the issues with pseudonymised/synthesised data. Even if the data are synthesised and doesn't represent a real individual, there are cases where a group of individuals, particular under-represented individuals, could appear and so privacy is another issue.						
				13	JS	25/07/2024 10:07
I face more or less the same issues. I work in genomics. I have an obligation to open-source data. Sharing data can become more complex because of the expense. Without data dictionaries, the data can be difficult to validate.						
				14	JS	25/07/2024 10:11
Well documented, open data is not very common. Some people just put data out there without context and documenting steps.						
				15	JS	25/07/2024 10:12
Computational finance. Nothing there is open. The data can be proprietary. Stock exchange data is public but the data that is recorded on the servers, where you can check each trade, that is not public. Access is restricted to the regulator.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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16 JS 25/07/2024 10:13

Pharmaceutical companies and interests around vaccines.

17 JS 25/07/2024 10:14

Trusted research environments (TREs) however can apparently be a great way of analysing data without compromising research data privacy.

18 JS 25/07/2024 10:15

Data dictionaries and metadata need to be there. I can store research data privately on my personal drive and no one would ever know about it or request access to it.

Codes\\Peer-review

No 0.0094 3

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:53

needs standardised ways – peer review system needs change – info on groups championing Open Research – needs balance between Open Research and Intellectual Property (IP) – guidance from high level authority in college.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:53

Lack of process - system of peer-review has poor quality checks.

3 JS 29/07/2024 14:52

(Who is putting forward the funds for better peer-review processes and who is choosing the reviewers?)

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.1336 34

1 JS 24/07/2024 12:54

International collaboration; sharing and bringing together diverse views.

2 JS 24/07/2024 12:58

Big change happened when journals would not accept the paper if the sequence was not made available.

3 JS 24/07/2024 13:02

FAIR data principles for the community but also personal usefulness of methods/open data/DMP.

4 JS 24/07/2024 14:03

Survey on enthusiasm on sharing data - people are keen to use shared data by others but they do not want to share data themselves (self-interest) - but this depends on field.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	24/07/2024 14:04
				Only small part of research is funded by grants. You do not want to treat everything as a matter of compliance.		
				6	JS	24/07/2024 14:09
				When people see that it can benefit them, they will be more likely to adopt the practices.		
				7	JS	24/07/2024 14:09
				People found that there are ways to support them (financially) to publish open access.		
				8	JS	24/07/2024 14:16
				Ideas are refined, needs altruism and generosity in sharing ideas.		
				9	JS	24/07/2024 14:21
				When leading research group – need structure of Open Research – degree of openness between different research group and the implications of competition – chemical engineering – what is data, what is result – from data -> result – needs detailed documentation from researcher on the pathway – Max Planck institute -> infra for data storage, ideas into stored for future use – distinction between data and result – store data as well, can be utilised in the future by technology (e.g. Using AI [on pattern detection] on historical data) - needs good structure for researcher during data collection		
				10	JS	24/07/2024 14:26
				Inertia of research culture – detailed data interpretation and decision making for traceability, needs an overhaul of research procedure (protocols) - needs a step away from chasing incentives.		
				11	JS	24/07/2024 14:27
				Provision of training – but needs standardisation of open research practises beforehand – biomedical data – use of (licensed) software vs. self-coded software – unclear incentive and time commitments in way.		
				12	JS	24/07/2024 14:27
				No standard way of structuring data between different research groups – lack of college infra structure – current solution of OneDrive.		
				13	JS	24/07/2024 14:30
				Restriction on data format (proprietary, not open, not flexible) - needs to be open.		
				14	JS	24/07/2024 14:31
				PhD student finishes work – attribution of data/result authorship – (data can be complex – needs to keep track) – time investment to check data quality – no contractual obligation for open data - "perception of data ownership".		
				15	JS	24/07/2024 15:14
				Has seen a positive steps forward, where research councils / universities / libraries promote everyone sharing their research data.		
				16	JS	24/07/2024 15:18
				Within enterprise data, one has to state the quality of data, but how exactly one states and records it is not standardised. The quality (assurance) is required, but not the format and so there's no clear guidelines.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				17	JS	24/07/2024 15:22
				Less about programming the data workflows, but more about defining the data structures that make it reproducible and equipping the students with such skill.		
				18	JS	24/07/2024 15:24
				Funders (UKRI) demand the release of data within 2 years of getting the funding.		
				19	JS	24/07/2024 15:25
				"There's a publication bias, where negative clinical trial results disappear". Having some enforcement that if the funding is public, one has to release the data regardless of publishing might help alleviate this.		
				20	JS	24/07/2024 15:27
				Some journals do not require enough data from big pharma to reproduce the results, as they still want to attract them to publish in their journal.		
				21	JS	24/07/2024 15:27
				Scripting of data manipulation should be in the same part of the code for reproducibility.		
				22	JS	24/07/2024 15:30
				Invest more time into developing the middleware that gets used again and again.		
				23	JS	24/07/2024 15:36
				We should be focusing on publishing less and only publishing what matters.		
				24	JS	24/07/2024 15:41
				Excel has been around and will probably be around for a long time, making it a sustainable choice.		
				25	JS	08/10/2024 11:12
				PhD students use cut-and-paste in Excel for their data practice, making it completely non-reproducible.		
				26	JS	08/10/2024 11:12
				We should promote students creating clear programming workflows that manipulate the data and lead to reproducible outcomes.		
				27	JS	24/07/2024 15:47
				Shouldn't we be insisting on unit testing to ensure that the code (for data manipulation) is doing the thing we think it's doing?		
				28	JS	25/07/2024 10:05
				The data that we deal with is pseudonymised, patient data but we can publish the methods and code and processes by which we took that sensitive data and got to our final result.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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29 JS 25/07/2024 10:14

From enterprise we have a very different way of looking at datasets over a long long time. If we can share it and find a way to make it bring income into the University. Trusted research environments (TREs) however can apparently be a great way of analysing data without compromising research data privacy.

30 JS 25/07/2024 10:15

In the medical field, the maturity of datasets can be skewed. We have datasets from populations and demographics that are concentrated in White patients for example. Standardisation is needed

31 JS 25/07/2024 10:36

Common themes around inconsistency. Siloes. I wondered if we wanted to comment on imposing consistency via "beefy governance" and trying to be agile as an institution.

32 JS 25/07/2024 10:37

In some ways we have to have more governance. More admin. We make researchers into administrators themselves. Data is so vast.

33 JS 25/07/2024 10:37

The data we hold might just be for high security or it may just be a high volume. We have such a diverse range of data that it is hard to find a one-size fits all solution. We haven't reached a solution that fulfils all of these demands. We need to find a way that we have a relatively simple pipeline that outlines how data can be identified but administratively light.

34 JS 25/07/2024 10:38

Turnover of people. People have been in my department for 3 years. The institution needs to have something fixed [a standard] or a culture of long-termism. Otherwise you have a culture change every 5 years.

Codes\\Sustainability

No 0.0172 4

1 JS 02/10/2024 12:38

(Sustainability): are technologies for holding the data sustainable?

2 JS 24/07/2024 14:02

Imperial data store is nearly full – should we find a better way to store data (publishing vs archiving) - we cannot be buying hard drives as this is not sustainable.

3 JS 24/07/2024 15:28

Scripting of data manipulation should be in the same part of the code for reproducibility. Regardless of the programming language, there might be a problem of longevity of that data manipulation, as old languages become obsolete and are not runnable on the future generation of machines, i.e. future versions being incompatible. Making data and software future-proof.

4 JS 24/07/2024 15:39

Excel has been around and will probably be around for a long time, making it a sustainable choice.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Codes\\Transparency						
	No	0.0676	10			
				1	JS	02/12/2024 10:08
How can we ensure our research is						
				2	JS	02/12/2024 10:08
? Results should be repeatable and testable.						
				3	JS	24/07/2024 12:15
Transparency – Making provenance of the research accessible; processes by which results were achieved are ethical and clear, tested and testable.						
				4	JS	24/07/2024 14:06
More transparency is needed on what Open Research means.						
				5	JS	24/07/2024 15:26
"There's a publication bias, where negative clinical trial results disappear".						
				6	JS	25/07/2024 10:10
Thinking around Open Research which College can help with in terms of increasing our transparency about what we do. When we have a new project. How do we comply with legislation. Privacy notices. Why are we holding data in NHS hospitals. I feel there is work that can be done to make that easier. When we publish, we can streamline ways we can tag research data to research publications. It would be good to have a pipeline showing that we are being as transparent as we can. There are a number of different ways that we can streamline that process.						
				7	JS	25/07/2024 10:12
Computational finance. Nothing there is open. The data can be proprietary. Stock exchange data is public but the data that is recorded on the servers, where you can check each trade, that is not public. Access is restricted to the regulator. There are a lot of moving parts. Currency data, BOE and European Central Bank, both have public records and publicly available. When attempting to match the data between the two and scrutinising that you often get no answer. So even though they are public institutions they have their own autonomy. It's systematically intransparent. When you say that it has "benefit to society" but each of these members of society have different interests.						
				8	JS	25/07/2024 10:13
And they [Corporations] have their own interests which they want to protect. Corporations have more rights than individuals.						
				9	JS	25/07/2024 10:17
Data dictionaries and metadata need to be there. I can store research data privately on my personal drive and no one would ever know about it or request access to it. There are many standards in place but some of these do not have teeth or there is a lack of willingness to engage with these. It is crucial for the culture of research at Imperial that there are standards in place that have teeth. With measles, many nurses don't know how to treat patients suffering from measles in Sub-Saharan Africa [because of the gaps in the datasets].						
				10	JS	25/07/2024 10:18
There are processes and policies in place. But in classic Imperial fashion, everything is siloed. Data protection team, Contracts team, Ethics team. Lack of interconnectivity. No systematic checking. My worry is that this potentially exposes us to risk. There is the legislative risk of the ICO coming knocking at our door or the risk of publishing data that is potentially flawed. Lots of people are trying their best but there are gaps in communication which prevent us from connecting the dots.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Trustworthiness

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0088	5		1	JS	24/07/2024 12:36
trusted?						
				2	JS	02/12/2024 10:09
Creating an authoritative source of knowledge.						
				3	JS	24/07/2024 13:57
Open Research is about trustworthiness, speed and scrutiny. Combining data from different places is just practical						
				4	JS	24/07/2024 14:00
Where trust comes from – trust is one of the key points and there are different routes where trust is coming from rather than Open Research alone.						
				5	JS	24/07/2024 14:02
Data is useless if it cannot be trusted.						

Files\\Notes W1 S2 - Openness and Scrutiny in Data Science

Code

Codes\\Assessment

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0025	1		1	JS	29/07/2024 14:17
In open-source projects there is a market by which the software is checked.						

Codes\\Data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.2750	50		1	JS	29/07/2024 13:48
Relativity of data – depends on what data was used for.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	29/07/2024 13:54
Data bias/data correlations/unconscious and unseen bias/historical data.						
				3	JS	29/07/2024 13:55
We only publish what is good.						
				4	JS	08/10/2024 13:45
Difficult because technological landscape changes so quickly. Ethical and copyright issues using media and software (permission, etc.).						
				5	JS	08/10/2024 13:45
How does this apply to software that is being developed?						
				6	JS	08/10/2024 13:45
Open-source software.						
				7	JS	29/07/2024 14:18
Sensitive data – to get the support and guidance you need, you need to go to a lot of different departments/services.						
				8	JS	29/07/2024 14:20
Sensitivity to data, medical data.						
				9	JS	29/07/2024 14:27
Anonymisation in data is very difficult. Pseudonymised data can in combination with other metadata be linked back to individuals.						
				10	JS	29/07/2024 14:28
Data Integrity - the data is of sufficient quality to support decision making (to reach conclusion).						
				11	JS	29/07/2024 14:27
Data quality – accurate, complete, timely.						
				12	JS	29/07/2024 14:27
Accuracy, complete: "first name can be discriminatory in ML models, someone called Mohammed can be discriminated against by ML model just based on correlation data".						
				13	JS	29/07/2024 14:28
Bias in datasets.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				14	JS	29/07/2024 14:28
Can we rely on the data? (cats that fell from 6th floor are more injured than cats falling from higher floors – reason: many cats falling from higher floors died so sample bias).						
				15	JS	29/07/2024 14:29
Can we avoid Bias? Be open, transparent and compliant with data ethics.						
				16	JS	29/07/2024 14:29
We do not need more regulation but more thought.						
				17	JS	29/07/2024 14:30
It was interesting that the focus was on the equality act and things that can be tested in bias (e.g. the Mohammed/John case) rather than different aspect of discrimination.						
				18	JS	02/10/2024 14:09
We have many amazing tools and data, but there needs to be a link to how the data were generated. Some verification to the quality of the data so we can have our own judgement on the quality.						
				19	JS	02/10/2024 14:09
Quality is a subjective measure. Processes for data generation are not standardised – but everyone can have their own judgement. People can engineer bias by trying to avoid bias – especially in medicine. We need to know what we want to collect.						
				20	JS	02/10/2024 14:10
Private company data – there was a trial in early Covid days: private company collected data but only findings were published – then these were retracted because the data were not reliable. Sometimes companies do not have a good track record – we need to work with trusted entities if we cannot have access to data directly.						
				21	JS	02/10/2024 14:10
Trustless mathematics – encryption etc. Cryptographic checks to keep track on the data, and the processing of the data. Content credentials – to avoid generated data such as deep fakes or fake imaging.						
				22	JS	29/07/2024 14:40
How are we keeping the data and what do we do to the data: many people delete outliers without even knowing that those were outliers, people frequently use PCA [Principal Component Analysis] without knowing what this does to the dataset. How can we create the pipeline from data collection to publishing?						
				23	JS	02/10/2024 14:10
To what extent can science and engineering be algorithmicised and, as a result of that, can it be reproducible and trusted?						
				24	JS	02/10/2024 14:14
What do we want to get from the review process? Reviewers usually take data as trusted and only check whether the methods are correct rather than if the research can be trusted.						
				25	JS	31/07/2024 10:09
EU – data should be shared for common good.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				26	JS	31/07/2024 10:09
Data anonymisation is hard: identities can be retrieved from combining different datasets for de-anonymisation.						
				27	JS	31/07/2024 10:08
Definition of integrity: where data is most effective.						
				28	JS	31/07/2024 10:08
Data quality (data quality is relative).						
				29	JS	02/10/2024 14:15
Where to make open data available, knowledge and public knowledge of data existence.						
				30	JS	08/10/2024 12:24
Data processing procedure, trace of data input/data source – started using GitHub for traceability but full potential unrealised in terms of reproducibility.						
				31	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
Data sensitivity – threshold on degree of data openness – how to determine allowable openness in health sector.						
				32	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
When data is too easily de-anonymised, there must be a restriction to be published (e.g. Number of sample in data).						
				33	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
Tension between privacy and data usefulness – mother–baby link – e.g.: mother's historical health issues can be used to infer the baby's potential health issues – code for inference can be made public but not sensitive data.						
				34	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
Requires framework for detecting bias – and latency of detecting biases vs. impact in terms of real-world consequences.						
				35	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
Infrastructure is main barrier for open data – needs to be easier to annotate meta-data – needs to minimise human time and workload – hard for an external community to understand data.						
				36	JS	02/10/2024 14:17
In terms of infrastructure cost – knowledge of lifecycle of data – when [CRUD operations needs to be done in databases] – needs consciousness of end-users to manage deletion over a long-term period to manage size of data to minimise required capacity of storage [CRUD – Creation, Read, Updates and Deletion of data].						
				37	JS	02/10/2024 14:17
Interpretation of data is affected by data collection process – e.g.: different research(er) methodology in data collection can affect interpretation (data treatment is sensitive for result interpretations) - data treatment needs to be consciously done as it affects the interpretation of results through the quality of raw data – a historical log of data lifecycle is needed to be documented – attitude of researcher needs to be changed.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				38	JS	29/07/2024 15:06
				The scrutiny of data in clinical research. When one goes to the site of where the collection of data was done, there is some confusion about what the source of the data is. Is it the CT scan, is it the analysis of the scan in the sheet, etc. There are still questions about what the source of the data is, and this is not really improving.		
				39	JS	29/07/2024 15:07
				Source data – the first place that data exists. There are more opportunities for errors to occur when we move away from the data source.		
				40	JS	29/07/2024 15:11
				The problem with the "university (open) vs. commercial (closed)" debate is less about data, but also the methods that are developed within universities that are then used by commercial actors that do not disclose how they work at scale and how exactly they are further developed. This means the original ideator of the method from academia does not have the information on the performance of such methods in the real setting, which would help drive further innovation. This disbalance is also about talent, as people do not want to do research at universities as data is locked up in companies.		
				41	JS	29/07/2024 15:11
				"We produce data, talent and algorithms for the good of humanity; but all of it ends up being locked up in three companies. I don't have the answers to fix this tilted disbalance, but we all need to think about this deeply".		
				42	JS	29/07/2024 15:12
				The more you go into the detail of data, the variability, variations and uncertainty increases.		
				43	JS	29/07/2024 15:13
				Commercial institutions get use of open data, but they do not have to open their own data. There are no incentives for companies to open up their closed-boxed applications to help academics understand how things work.		
				44	JS	29/07/2024 15:14
				With CT scan data, there's a clear question of, what is the original source of the data? Is it the CT scan itself; or is there even something even more fundamental, as the image is already processed in some way.		
				45	JS	29/07/2024 15:15
				If we are to recognise that errors exist, the question then becomes how do we go about measuring them in the first place, spotting them out and making use of them to drive uncertainty measurement? Even just have an initial flagging mechanism to inform further investigation. Metadata of how the data was acquired could potentially help here.		
				46	JS	29/07/2024 15:16
				There is not much we can do in academia to deal with the problem of these big companies. There needs to be better governance to deal with how to open data from commercial companies.		
				47	JS	29/07/2024 15:17
				Domain specific problem around null publishing/negative result publishing. For something like clinical trials, where there is a clear protocol to follow, it makes sense to publish negative results; for other fields, such as computing/electronics where one mostly tries out things, it's not clear what the negative data would be. In the extreme, one would have to release their lab book completely.		
				48	JS	02/10/2024 14:20
				Malicious data is not a concern as highlighted in the introductory talk. You need to have context to accompany the dataset. How do you normalise gender disparities? This leads to the question of how regulatory forces work.		
				49	JS	02/10/2024 14:20
				As opposed to creating more bureaucracy and governance, there is an institutional opportunity to create an institutional framework to apply.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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50 JS 29/07/2024 15:27

There is an assumption that open-source data is inferior in some way to proprietary data. "If it was high quality, why wouldn't it be monetized?"

Codes\\Data\Data challenges

No 0.1857 27

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:27

Anonymisation in data is very difficult. Pseudonymised data can in combination with other metadata be linked back to individuals.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:28

Bias in datasets.

3 JS 29/07/2024 14:28

Can we rely on the data? (cats that fell from 6th floor are more injured than cats falling from higher floors – reason: many cats falling from higher floors died so sample bias).

4 JS 29/07/2024 14:29

Can we avoid Bias? Be open, transparent and compliant with data ethics.

5 JS 29/07/2024 14:29

We do not need more regulation but more thought.

6 JS 29/07/2024 14:30

It was interesting that the focus was on the equality act and things that can be tested in bias (e.g. the Mohammed/John case) rather than different aspect of discrimination.

7 JS 02/10/2024 14:10

Private company data – there was a trial in early Covid days: private company collected data but only findings were published – then these were retracted because the data were not reliable. Sometimes companies do not have a good track record – we need to work with trusted entities if we cannot have access to data directly.

8 JS 29/07/2024 14:40

How are we keeping the data and what do we do to the data: many people delete outliers without even knowing that those were outliers, people frequently use PCA [Principal Component Analysis] without knowing what this does to the dataset. How can we create the pipeline from data collection to publishing?

9 JS 02/10/2024 14:10

To what extent can science and engineering be algorithmicised and, as a result of that, can it be reproducible and trusted?

10 JS 31/07/2024 10:09

EU – data should be shared for common good.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				11	JS	02/10/2024 14:15
				Where to make open data available, knowledge and public knowledge of data existence.		
				12	JS	08/10/2024 12:24
				Data processing procedure, trace of data input/data source – started using GitHub for traceability but full potential unrealised in terms of reproducibility.		
				13	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
				Requires framework for detecting bias – and latency of detecting biases vs. impact in terms of real-world consequences.		
				14	JS	02/10/2024 14:16
				Infrastructure is main barrier for open data – needs to be easier to annotate meta-data – needs to minimise human time and workload – hard for an external community to understand data.		
				15	JS	02/10/2024 14:17
				In terms of infrastructure cost – knowledge of lifecycle of data – when [CRUD operations needs to be done in databases] – needs consciousness of end-users to manage deletion over a long-term period to manage size of data to minimise required capacity of storage [CRUD – Creation, Read, Updates and Deletion of data].		
				16	JS	02/10/2024 14:17
				Interpretation of data is affected by data collection process – e.g.: different research(er) methodology in data collection can affect interpretation (data treatment is sensitive for result interpretations) - data treatment needs to be consciously done as it affects the interpretation of results through the quality of raw data – a historical log of data lifecycle is needed to be documented – attitude of researcher needs to be changed.		
				17	JS	29/07/2024 15:06
				The scrutiny of data in clinical research. When one goes to the site of where the collection of data was done, there is some confusion about what the source of the data is. Is it the CT scan, is it the analysis of the scan in the sheet, etc. There are still questions about what the source of the data is, and this is not really improving.		
				18	JS	29/07/2024 15:07
				Source data – the first place that data exists. There are more opportunities for errors to occur when we move away from the data source.		
				19	JS	29/07/2024 15:11
				The problem with the "university (open) vs. commercial (closed)" debate is less about data, but also the methods that are developed within universities that are then used by commercial actors that do not disclose how they work at scale and how exactly they are further developed. This means the original ideator of the method from academia does not have the information on the performance of such methods in the real setting, which would help drive further innovation. This disbalance is also about talent, as people do not want to do research at universities as data is locked up in companies.		
				20	JS	29/07/2024 15:11
				"We produce data, talent and algorithms for the good of humanity; but all of it ends up being locked up in three companies. I don't have the answers to fix this tilted disbalance, but we all need to think about this deeply".		
				21	JS	29/07/2024 15:12
				The more you go into the detail of data, the variability, variations and uncertainty increases.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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22 JS 29/07/2024 15:13

Commercial institutions get use of open data, but they do not have to open their own data.
There are no incentives for companies to open up their closed-boxed applications to help academics understand how things work.

23 JS 29/07/2024 15:14

With CT scan data, there's a clear question of, what is the original source of the data? Is it the CT scan itself; or is there even something even more fundamental, as the image is already processed in some way.

24 JS 29/07/2024 15:15

If we are to recognise that errors exist, the question then becomes how do we go about measuring them in the first place, spotting them out and making use of them to drive uncertainty measurement? Even just have an initial flagging mechanism to inform further investigation. Metadata of how the data was acquired could potentially help here.

25 JS 29/07/2024 15:16

There is not much we can do in academia to deal with the problem of these big companies.
There needs to be better governance to deal with how to open data from commercial companies.

26 JS 29/07/2024 15:17

Domain specific problem around null publishing/negative result publishing. For something like clinical trials, where there is a clear protocol to follow, it makes sense to publish negative results; for other fields, such as computing/electronics where one mostly tries out things, it's not clear what the negative data would be. In the extreme, one would have to release their lab book completely.

27 JS 02/10/2024 14:20

As opposed to creating more bureaucracy and governance, there is an institutional opportunity to create an institutional framework to apply.

Codes\\Data\Data integrity

No 0.0134 6

1 JS 29/07/2024 13:55

We only publish what is good.

2 JS 08/10/2024 13:45

Difficult because technological landscape changes so quickly.
Ethical and copyright issues using media and software (permission, etc.).

3 JS 08/10/2024 13:45

How does this apply to software that is being developed?

4 JS 08/10/2024 13:45

Open-source software.

5 JS 29/07/2024 14:28

Data Integrity - the data is of sufficient quality to support decision making (to reach conclusion).

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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6 JS 31/07/2024 10:08

Definition of integrity: where data is most effective.

Codes\\Data\Data quality

No 0.0477 9

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:27

Data quality – accurate, complete, timely.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:27

Accuracy, complete: "first name can be discriminatory in ML models, someone called Mohammed can be discriminated against by ML model just based on correlation data".

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:09

We have many amazing tools and data, but there needs to be a link to how the data were generated. Some verification to the quality of the data so we can have our own judgement on the quality.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:09

Quality is a subjective measure. Processes for data generation are not standardised – but everyone can have their own judgement. People can engineer bias by trying to avoid bias – especially in medicine. We need to know what we want to collect.

5 JS 02/10/2024 14:10

Trustless mathematics – encryption etc. Cryptographic checks to keep track on the data, and the processing of the data. Content credentials – to avoid generated data such as deep fakes or fake imaging.

6 JS 02/10/2024 14:14

What do we want to get from the review process? Reviewers usually take data as trusted and only check whether the methods are correct rather than if the research can be trusted.

7 JS 31/07/2024 10:08

Data quality (data quality is relative).

8 JS 02/10/2024 14:20

Malicious data is not a concern as highlighted in the introductory talk. You need to have context to accompany the dataset. How do you normalise gender disparities? This leads to the question of how regulatory forces work.

9 JS 29/07/2024 15:27

There is an assumption that open-source data is inferior in some way to proprietary data. "If it was high quality, why wouldn't it be monetized?"

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data

No 0.0236 6

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:18

Sensitive data – to get the support and guidance you need, you need to go to a lot of different departments/services.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:20

Sensitivity to data, medical data.

3 JS 31/07/2024 10:09

Data anonymisation is hard: identities can be retrieved from combining different datasets for de-anonymisation.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:16

Data sensitivity – threshold on degree of data openness – how to determine allowable openness in health sector.

5 JS 02/10/2024 14:16

When data is too easily de-anonymised, there must be a restriction to be published (e.g. Number of sample in data).

6 JS 02/10/2024 14:16

Tension between privacy and data usefulness – mother–baby link – e.g.: mother's historical health issues can be used to infer the baby's potential health issues – code for inference can be made public but not sensitive data.

Codes\\FAIR principles

Yes 0.0159 5

1 JS 08/10/2024 14:12

Lack of communication between departments and central services at Imperial.

There is no one-size-fits-all.

Each project will have coding standards.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:20

The need to provide the context for the data so that it can be reusable.

3 JS 29/07/2024 14:21

You can make your raw data available but unless you specify the licence ,it is not possible to reuse and validate results.

4 JS 29/07/2024 14:23

Standards and code, and metadata.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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5 JS 02/10/2024 14:18

GitHub repository – publishing Github repository to public instead of creating new GitHub libraries.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Accessibility

No 0.0033 1

1 JS 02/10/2024 14:18

GitHub repository – publishing Github repository to public instead of creating new GitHub libraries.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Interoperability

No 0.0061 2

1 JS 08/10/2024 14:12

Lack of communication between departments and central services at Imperial.

There is no one-size-fits-all.

Each project will have coding standards.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:23

Standards and code, and metadata.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Reusability

No 0.0064 2

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:20

The need to provide the context for the data so that it can be reusable.

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:21

You can make your raw data available but unless you specify the licence ,it is not possible to reuse and valide results.

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.1369 32

1 JS 29/07/2024 13:43

Openness – the data is available to be reviewed and used by others.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	29/07/2024 13:55
Data ethics canvas Open Data Institute. 70-20-10						
				3	JS	02/12/2024 10:15
There is a problem about Intellectual Property and commercialisation. Solutions to promote open software. Containers – IP changes from PhD to Post doc.						
				4	JS	29/07/2024 13:59
Barriers: given the size of the college, the easiest thing to do is to get behind the college policies.						
				5	JS	29/07/2024 14:00
People keep trying to avoid bureaucracy and long discussion etc.						
				6	JS	29/07/2024 14:01
Research data storage.						
				7	JS	29/07/2024 14:01
Issue: storing data is very expensive and it is a paradox with net zero policies.						
				8	JS	29/07/2024 14:02
Amount of data and size of the data – archives.						
				9	JS	29/07/2024 14:04
Policy is such a pain... what the teams are looking for is high quality software.						
				10	JS	29/07/2024 14:02
Lack of communication between departments and central services at Imperial.						
				11	JS	29/07/2024 14:19
Sensitive data – to get the support and guidance you need, you need to go to a lot of different departments/services.						
				12	JS	29/07/2024 14:21
For many subject areas there isn't good infrastructure to share data. Need to use proper metadata in order to share the data.						
				13	JS	29/07/2024 14:21
You can make your raw data available but unless you specify the licence ,it is not possible to reuse and valide results.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				14	JS	28/11/2024 13:42
Researchers software will not scrutinise and how to solve this problem, avoiding box ticking exercise to implement software.						
				15	JS	29/07/2024 14:24
Open data – other people can see and review them.						
				16	JS	29/07/2024 14:25
Ofgem strategy is to capture all data and put them in a central space where all in the organisation (and public) have access to them. Appropriate control in place not to share sensitive and private data (to comply with UK GDPR). How data should be open – open raw data vs open output data.						
				17	JS	08/10/2024 14:29
AllTrials – a campaign for all medical trial data to be published (including negative findings).						
				18	JS	29/07/2024 14:26
EU data act – data should be shared for good where possible with appropriate controls and governance.						
				19	JS	29/07/2024 14:43
It will be a huge barrier to research if we will say that it is necessary to only work with data collected in a specific way. Data from settings with economical disadvantages may be highly valuable.						
				20	JS	02/10/2024 14:14
What can we share across – legally sound to be as open as possible.						
				21	JS	02/10/2024 14:14
Current framework is not set to ensure that the code and data are shared.						
				22	JS	31/07/2024 10:12
Openness of raw data vs. distilled results.						
				23	JS	02/10/2024 14:18
On data openness – data can be maliciously used/use large language models to hallucinate data by training on open data.						
				24	JS	08/10/2024 14:24
Folks that need to publish their data in 2 years (based on their UKRI funding, or something like that), suddenly after those 2 years pass start jolting and saying there is a commercial aspect to it, and a competitive landscape, and so they can't really publish. There might be situations, where the data is not ready, there's IP, there's commercial aspect to it. This agreement of 2 years doesn't seem to be considered.						
				25	JS	08/10/2024 14:24
It seems that this 2 years agreement with funding institutions is sometimes being breached.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				26	JS	29/07/2024 15:16
Universities are about furthering human knowledge, why is it a problem that we open our data for commercial institutions? That's the point and there's a clear flow of knowledge from academia to industry. It doesn't mean it's unfair.						
				27	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
Who published the data? You need to ask questions. Where does it come from? Be critical. Taxpayers pay enormous sums of money for the human genome. If we publish anything related to the human genome, it needs to be open access.						
				28	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
If you want to make data open you have to allocate costs, place in a data repository. We don't have a university solution for storing the raw data that we use to generate the aggregated data. We have a retention policy that we're supposed to keep research data for 10 years but we don't have the infrastructure to match that. We don't have a solution. And part of the challenge is cost. That is a part that is being overlooked. And that will affect whether data is robust, reliable.						
				29	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
There is nothing for sensitive or large datasets. The only solution is "pay for it yourself".						
				30	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
So you get yourself an external hard drive and it's highly inefficient.						
				31	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
The policy is left up to my own interpretation. This will lead to unintended consequences.						
				32	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
In computing we don't have a space for a data scientist or curator. Anyone can do it but it's not a job and it's not recognised or incentivised.						
Codes\\Open Research\Obstacles to Open Research						
	No	0.0842	19			
				1	JS	02/12/2024 10:15
There is a problem about Intellectual Property and commercialisation.						
Solutions to promote open software. Containers – IP changes from PhD to Post doc.						
				2	JS	29/07/2024 13:59
Barriers: given the size of the college, the easiest thing to do is to get behind the college policies.						
				3	JS	29/07/2024 14:00
People keep trying to avoid bureaucracy and long discussion etc.						
				4	JS	29/07/2024 14:01
Research data storage.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	29/07/2024 14:01
Issue: storing data is very expensive and it is a paradox with net zero policies.						
				6	JS	29/07/2024 14:02
Amount of data and size of the data – archives.						
				7	JS	29/07/2024 14:04
Policy is such a pain... what the teams are looking for is high quality software.						
				8	JS	29/07/2024 14:02
Lack of communication between departments and central services at Imperial.						
				9	JS	29/07/2024 14:19
Sensitive data – to get the support and guidance you need, you need to go to a lot of different departments/services.						
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				11	JS	29/07/2024 14:43
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				12	JS	02/10/2024 14:14
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				13	JS	08/10/2024 14:24
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				14	JS	08/10/2024 14:24
It seems that this 2 years agreement with funding institutions is sometimes being breached.						
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				16	JS	08/10/2024 16:14
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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17 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

So you get yourself an external hard drive and it's highly inefficient.

18 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

The policy is left up to my own interpretation. This will lead to unintended consequences.

19 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

In computing we don't have a space for a data scientist or curator. Anyone can do it but it's not a job and it's not recognised or incentivised.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Yes 0.0526 13

1 JS 29/07/2024 13:43

Openness – the data is available to be reviewed and used by others.

2 JS 29/07/2024 13:55

Data ethics canvas Open Data Institute.
70-20-10

3 JS 29/07/2024 14:21

You can make your raw data available but unless you specify the licence ,it is not possible to reuse and validate results.

4 JS 28/11/2024 13:42

Researchers software will not scrutinise and how to solve this problem, avoiding box ticking exercise to implement software.

5 JS 29/07/2024 14:24

Open data – other people can see and review them.

6 JS 29/07/2024 14:25

Ofgem strategy is to capture all data and put them in a central space where all in the organisation (and public) have access to them. Appropriate control in place not to share sensitive and private data (to comply with UK GDPR).
How data should be open – open raw data vs open output data.

7 JS 08/10/2024 14:29

AllTrials – a campaign for all medical trial data to be published (including negative findings).

8 JS 29/07/2024 14:26

EU data act – data should be shared for good where possible with appropriate controls and governance.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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9 JS 02/10/2024 14:14

What can we share across – legally sound to be as open as possible.

10 JS 31/07/2024 10:12

Openness of raw data vs. distilled results.

11 JS 02/10/2024 14:18

On data openness – data can be maliciously used/use large language models to hallucinate data by training on open data.

12 JS 29/07/2024 15:16

Universities are about furthering human knowledge, why is it a problem that we open our data for commercial institutions? That's the point and there's a clear flow of knowledge from academia to industry. It doesn't mean it's unfair.

13 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

Who published the data? You need to ask questions. Where does it come from? Be critical. Taxpayers pay enormous sums of money for the human genome. If we publish anything related to the human genome, it needs to be open access.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open access

No 0.0075 1

1 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

Who published the data? You need to ask questions. Where does it come from? Be critical. Taxpayers pay enormous sums of money for the human genome. If we publish anything related to the human genome, it needs to be open access.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open code

No 0.0041 1

1 JS 28/11/2024 13:42

Researchers software will not scrutinise and how to solve this problem, avoiding box ticking exercise to implement software.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data

No 0.0387 10

1 JS 29/07/2024 13:55

Data ethics canvas Open Data Institute.
70-20-10

2 JS 29/07/2024 14:21

You can make your raw data available but unless you specify the licence ,it is not possible to reuse and validade results.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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				4	JS	29/07/2024 14:25
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				7	JS	02/10/2024 14:14
What can we share across – legally sound to be as open as possible.						
				8	JS	31/07/2024 10:12
Openness of raw data vs. distilled results.						
				9	JS	02/10/2024 14:18
On data openness – data can be maliciously used/use large language models to hallucinate data by training on open data.						
				10	JS	29/07/2024 15:16
Universities are about furthering human knowledge, why is it a problem that we open our data for commercial institutions? That's the point and there's a clear flow of knowledge from academia to industry. It doesn't mean it's unfair.						

Codes\\Peer-review

No	0.0057	3				
			1	JS		08/10/2024 14:36
What is expected from peer review has changed recently. When they						
			2	JS		08/10/2024 14:36
did peer-review						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 08/10/2024 14:36

they could not access the code so he was not sure whether he should reject it or accept it.

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.0384 8

1 JS 29/07/2024 14:22

Positive professional services do quality check for compliant software

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:17

Interpretation of data is affected by data collection process – e.g.: different research(er) methodology in data collection can affect interpretation (data treatment is sensitive for result interpretations) - data treatment needs to be consciously done as it affects the interpretation of results through the quality of raw data – a historical log of data lifecycle is needed to be documented – attitude of researcher needs to be changed.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:18

Involving patients and public during conception of research questions [and even across the whole range of research lifecycle activities] – inclusion of public as a "stakeholder" in the research outcome.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:18

A good and strong point at Imperial is using GitHub for research software.

5 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

So that's a good reason to make data open, so that the research community can scrutinise.

6 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

But also taxpayers ultimately pay for this data.

7 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

It's a fine line because the university want to put in good policies but academics also need some level of freedom.

8 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

Goldacre review. The findings said that data needed expertise to curate data and that we needed to train people.

Codes\\Sustainability

No 0.0159 2

1 JS 02/10/2024 14:14

It is not sustainable to increase data storage. Researchers in developing countries can be disadvantaged, but it does not mean that their data are less reliable.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 02/10/2024 14:17

In terms of infrastructure cost – knowledge of lifecycle of data – when [CRUD operations needs to be done in databases] – needs consciousness of end-users to manage deletion over a long-term period to manage size of data to minimise required capacity of storage [CRUD – Creation, Read, Updates and Deletion of data].

Codes\\Transparency

No 0.0330 4

1 JS 29/07/2024 13:44

Transparency – we are honest and clear about the data we have and how we have used it.

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:20

The problem is that you take raw data and create metadata. You should be transparent about how the data is processed and manipulated. This plays out in debates about open source versus closed and proprietary data. Historical data also needs to occasionally be adjusted to apply in modern contexts.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:21

Open data generally may raise issues about lack of liability if it is not commercially "owned". But in research contexts this may be different. Speaking of incentives, I am not evaluated on how my software is developed. This is different to data that is developed in open source as it needs to be properly documented.

4 JS 08/10/2024 16:14

Grants have been mentioned a lot. Is this generally something that is being asked a lot through the course of applying for funding? Are funders asking for this openness and transparency more? Can funders make costs more readily for data storage? It sounds like you are not finding that space.

Codes\\Trustworthiness

No 0.0187 3

1 JS 02/10/2024 14:10

We can argue whether more transparent means more trustworthy. There is still human bias.

2 JS 29/07/2024 15:12

There should be qualitative checks of clinical equipment to ensure that the processing is accurate and correct to ensure that if that is the first step of processing and the processed data is the source data, we can trust it.

3 JS 29/07/2024 15:13

Uncertainty about processing/analysing data is present with both humans and machines; as humans might also might have trouble making decisions between inconclusive samples (for instance, in a classification task) similar to ML [Machine Learning] models.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Files\\Notes W1 S3 - Data in Decision Making and Society

Code

Codes\\AI

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References
No	0.0390	9

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
1	JS	31/07/2024 12:05

People are nowadays more aware of AI because now they can play with it [ChatGPT] freely. So AI now has a sort of bad reputation.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
2	JS	02/10/2024 14:31

Keep principal investigator conscious of AI (pros and cons of AI) when applying for grant applications.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
3	JS	02/10/2024 14:31

Time perception, research used to inform AI on time.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
4	JS	02/10/2024 14:32

AI has garbage in – garbage out principal – input and mode.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
5	JS	31/07/2024 12:10

AI has huge potential but suffers from implicit biases due to the garbage in – garbage out principal for data-driven AI
Easy for AI to suffer from bias due to data pollution during training.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
6	JS	05/08/2024 10:25

DeepMind had a recent paper that one can outperform physics-based weather forecast prediction models – where the AI model was able to learn parts of physics not present in the traditional models.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
7	JS	05/08/2024 10:28

You need a series of very complicated prompts to use these LLMs [Large Language Models] for specific applications where they could perform on-par or outperform humans.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
8	JS	05/08/2024 10:59

With the use of ML [Machine Learning] emulators for simulations, folks will trust the outputs of such ML models, which is so far away from the actual physical experiment.

Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
9	JS	05/08/2024 10:59

With such ML emulators/simulations, one needs to be sure to know what question they are asking and whether their model gives accurate description in the scenarios (problem space) of interest.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Assessment

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0071	2		1	JS	02/10/2024 14:34

Encouraging surveys to increase sample quantity introduces bias [surveyors are less serious in their feedback] as well.

				2	JS	05/08/2024 11:13
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Austerity paper which was highly cited was flagged by a PhD student for having an error. Reinhard-Rogoff case.

Codes\\Bias (data, model...)

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0473	6		1	JS	02/10/2024 14:33

Bias in chemical engineering – e.g.: raw materials are complex, but possesses subtleties, needs to define threshold during chemical processing – e.g.: toxic compounds, when accumulated can be dangerous, especially when chem industry is self-regulated, no clear threshold – perception and understanding.

				2	JS	02/10/2024 14:33
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Complex processes that would require assumptions when creating models needs to be stated clearly, rather than stated with strong certainty in literature (research articles) - AI bias needs to be considered – when complexity arises in chemistry, things being described by the "dominant" compound.

				3	JS	08/10/2024 15:08
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Graduate school designer – educate the graduate courses through survey feedback – imbalance of survey quantities – low sample reflect poorer reliability – to address, need to go back to main subject matter expert – need a robust set of methodologies to educate decision making.

				4	JS	02/10/2024 14:34
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Historical bias leads to students giving survey based on past experience rather than actual lecture experience although lecturers were different from previous years.

				5	JS	31/07/2024 12:17
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Examples of biases in surveys – low quantity of survey leads to poor reliability in conclusion. However, efforts to encourage survey participation induces biases too.

				6	JS	05/08/2024 11:04
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Survival bias. If patients no longer participate in clinical trials for whatever reason, that data is no longer recorded. Incomplete dataset. Analogy to market crashing and collapsing. If I see a trajectory of lung functions that go down and the survival plots show that a group people will die, that provides vital context.

Codes\\Collaboration

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0194	2		1	JS	02/10/2024 14:30

Accepting co-design. Public responses [in questionnaires] might not be accurate. Some investigators may believe that survey data are unreliable. People often do not have attention to detail – for example if researcher asks if they took any drugs they might answer no even if they took paracetamol in the morning [they do no consider paracetamol to be a drug]

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 31/07/2024 12:24

You need technologists (analysts) and domain-experts to help analyse and understand data. One needs a mix of that ideally, a cross-over of people having both expertise. There's some imbalance of the skillset. One needs a culture of all these expertise working together.

Codes\\Data

Yes 0.2090 47

1 JS 31/07/2024 11:19

Barriers: bureaucracy.

2 JS 31/07/2024 11:20

Real-time responses to outbreaks: how to manage that?

3 JS 31/07/2024 11:21

Dataset must be manually reviewed.

4 JS 31/07/2024 11:21

How to provide domain-specific curation?

5 JS 31/07/2024 11:24

Where does the responsibility of the researcher end – there is a disclaimer saying "this is what we found do with it what you will".

6 JS 31/07/2024 11:24

Evidence and context – this is what the science says, about this scenario under these assumptions.

7 JS 31/07/2024 11:24

In terms of clinical trials – they have a separate dataset; according to the research, you are able to tailor the data you need – data integrity and how do you make sure that the data entered is correct.

8 JS 31/07/2024 11:24

Audits in term of patient data.

9 JS 31/07/2024 11:25

Data standards.

10 JS 31/07/2024 11:25

Data on East Africa and disease – mark up model to analyse life expectancies, mistyped dates.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				11	JS	08/10/2024 15:13
				Whole range of statistical approaches to data treatment and researchers have to deal with an inherent level of uncertainty.		
				12	JS	31/07/2024 11:27
				How can you ask for data cleaning in contexts like Ebola outburst in Africa?		
				13	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
				Data quality and assurance – DMPs are asked for funding institutions.		
				14	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
				Quality and assurance in DMP [Data Management Plan] – in certain domains it is clear that people are very sure about what that means, in others they have no clue.		
				15	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
				Data providers should provide good quality data, but we are not in the position to ask for that.		
				16	JS	31/07/2024 11:31
				Missing data is the norm – positive observations with huge amount of missing data.		
				17	JS	31/07/2024 11:31
				There are always a lot of biases in health care.		
				18	JS	31/07/2024 11:34
				Research data analysis – equity. Global South and difficulty to publish.		
				19	JS	31/07/2024 11:35
				There aren't facilities or the facilities are not there to do it rapidly in the global south?		
				20	JS	02/10/2024 14:23
				How can you [objectively] test for reliability?		
				21	JS	08/10/2024 15:19
				There is already a bias from regulatory point of view, in clinical settings you cannot take [use] machine decision. It might be not a question about Open Research but rather on what people do. Financial inclusivity – it is not legal to act on a decision that was generated by AI (for example in insurance business) but we cannot prove that it is not being done.		
				22	JS	08/10/2024 15:20
				Economists and people in finance work in this way [they use AI models for decision making].		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				23	JS	02/10/2024 14:24
				In chemistry, there is a lack of usable data. In chemistry there is a lack of reliable data for (ML) training purposes. There is a movement to find good ideas in previously published data from previous research articles.		
				24	JS	31/07/2024 11:45
				As long as you can explain the model, I do not see any issue with the [biased] data or that the AI causes issues. "AI model can be capturing real biology, but that is not necessarily what we want to do". Rejecting AI only because it seems scary does not mean that we should not be using it.		
				25	JS	31/07/2024 11:53
				There can also be bad ways of collecting data outside of AI/ML domain. For example, during Covid it was discovered that sensors to measure oxygen-blood levels do not work well with darker skins.		
				26	JS	02/10/2024 14:24
				Designing algorithm for finding harmful molecules is not a problem with the AI/ML but rather problem with the intent itself. Using the same introduction in [many different] papers that was written by humans was not a problem, but now when it is written by AI [across many papers] it seems to be a problem – self-plagiarism [now plagiarism with AI]. Scraping data [on the internet] relating to drug volume sizes is easier to do than manually collecting the information but it can lead to that could be avoided by a simple visual check. But collecting data manually can also introduce the same mistakes. A solution could be to provide the code that was used to do the data scraping so that reviewers can check its robustness.		
				27	JS	02/10/2024 14:30
				We need to look to socio-economic data in research.		
				28	JS	02/10/2024 14:31
				Historical data affects bias in AI training – needs data from diverse use groups to remedy bias.		
				29	JS	31/07/2024 12:10
				Data have to be traceable to determine reliability and quality of data to train AI.		
				30	JS	31/07/2024 12:21
				When it comes to creating data by observation, what seems true to one person might be very different to someone else.		
				31	JS	31/07/2024 12:22
				The quality of data has changed in aeronautics, there has been a shift from using wind tunnel as the standard to computational fluid dynamics. Aircraft manufactures would believe CFD simulations and use them as the ground truth.		
				32	JS	31/07/2024 12:22
				When using software, one also needs to look into whether that software doesn't leak your data. It might be reliable to produce the intended results, but it would lead to security risks.		
				33	JS	31/07/2024 12:23
				If your data is more reproducible, it is probably more reliable		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				34	JS	05/08/2024 10:18
				There need to be some risk assessment measure to evaluate how confident can one be in a model, or for what specific applications and situations		
				35	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
				There's a trade-off for prioritising what to de-bug. If one wanted to completely de-bug Linux, the entire staff of Imperial would not be enough. One needs to make sure that software is reliable for the intended use – but for some other use, it might not be. The question is how much does one prioritise to cover all the edge cases. What is the unexpected disruption?		
				36	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
				If we make it super difficult for people to develop very safe and reliable code, they might go elsewhere and develop it somewhere else – where they no longer comply to a high standard of reliability and security – just to make it easier for themselves.		
				37	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
				Have the algorithm and the data separately to be able to evaluate them separately.		
				38	JS	05/08/2024 10:21
				Most ML models can be probabilistic and thus give uncertainty estimation, confidence interval estimation.		
				39	JS	05/08/2024 10:25
				We are focusing on quality of ML model outputs, but we should also not forget about holding accountable the medical workforce that might also be making mistakes. It seems as though we might have higher standards for ML models than for the workforce and health practitioners.		
				40	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
				There are certain types of encryption which allow users to perform operations on the encrypted data rather than on the data itself. Zero-trust code. How can we use microservices for algorithms instead of modules in a trusted and safe way?		
				41	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
				How to codify a chain-of-trust for critical libraries so that we can trust them and their reliability? Blockchain technologies might be useful here.		
				42	JS	05/08/2024 11:05
				It's not really a problem of one discipline. Domain knowledge plus evaluation metrics [for auditing data] are what we need to pay close attention to. In terms of quality, you look at how the data are distributed. Are the correlations consistent within different sets of data?		
				43	JS	05/08/2024 11:05
				You can also take an external dataset and apply the same model.		
				44	JS	05/08/2024 11:05
				This is what I was referring to by "utility". Quality and utility are two different ideas.		
				45	JS	05/08/2024 11:07
				This [process of documenting all steps when collecting a dataset] is difficult for individual researchers to balance and manage.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				46	JS	05/08/2024 11:12
There is a blood bank test that is intended to identify markers for people with Dementia. What do we do with that knowledge? That could be used for negative consequences [i.e. just because we can do it, doesn't mean we always should?].						
				47	JS	05/08/2024 11:12
Post office scandal. We need some accountability.						
Codes\\Data\Data challenges						
	No	0.1458	31			
				1	JS	31/07/2024 11:19
Barriers: bureaucracy.						
				2	JS	31/07/2024 11:20
Real-time responses to outbreaks: how to manage that?						
				3	JS	31/07/2024 11:21
How to provide domain-specific curation?						
				4	JS	31/07/2024 11:24
Where does the responsibility of the researcher end – there is a disclaimer saying "this is what we found do with it what you will".						
				5	JS	31/07/2024 11:25
Data standards.						
				6	JS	31/07/2024 11:25
Data on East Africa and disease – mark up model to analyse life expectancies, mistyped dates.						
				7	JS	08/10/2024 15:13
Whole range of statistical approaches to data treatment and researchers have to deal with an inherent level of uncertainty.						
				8	JS	31/07/2024 11:27
How can you ask for data cleaning in contexts like Ebola outburst in Africa?						
				9	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
Quality and assurance in DMP [Data Management Plan] – in certain domains it is clear that people are very sure about what that means, in others they have no clue.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				10	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
				Data providers should provide good quality data, but we are not in the position to ask for that.		
				11	JS	31/07/2024 11:31
				Missing data is the norm – positive observations with huge amount of missing data.		
				12	JS	31/07/2024 11:31
				There are always a lot of biases in health care.		
				13	JS	31/07/2024 11:34
				Research data analysis – equity. Global South and difficulty to publish.		
				14	JS	31/07/2024 11:35
				There aren't facilities or the facilities are not there to do it rapidly in the global south?		
				15	JS	02/10/2024 14:23
				How can you [objectively] test for reliability?		
				16	JS	08/10/2024 15:19
				There is already a bias from regulatory point of view, in clinical settings you cannot take [use] machine decision. It might be not a question about Open Research but rather on what people do. Financial inclusivity – it is not legal to act on a decision that was generated by AI (for example in insurance business) but we cannot prove that it is not being done.		
				17	JS	08/10/2024 15:20
				Economists and people in finance work in this way [they use AI models for decision making].		
				18	JS	02/10/2024 14:24
				In chemistry, there is a lack of usable data. In chemistry there is a lack of reliable data for (ML) training purposes. There is a movement to find good ideas in previously published data from previous research articles.		
				19	JS	31/07/2024 11:45
				As long as you can explain the model, I do not see any issue with the [biased] data or that the AI causes issues. "AI model can be capturing real biology, but that is not necessarily what we want to do". Rejecting AI only because it seems scary does not mean that we should not be using it.		
				20	JS	02/10/2024 14:24
				Designing algorithm for finding harmful molecules is not a problem with the AI/ML but rather problem with the intent itself. Using the same introduction in [many different] papers that was written by humans was not a problem, but now when it is written by AI [across many papers] it seems to be a problem – self-plagiarism [now plagiarism with AI]. Scraping data [on the internet] relating to drug volume sizes is easier to do than manually collecting the information but it can lead to that could be avoided by a simple visual check. But collecting data manually can also introduce the same mistakes. A solution could be to provide the code that was used to do the data scraping so that reviewers can check its robustness.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				21	JS	02/10/2024 14:30
				We need to look to socio-economic data in research.		
				22	JS	02/10/2024 14:31
				Historical data affects bias in AI training – needs data from diverse use groups to remedy bias.		
				23	JS	31/07/2024 12:21
				When it comes to creating data by observation, what seems true to one person might be very different to someone else.		
				24	JS	31/07/2024 12:22
				When using software, one also needs to look into whether that software doesn't leak your data. It might be reliable to produce the intended results, but it would lead to security risks.		
				25	JS	05/08/2024 10:18
				There need to be some risk assessment measure to evaluate how confident can one be in a model, or for what specific applications and situations		
				26	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
				There's a trade-off for prioritising what to de-bug. If one wanted to completely de-bug Linux, the entire staff of Imperial would not be enough. One needs to make sure that software is reliable for the intended use – but for some other use, it might not be. The question is how much does one prioritise to cover all the edge cases. What is the unexpected disruption?		
				27	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
				If we make it super difficult for people to develop very safe and reliable code, they might go elsewhere and develop it somewhere else – where they no longer comply to a high standard of reliability and security – just to make it easier for themselves.		
				28	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
				There are certain types of encryption which allow users to perform operations on the encrypted data rather than on the data itself. Zero-trust code. How can we use microservices for algorithms instead of modules in a trusted and safe way?		
				29	JS	05/08/2024 11:07
				This [process of documenting all steps when collecting a dataset] is difficult for individual researchers to balance and manage.		
				30	JS	05/08/2024 11:12
				There is a blood bank test that is intended to identify markers for people with Dementia. What do we do with that knowledge? That could be used for negative consequences [i.e. just because we can do it, doesn't mean we always should?].		
				31	JS	05/08/2024 11:12
				Post office scandal. We need some accountability.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Data integrity

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	No	0.0098	3	1	JS	31/07/2024 11:24

In terms of clinical trials – they have a separate dataset; according to the research, you are able to tailor the data you need – data integrity and how do you make sure that the data entered is correct.

				2	JS	31/07/2024 11:24
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Audits in term of patient data.

				3	JS	31/07/2024 12:10
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Data have to be traceable to determine reliability and quality of data to train AI.

Codes\\Data\Data quality

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	No	0.0533	13	1	JS	31/07/2024 11:21

Dataset must be manually reviewed.

				2	JS	31/07/2024 11:24
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Evidence and context – this is what the science says, about this scenario under these assumptions.

				3	JS	31/07/2024 11:28
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Data quality and assurance – DMPs are asked for funding institutions.

				4	JS	31/07/2024 11:53
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There can also be bad ways of collecting data outside of AI/ML domain. For example, during Covid it was discovered that sensors to measure oxygen-blood levels do not work well with darker skins.

				5	JS	31/07/2024 12:22
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The quality of data has changed in aeronautics, there has been a shift from using wind tunnel as the standard to computational fluid dynamics. Aircraft manufactures would believe CFD simulations and use them as the ground truth.

				6	JS	31/07/2024 12:23
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If your data is more reproducible, it is probably more reliable

				7	JS	05/08/2024 10:20
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Have the algorithm and the data separately to be able to evaluate them separately.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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8 JS 05/08/2024 10:21

Most ML models can be probabilistic and thus give uncertainty estimation, confidence interval estimation.

9 JS 05/08/2024 10:25

We are focusing on quality of ML model outputs, but we should also not forget about holding accountable the medical workforce that might also be making mistakes. It seems as though we might have higher standards for ML models than for the workforce and health practitioners.

10 JS 05/08/2024 10:27

How to codify a chain-of-trust for critical libraries so that we can trust them and their reliability? Blockchain technologies might be useful here.

11 JS 05/08/2024 11:05

It's not really a problem of one discipline. Domain knowledge plus evaluation metrics [for auditing data] are what we need to pay close attention to. In terms of quality, you look at how the data are distributed. Are the correlations consistent within different sets of data?

12 JS 05/08/2024 11:05

You can also take an external dataset and apply the same model.

13 JS 05/08/2024 11:05

This is what I was referring to by "utility". Quality and utility are two different ideas.

Codes\\FAIR principles

Yes 0.0223 6

1 JS 31/07/2024 11:20

Self-publish – in Imperial repository.
DOI [Digital Object Identifier] process - Symplectic – Spiral – DOI for datasets.

2 JS 31/07/2024 11:22

Data driven models were not always as they are now. These models are more thought through than before. The modelling is very different to the kind of black box they were before.

3 JS 31/07/2024 11:34

Data owners and access issues.

4 JS 31/07/2024 11:33

Data access statement for publishing.

5 JS 25/11/2024 10:16

Look for protocols that may exist elsewhere – there is limited protocol guidance; how to practically follow?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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6 JS 05/08/2024 11:01

If we codify the method, we make it more reproducible, it suddenly becomes something we can challenge (and find negative results in) – rather than just making a subjective observation. If there's a mistake in the methods, I can see where it is.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Accessibility

No 0.0113 4

1 JS 31/07/2024 11:20

Self-publish – in Imperial repository.
DOI [Digital Object Identifier] process - Symplectic – Spiral – DOI for datasets.

2 JS 31/07/2024 11:22

Data driven models were not always as they are now. These models are more thought through than before. The modelling is very different to the kind of black box they were before.

3 JS 31/07/2024 11:34

Data owners and access issues.

4 JS 31/07/2024 11:33

Data access statement for publishing.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Interoperability

No 0.0033 1

1 JS 25/11/2024 10:16

Look for protocols that may exist elsewhere – there is limited protocol guidance; how to practically follow?

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Reusability

No 0.0076 1

1 JS 05/08/2024 11:01

If we codify the method, we make it more reproducible, it suddenly becomes something we can challenge (and find negative results in) – rather than just making a subjective observation. If there's a mistake in the methods, I can see where it is.

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.0458 9

1 JS 31/07/2024 11:34

Decolonising public health repositories.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	02/10/2024 14:23
				Observed data are more reliable than learning from data. Open Research for researchers in fields such as electrical engineering is to publish the schematics of their circuits rather than share the data.		
				3	JS	02/10/2024 14:30
				We are more and more pushed to communicate with public as part of research. Interaction with public is becoming more important [in health research].		
				4	JS	05/08/2024 10:15
				Case study: Boeing. How reliable do our products need to be before we need to go back to the drawing board and re-evaluate. Boeing would not worry about it until the door falls off of an airplane. Again a risk budget assessment.		
				5	JS	05/08/2024 10:26
				Common software packages are well tested, but they are fundamentally black boxes and we need to trust them. We have a more distributed trust system at the moment. The open-source movement has been very helpful in some regards, but we need more robust ways of providing reliability for these packages. There are some parts of Linux that are maintained by a single person.		
				6	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
				There are certain types of encryption which allow users to perform operations on the encrypted data rather than on the data itself. Zero-trust code. How can we use microservices for algorithms instead of modules in a trusted and safe way?		
				7	JS	05/08/2024 10:31
				There's a need for a continuous dialogue with the public about the actual levels of risk (about medical interventions).		
				8	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
				Pipeline pattern – uses conventions used in coding.		
				9	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
				I worked in molecular biology and jumped to coding but it [coding] isn't taught.		

Codes\\Open Research\\Obstacles to Open Research

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0083	2	1	JS	31/07/2024 11:34
			Decolonising public health repositories.		
			2	JS	05/08/2024 10:15
			Case study: Boeing. How reliable do our products need to be before we need to go back to the drawing board and re-evaluate. Boeing would not worry about it until the door falls off of an airplane. Again a risk budget assessment.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Yes	0.0228	4
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1	JS	05/08/2024 10:26
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Common software packages are well tested, but they are fundamentally black boxes and we need to trust them. We have a more distributed trust system at the moment. The open-source movement has been very helpful in some regards, but we need more robust ways of providing reliability for these packages. There are some parts of Linux that are maintained by a single person.

2	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
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There are certain types of encryption which allow users to perform operations on the encrypted data rather than on the data itself. Zero-trust code. How can we use microservices for algorithms instead of modules in a trusted and safe way?

3	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
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Pipeline pattern – uses conventions used in coding.

4	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
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I worked in molecular biology and jumped to coding but it [coding] isn't taught.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open code

No	0.0228	4
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1	JS	05/08/2024 10:26
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Common software packages are well tested, but they are fundamentally black boxes and we need to trust them. We have a more distributed trust system at the moment. The open-source movement has been very helpful in some regards, but we need more robust ways of providing reliability for these packages. There are some parts of Linux that are maintained by a single person.

2	JS	05/08/2024 10:27
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There are certain types of encryption which allow users to perform operations on the encrypted data rather than on the data itself. Zero-trust code. How can we use microservices for algorithms instead of modules in a trusted and safe way?

3	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
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Pipeline pattern – uses conventions used in coding.

4	JS	05/08/2024 11:08
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I worked in molecular biology and jumped to coding but it [coding] isn't taught.

Codes\\Peer-review

No	0.0162	4
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1	JS	02/10/2024 14:34
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Hard to have uniform research culture – in journals, hard for editors to facilitate referees, especially when research quality is hugely variable – bias in social pressure for editors to accept papers – generative AI would increase volume of data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	02/10/2024 14:34
Editor's perspective: they need to ask 20 reviewers to find one available; moreover, it is hard for reviewer to accept responsibility for reviews (due to high workload).						
				3	JS	02/10/2024 14:34
Hard for reviewer to trust data/graph of article manuscript.						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 14:35
Reviewers have their own perspective on articles.						
Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality						
	No	0.0697	16			
				1	JS	31/07/2024 11:23
People are now thinking about the bias of the models, AI and application.						
				2	JS	31/07/2024 11:33
How to fill in the gaps left – describe what you've done and do sensitivity analysis.						
				3	JS	31/07/2024 11:33
Data cleaning and data processing – publish the dataset.						
				4	JS	31/07/2024 11:34
Making sure that we build and collaborate with data providers from the Global South.						
				5	JS	31/07/2024 11:35
Working closely with/for collaborators – working with people and for real situations.						
				6	JS	02/10/2024 14:34
Octopus programme – framework for anonymously uploading research, or hypothesis and progress on research progress will lead to open discussion on ideas – can create a network on how insights / ideas are linked together.						
				7	JS	05/08/2024 10:14
For using simulation/ML emulators, there needs to be some reliable feedback loop to ensure the results are accurate.						
				8	JS	05/08/2024 10:15
One needs to balance the risk budget. The more risk one puts in, the more disruptive they could be. Therefore, Google is now trying out a wide range of things, where there's a lot of risk, we being the subjects as it's our data (the public), but they can do it, as their goal is to still be disruptive and innovative.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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9 JS 05/08/2024 10:18

Nothing really stays the same, things always change. Regulation might happen, but it will always be a case of playing catch-up. TV, mobile phones, messaging were all disruptive and they need to be regulated.

10 JS 05/08/2024 10:29

One has to do a risk assessment for unintended use of software to avoid security risks.

11 JS 05/08/2024 10:30

Case study: Educating people before taking an x-ray and the radiation damage associated being the same as on a long-haul flight makes them much better equipped about the associated risk and thus then taking the x-ray examinations rather than being cautious (especially when those patients were cancer survivors and thus were cautious of radiation causing cancer).

12 JS 05/08/2024 10:31

Log all your methodologies.

13 JS 05/08/2024 11:06

When you collect a dataset, you need to document all the steps you are taking.

14 JS 05/08/2024 11:13

We don't have a culture which supports you if you "fail". Your career suffers. If you have a technology that is patented and is licensed out and it causes harm, legally there are some protections but the reputational damage could potentially sit with the company and the university.

15 JS 02/10/2024 14:41

What systemic changes are needed to embed reliability into applications?

16 JS 02/10/2024 14:41

Well, embracing failure perhaps. Entertaining the idea that the alternative hypothesis might be true.

Codes\\Sustainability

No 0.0165 3

1 JS 02/10/2024 14:40

Have a code logbook. There still doesn't seem to be a very reliable, reproducible electronic logbook for development of code, software and analysing data.

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:40

Comment: Jupyter notebook exists, but it doesn't really offer consistency in terms of the order the code has been executed in, what exact data files have been imported, what version of the package was used, etc.).

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 05/08/2024 11:09

You need an administrator that documents all of these processes. Dates are a common issue. There are different ways for these to be represented and recorded consistently.

Codes\\Transparency

No 0.0298 5

1 JS 31/07/2024 11:53

As long as you can explain the model, I do not see any issue with the [biased] data or that the AI causes issues. "AI model can be capturing real biology, but that is not necessarily what we want to do". Rejecting AI only because it seems scary does not mean that we should not be using it.

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:29

Sometimes they [commercial partners] do not appreciate the importance and impact. Pharma companies might not want to publish negative results, but also may not need to publish positive findings because they want to monetise as much as possible.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:29

Some companies want to monetise every element of a research before they release it as open-source.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:30

We are talking about members of the public and transparency. We can be transparent, but members of the public might not understand some key elements. Sometimes legislations have many exceptions and signing an agreement might not even be useful.

5 JS 05/08/2024 11:09

Transparency will mean something different according to different domains.

Codes\\Trustworthiness

No 0.0352 10

1 JS 02/10/2024 14:31

Designing framework for educating policy makers – dependent on data collection from end-users (individual and firms) - data coming direct demand side consumers of market – data reliability dependent on choice of experiment/survey to generate the data.

2 JS 09/10/2024 10:27

[Importance of minimising false results] Because clinical trials have higher stakes, they will have higher reliability requirements.

3 JS 09/10/2024 10:29

How to identify bias?

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:32

Dependent on design of data collection – use statistical methods (clustering of data, questions).

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	09/10/2024 10:29
ow about self-selection bias?						
				6	JS	02/10/2024 14:33
Self-selection bias can be addressed by having patients follow up.						
				7	JS	05/08/2024 11:00
There's lack of confidence / uncertainty estimation/evaluation of ML models.						
				8	JS	05/08/2024 11:01
In countries where each citizen has an ID, there's a clear level of trust, where we trust that the information about that is only given to the people and agents that need it and there's no exploitation of it.						
				9	JS	05/08/2024 11:11
When you generate a model, the test is when you apply the model to the external database and the model still works. If there are variances that are flagged these can provide clues.						
				10	JS	05/08/2024 11:14
What systemic changes are needed to embed reliability into applications?						

Files\\Notes W2 S1 - Data and AI in decision-making

Code

Codes\\AI

	No	0.2039	34			
				1	JS	07/08/2024 16:32
AI in healthcare diagnoses,						
Benefits: 1) Early detection; 2) Increased accuracy; 3) Personalised treatment.						
				2	JS	02/10/2024 14:43
The name AI is off-putting, it is not real. It could be beneficial to change it.						
				3	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
AI is owned by technology to show patient benefit.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
				The way in which we define AI is not accessible – how can we translate it – The use of tech terms is deterring people to trust AI.		
				5	JS	07/08/2024 16:40
				Dehumanises even your everyday GP service with less and less human contact. This is a way to getting rid of administration.		
				6	JS	07/08/2024 16:41
				We have balance - AI to assist humanity – Fear of the unknown.		
				7	JS	07/08/2024 16:42
				Difference between training and performance.		
				8	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
				AI to acquire the data, the way it is used: data is acquired the same way. AI is used to process the data – currently you don't need to ask patients about that. 95% of the time the patient does not need the radiologist. Tasks where the specialties are not in contact with patient and where AI is already being used.		
				9	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
				I think there should be a much stronger surveillance with AI.		
				10	JS	08/08/2024 09:21
				Regulation – how much red tape is enough; international differences.		
				11	JS	08/08/2024 09:21
				Learning from AI experiences in other sectors outside Health.		
				12	JS	08/08/2024 09:25
				Potential around personalisation.		
				13	JS	08/08/2024 09:26
				AI always need to be vetoed.		
				14	JS	08/08/2024 09:27
				The black box of AI - when the product is proprietary that is secret – there isn't a 3rd party to scrutinise		
				15	JS	02/10/2024 14:46
				AI inequalities across different sectors but raises lots of red flags		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				16	JS	02/10/2024 14:46
				My principle concerns are the disparities and inequalities. It worries me whether AI will feed into the appropriate data.		
				17	JS	02/10/2024 14:46
				I think it is always important to remember that AI is a tool. I have spent my entire working life in IT. Frustration that I have encountered around the excitement for a new tool. We need to not lose sight that it is a tool. I don't think the benefits about AI are as widely known or as widely published as we think. There is a lot of manual work. And AI can be used to cut down the time to handle tasks from 4-5 hours. That is not cutting out a job, that is supporting the traditional role. It's not just about efficiency and money saving.		
				18	JS	02/10/2024 14:47
				It is interesting how AI can detect things. In my case I was recalled for [condition]. I was told that I was in a good place. That there was a lot of discussion as to whether to recall you. That is encouraging. That there is this level of attention which represents some progress.		
				19	JS	08/08/2024 09:45
				Cancer care is holistic. Surgeon and clinicians come together. And AI is a tool. Patients know themselves best, as well. I know that there is a backlog for mammography that women have expressed.		
				20	JS	02/10/2024 16:14
				The definition of AI presented as AI as a tool - data, algorithm branch of computer science focused on creating systems and tasks typically requiring human intelligence - is a very good definition, a calming, balanced definition.		
				21	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
				A lot of exposure to information on hacking, misuse of data in social media/news. We get the idea that AI is taking over but in reality, it is always checked and regulations are in place.		
				22	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
				People might have a fear of AI replacing GP etc. But, we can think of AI as knowledge transferred into another system that can systematically look at tasks and processes.		
				23	JS	08/08/2024 09:57
				Acceptance of using AI will come when the public is exposed to positive case studies.		
				24	JS	09/10/2024 11:19
				AI being an imitation/clone of human – people want an understanding of how humans are making AI better and vis versa – why? As it is relevant for health diagnosis – AI diagnosis in conflict with human health professional – who to trust, AI or human diagnosis? What can AI do for humans? AI seems to be not a "utopia" currently, current state of AI is not interpretable for lay-person.		
				25	JS	09/10/2024 11:21
				AI think of data dictionary, search engine, software program that helps with [decision] / gives answers – e.g.: cancer diagnosis – have various treatments that have complicated ramifications in terms of side-effects due to other [personalised health-care] - AI can be used for algorithm optimisation (linear programming) with an appropriate [cost-function] to minimise.		
				26	JS	09/10/2024 11:23
				No concerns of the AI systems – speaker is familiar with AI tech.		
				27	JS	09/10/2024 11:23
				Ultimate decision is still based on a human clinician – AI will not operate independently – clinician will use AI as a recommendation.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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28 JS 08/08/2024 11:15

Two main advantage of AI: 1) speed and accuracy of diagnosis, 2) with vast data potential for more personalised treatment of patients.

29 JS 08/08/2024 11:15

Cons: data pollution (bias, sparse data), computational bias (insufficient training time [high-cost function, not converged to best solution] - hard to evaluate if trained AI is best AI).

30 JS 08/08/2024 11:16

Question: How patient inform about AI tech used in healthcare?
 Speaker – health care decision has minimal AI – when AI is used – patient will be informed

31 JS 08/08/2024 11:19

Summary of implication on healthcare consent:
 AI can analyse ECG – if insurers get hold of that data, they can evaluate potential health concern of buyers in 10-15 years into the future – charge higher premiums if they are high-risk.

32 JS 02/10/2024 16:21

How does AI improve treatment or speed up NHS service delivery? Concrete examples would be nice.

33 JS 25/11/2024 12:34

Biopsy, which has its risks, doesn't have to be done. But, largely believed that the demand will largely increase than decrease due to diseases being flagged up.

34 JS 25/11/2024 12:35

Earlier stage detections could be made?

Codes\\Bias (data, model...)

No 0.0412 10

1 JS 07/08/2024 16:30

Ai bias in medical system designs
 Data bias
 Algorithmic bias
 Computational bias

2 JS 07/08/2024 16:34

The form is designed for middle age white men – AI bias.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:44

(Bias) is the algorithm diverse, is the analysis diverse?

4 JS 08/08/2024 09:21

Recognising challenges of addressing biases.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	08/08/2024 09:25
Bias in dataset.						
				6	JS	08/08/2024 09:26
Negative side – biases > data set skewed and too many barriers to many people getting involved in consultation and research.						
				7	JS	08/08/2024 09:26
Bias – geographical, accessibility.						
				8	JS	02/10/2024 14:47
My relative has had a triple bypass, I am their carer. With all these apps. You can check your blood. Aren't the older generation being left behind a little? English is also not the first language. They must be isolated.						
				9	JS	08/08/2024 09:46
: With AI, I feel like AI is positive, but because there are so many disparities, With African and Caribbean patients there is a gap in the data. I feel like the group is the least likely to be entered into clinical trials. So maybe AI will be less biased potentially in around 10 years.						
				10	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
Biobank database - example of skewed or biased data. Useful and valuable but we need to be aware of bias.						
Codes\\Collaboration						
	No	0.0387	6			
				1	JS	02/10/2024 14:45
You cannot share data across borders. Some countries say that their data has to be kept in national territory.						
				2	JS	08/08/2024 09:23
System integration across NHS and specialist care; sharing info and trusting patients.						
				3	JS	08/08/2024 09:25
The lessons from different sectors are not being learned, including the health sector – we need to be really clear this is a tool not a toy - fear.						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 14:46
I want to take an optimistic view. There will be outliers as a natural course anyway. But there should always be a role for clinicians.						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:16
A lot of data already exists, example for me specifically, MRI etc.; AI can only add value if it is integrated – AI needs to understand me in the context of all the independent sources that exist.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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6 JS 02/10/2024 16:19

[Participant] mentions experience of radiology. MRI scans being annotated by AI (very time consuming and skilled job for humans), and then being checked and corrected by the radiologists, rather than having to do it all from scratch. So, AI output or flagging being audited by the human experts.

Codes\\Data

Yes 0.0688 15

1 JS 09/10/2024 10:55

surveillance

2 JS 07/08/2024 16:45

There should be an obligation to do surveillance – you would need approval from all patients.

3 JS 07/08/2024 16:45

We have to be very careful about personal data.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:45

There is not too much red tape in AI.

5 JS 02/10/2024 14:45

Data protection is a huge concern - how to rely on insecure systems, who is going to get hold, like insurance?

6 JS 07/08/2024 16:46

Data sharing: patients are not willing to share data – in the hospital I cannot see my info.
Data breach in NHS breach 10 years ago – since then your records are less accessible.

7 JS 08/08/2024 09:23

Data security and privacy – level of trust that does /doesn't exist in health care culture and whether people feel comfortable to share data.

8 JS 08/08/2024 09:24

Regulation, red tape and how that might be creating barriers, and international sharing difficulties.

9 JS 02/10/2024 14:47

GDPR also a huge concern and whether people fully understand the risks involved in inputting data into that.

10 JS 08/08/2024 09:56

Data quality - impacts automation - CRAP IN CRAP out - a lot of effort is required to transform patient experience. We must go back to the source and clean data. Genealogy etc can be incorporated, but the people must give permission to do this.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				11	JS	09/10/2024 11:41
How can we use AI to transform biggest NHS burden? - Best place to start?						
				12	JS	09/10/2024 11:41
GP cannot see detailed patient info - streamlining needed there in NHS. They need to combine primary and secondary care data. But who has access to this data and how can they be integrated?						
				13	JS	08/08/2024 11:18
In the NHS – there are guardians in charge of health data – in charge of data breach prevention – implement procedure by data protection officer in NHS.						
				14	JS	02/10/2024 16:21
How to deal with scarcity of data due to say rarity of disease (e.g. MS) or diseases manifesting in non-common and rare ways? Longer term consequences?						
				15	JS	02/10/2024 16:21
How to ensure data is up-to-date, say with changing lifestyle, diseases, etc.						
Codes\\Data\Data challenges						
	No	0.0367	7			
				1	JS	07/08/2024 16:46
Data sharing: patients are not willing to share data – in the hospital I cannot see my info. Data breach in NHS breach 10 years ago – since then your records are less accessible.						
				2	JS	08/08/2024 09:23
Data security and privacy – level of trust that does /doesn't exist in health care culture and whether people feel comfortable to share data.						
				3	JS	08/08/2024 09:24
Regulation, red tape and how that might be creating barriers, and international sharing difficulties.						
				4	JS	09/10/2024 11:41
How can we use AI to transform biggest NHS burden? - Best place to start?						
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				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:21
How to deal with scarcity of data due to say rarity of disease (e.g. MS) or diseases manifesting in non-common and rare ways? Longer term consequences?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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7 JS 02/10/2024 16:21

How to ensure data is up-to-date, say with changing lifestyle, diseases, etc.

Codes\\Data\Data integrity

No 0.0102 3

1 JS 09/10/2024 10:55

surveillance

2 JS 07/08/2024 16:45

There should be an obligation to do surveillance – you would need approval from all patients.

3 JS 08/08/2024 11:18

In the NHS – there are guardians in charge of health data – in charge of data breach prevention – implement procedure by data protection officer in NHS.

Codes\\Data\Data quality

No 0.0097 1

1 JS 08/08/2024 09:56

Data quality - impacts automation - CRAP IN CRAP out - a lot of effort is required to transform patient experience. We must go back to the source and clean data. Genealogy etc can be incorporated, but the people must give permission to do this.

Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data

No 0.0121 4

1 JS 07/08/2024 16:45

We have to be very careful about personal data.

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:45

There is not too much red tape in AI.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:45

Data protection is a huge concern - how to rely on insecure systems, who is going to get hold, like insurance?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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4 JS 02/10/2024 14:47

GDPR also a huge concern and whether people fully understand the risks involved in inputting data into that.

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

No 0.0585 8

1 JS 08/08/2024 09:20

Ensuring full datasets are comprehensive, representative and recognise lived experience.

2 JS 02/10/2024 14:47

My relative has had a triple bypass, I am their carer. With all these apps. You can check your blood. Aren't the older generation being left behind a little? English is also not the first language. They must be isolated.

3 JS 02/10/2024 14:47

I agree, for some people I know these systems would exclude them from these benefits. How as we get older, are we going to be retain independence/autonomy and manage our own health. And not just elderly people but disabled or neurodivergent people.

4 JS 02/10/2024 14:47

These discussions remind me of occasions where we have had to prepare lessons for neurodiverse students.

5 JS 08/08/2024 09:47

We are also talking about digital poverty. You need to be able to harness the benefits of these AI tools but there is a challenge in the area of language and context where accuracy still seems to be an issue.

6 JS 02/10/2024 16:15

Biased data presents challenges when applied to wider population. How to address this?

7 JS 02/10/2024 16:17

Public involvement is important but language barriers in minority groups exists – as well as cultural and ethnic barriers. We only get info on people from certain sectors of society so our research data is biased - lots of people do not come forward. Important to the NHS to ensure equity in people who come forward in research

8 JS 02/10/2024 16:17

Underserved communities - lack of access. Let us think of covid and the difficulty in getting people to get vaccine. How would we get resources to poorer, marginalised communities?

Codes\\Expectations

Yes 0.0408 8

1 JS 08/08/2024 09:46

How can we empower those communities to take part? How can we also ensure that those clinicians and professionals are aware of those disparities and biases? I am training staff and there needs to be more discussion around ethics.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:14
A lot of exposure to information on hacking, misuse of data in social media/news. We get the idea that AI is taking over but in reality, it is always checked and regulations are in place.						
				3	JS	08/08/2024 09:53
Education, to encourage people to engage. Government push towards diversity - at community level.						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
Do people understand the impact of not taking part in research?						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
Younger people are more aware of AI and research - diverse groups need more work towards engaging in research.						
				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:16
Would concrete examples help people to engage in research?						
				7	JS	02/10/2024 16:16
Yes - as well as more simplified examples so that they can clearly understand benefits and impacts.						
				8	JS	25/11/2024 14:02
Incentives for being involved in research - Imperial newsletter too broad - some specialisation needed by age etc. Help community become interested in AI and ongoing projects.						

Codes\\Expectations\\Information security

No	0.0074	1
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				1	JS	02/10/2024 16:14
A lot of exposure to information on hacking, misuse of data in social media/news. We get the idea that AI is taking over but in reality, it is always checked and regulations are in place.						

Codes\\Expectations\\Patient and Public involvement

No	0.0334	7
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				1	JS	08/08/2024 09:46
How can we empower those communities to take part? How can we also ensure that those clinicians and professionals are aware of those disparities and biases? I am training staff and there needs to be more discussion around ethics.						
				2	JS	08/08/2024 09:53
Education, to encourage people to engage. Government push towards diversity - at community level.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	02/10/2024 16:15
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				7	JS	25/11/2024 14:02
Incentives for being involved in research - Imperial newsletter too broad - some specialisation needed by age etc. Help community become interested in AI and ongoing projects.						

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Yes	0.0199	4				
				1	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
The public needs to be educated.						
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:17
Improved internal communications in Imperial to improve what then goes out to community - integrate internal and external comms.						
				3	JS	02/10/2024 16:17
At what point is public consultation most useful?						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:17
We target areas where we might make the biggest difference - biggest burden on NHS - obesity, diabetes. Use technology to transform those health issues and begin to impact NHS budget in those areas. Right now, 6/10 adults are obese - 40 % children under 11 and 1/5 under 5 are obese.						

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No	0.0199	4				
				1	JS	02/10/2024 14:44
The public needs to be educated.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 02/10/2024 16:17

Improved internal communications in Imperial to improve what then goes out to community - integrate internal and external comms.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:17

At what point is public consultation most useful?

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:17

We target areas where we might make the biggest difference - biggest burden on NHS - obesity, diabetes. Use technology to transform those health issues and begin to impact NHS budget in those areas. Right now, 6/10 adults are obese - 40 % children under 11 and 1/5 under 5 are obese.

Codes\\Reliability

No 0.0214 5

1 JS 08/08/2024 11:07

Negative words spreads faster than positive. How to deal with case studies when the result is bad. Scepticism spreads and that creates difficulty for people to engage and fear to engage.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:20

What questions would you ask of a doctor, researcher or developer about how AI is used in decision-making?

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:20

How fast does AI systems glitches get caught by the clinicians? Human quality checks over AI decisions along the way would increase trust.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:20

AI being assistive rather than being in the driver's seat.

5 JS 25/11/2024 14:06

Humans could be just as wrong [as AI].

Codes\\Transparency

No 0.0326 4

1 JS 08/08/2024 09:20

Being clear about what role AI is playing from the very start of patient process – related to that: training GP's for humanising patient experience : we might need to redesign the patient experience.

2 JS 08/08/2024 11:14

AI has capability but patient needs to be transparent about medical history – speaker hopes AI is not seen as utopia, patients need to be able to interpret AI with scepticism for AI tools too.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 08/08/2024 11:17

Regulation : Can patient opt-out/opt-in of AI tech-use?

Speaker (healthcare clinician / researcher) – regulated medical technology – consent – a minimized level of required procedure for approval for regulated medical technology – in contrast with research – consent is required to be explained in detail.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:21

Concern that AI is more of a black box, not transparent and known enough by public, and possibly not probable by 3rd party

Codes\\Trustworthiness

No 0.0078 1

1 JS 08/08/2024 11:19

How to build trust in NHS on being guardians of patient data?

Public needs to understand how AI uses data – there is also the need for healthcare practitioner to actually understand AI algorithms.

Files\\Notes W2 S2 - What makes AI trustworthy

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No 0.0253 6

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:42

Is AI enhancing? Has it been given more chances to make it right?

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:42

Accountability in patient decision that doesn't happen with AI.

3 JS 08/08/2024 14:13

AI as not being accountable.

Blackboxing also in human decision making.

4 JS 08/08/2024 14:18

There are trials and tests on AI – operation by robots and doctor – asking questions about the patient experience

5 JS 02/10/2024 16:45

We are not very good at asking doctors to justify their decisions. I just want to understand their rationale in order to reach my own informed decision. You walk out and think "why didn't I ask that?".

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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6 JS 08/08/2024 15:26

Trust generated by accountability – accountability lies with the creator of AI tools.

Codes\AI

No 0.1150 19

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:37

It's like the Internet when it first started.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:38

It's interesting how you frame it – language.

Would you be happy if AI examines your mammography / if we also use AI because the results might be better? You need to convey what the thing is going to do. Specialties and the impact

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:41

Mammography and interpretation: you can make an informed decision but it is a probability game.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:41

Can AI be more accurate?

5 JS 02/10/2024 16:41

If you get more opinions you get a more informed and clear decision.

6 JS 02/10/2024 16:42

It may be beneficial using AI as a complement not one or the other.

7 JS 02/10/2024 16:42

Second opinion.

8 JS 08/08/2024 14:18

Reflections/questions whether we hold AI to a higher standard because it's new in comparison with doctors.

9 JS 08/08/2024 14:19

There needs to be more showing-off of successful stories, not only what went wrong.

10 JS 02/10/2024 16:44

Yes, could you use AI to get appropriate personalisation?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				11	JS	02/10/2024 16:44
There is so much promise for AI to be used for personalised medicine. It is really hard for patients to see any specialists now and get advice about dosage.						
				12	JS	02/10/2024 16:44
If AI had been a feature of the decision-making it could be more empowering for the patient in understanding the decision process and it would feel more transparent						
				13	JS	02/10/2024 16:44
If there was an AI that would transcribe notes for patients						
				14	JS	02/10/2024 16:45
My kids react differently to me about all of this. While I would have preferred face to face, some people may prefer an AI interface.						
				15	JS	02/10/2024 16:45
I think we're just trying to balance the discussion by identifying some of the positive aspects. We talked a lot about mistrust in the beginning. When it's just a calculator (low risk), I'm fully on board. Where there are more complex decisions involved (high stakes) I will have questions.						
				16	JS	02/10/2024 16:46
AI is the way forward - but from experience outsourcing of complex design away from top consultants in UK in my industry, the brainpower of consultants began to decline because they felt underused.						
				17	JS	08/08/2024 15:25
Speaker (long medical history with complexity) - medical practitioner can't give a cohesive diagnosis – how can AI be expected to? [especially when AI is trained in the supervised learning manner] - speaker is wondering if AI improves or decreases the decision-making accuracy of diagnosis? - speaker is worried about data pollution by data generated by generative AI/results of supervised learning AI.						
				18	JS	08/08/2024 15:27
AI is introduced in stages: doctor -> doctor + AI -> AI – currently at doctor + AI stage. Doctor intervening can improve trustworthiness. The closed-loop interaction of AI and real-world with data in between - this system is very rare due to regulations.						
				19	JS	08/08/2024 15:32
AI hours could be less costly than human hours. So, while clinicians visits are now 10 mins long, AI can be made to explain in great details how it arrived at its decisions. Cohesive explanations to various diverse questions can be asked over an AI decision and can be used to feel confident in the AI.						

Codes\\Collaboration

No	0.0196	3				
				1	JS	02/10/2024 16:43
Almost like pattern recognition. So when there is a new patient, that information goes in and there is a calculation of probability.						
				2	JS	08/08/2024 14:57
Even though we support the AI -human partnership - the more we automate and use AI, people use less brainpower overtime an imbalance in relationship develops so it is no longer an equal partnership						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 02/10/2024 16:47

Use of AI for hip replacement surgery but preferred that option due to accuracy of surgical robot. - good example of AI-human partnership.

Codes\\Data

Yes 0.0738 11

1 JS 09/10/2024 15:27

Social media is dangerous because it doesn't give an in-depth picture. Using social media into simplified diagnosis.

2 JS 08/08/2024 14:18

We can't control our data – ownership over the data.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

We're not really at the point where we have clear and consistent databases.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

One of these things that we teach is about confidentiality and security. You would need to give your consent. There will be non-identifiable data.

5 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

I also find data breaches concerning.

6 JS 08/08/2024 15:04

Individual human data is more difficult to deal with - the only way to validate human data is by going through patients themselves. There needs to be an educational element and some data cleansing of human data by going to the patient.

7 JS 08/08/2024 15:04

Every individual would have to say that they validate this data.

8 JS 08/08/2024 15:04

We are the ultimate arbitrators over our data. Until we can see all the health data held on and validate it and sign off on it being used, the data cannot be used to its fullest. The public needs a sense of ownership over our data.

9 JS 08/08/2024 15:24

Integrity of data – needs a holistic source of data [different data modalities] - accuracy of data – trust of AI also related to responsibility of human patients to be honest and handle their data in the right way [updating their healthcare data frequently and preventing personal biases].

10 JS 08/08/2024 15:30

Data ownership – individual owning data – gives control to external company on the decision of own individual consent

Cons: If data ownership is under individual control:

1. hard for regulatory body to make educated decision;
2. individual may not be aware of segments of data that are relevant to their medical condition.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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11 JS 08/08/2024 15:34

Central collation and storage of data would reduce doubts on which data was used, as one would be assured that all data from relevant and appropriate channels (NHS, GPs, scan centers) was used.

Codes\\Data\Data challenges

No 0.0302 5

1 JS 08/08/2024 14:18

We can't control our data – ownership over the data.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

We're not really at the point where we have clear and consistent databases.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

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2. individual may not be aware of segments of data that are relevant to their medical condition.

Codes\\Data\Data integrity

No 0.0201 2

1 JS 08/08/2024 15:24

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2 JS 08/08/2024 15:34

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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Data quality

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0048	1	1	JS	09/10/2024 15:27	

Social media is dangerous because it doesn't give an in-depth picture. Using social media into simplified diagnosis.

Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0186	3	1	JS	02/10/2024 16:43	

One of these things that we teach is about confidentiality and security. You would need to give your consent. There will be non-identifiable data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0186	3	2	JS	08/08/2024 15:04	

Individual human data is more difficult to deal with - the only way to validate human data is by going through patients themselves. There needs to be an educational element and some data cleansing of human data by going to the patient.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0186	3	3	JS	08/08/2024 15:04	

Every individual would have to say that they validate this data.

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0334	5	1	JS	02/10/2024 16:36	

Minorities might have a higher level of fear.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0334	5	2	JS	02/10/2024 16:47	

Trustworthiness fails at times. AI can make noise - that can cause problems. How does AI interact with all the community? How can it be used by people with disabilities? These are important factors to think about as well.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0334	5	3	JS	08/08/2024 15:31	

Clarity of training data being representative – in terms of the key characteristics

Age

Race

Gender

Socio-economic status

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0334	5	4	JS	08/08/2024 15:33	

Data must be centrally maintained for enough diversity, put to nationally decided standards and quality controls, with the ability for AI to catch correlations in the wider pool of data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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5 JS 02/10/2024 16:49

How is the model updated with new data? If we use AI more and more, will it populate and influence the datasets such that AI just reinforces on its own decisions/outcomes. And will that limit the diversity of the data?

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.0205 2

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

We are working on a piece of work called 'reasonable expectations' and it's surprising how little access these bodies have to patient data.

2 JS 25/11/2024 14:45

What would make you distrustful of an AI-based decision? Given that the various scams and scandals that have come to light, the public is probably biased to believe that systems are now fallible. Therefore, what factors and practices would inspire trust for you? What suggestions or questions would be important to consider to make AI trustworthy at all?

Codes\\Open Research\\Obstacles to Open Research

No 0.0147 1

1 JS 25/11/2024 14:45

What would make you distrustful of an AI-based decision? Given that the various scams and scandals that have come to light, the public is probably biased to believe that systems are now fallible. Therefore, what factors and practices would inspire trust for you? What suggestions or questions would be important to consider to make AI trustworthy at all?

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Yes 0.0058 1

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

We are working on a piece of work called 'reasonable expectations' and it's surprising how little access these bodies have to patient data.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data

No 0.0058 1

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:43

We are working on a piece of work called 'reasonable expectations' and it's surprising how little access these bodies have to patient data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Peer-review

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0075	1		1	JS	02/10/2024 16:49

Peer review of human clinicians' decisions to see the variance of the decisions of multiple clinicians to a certain scenario. That peer review can then be used for AI decisions too.

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.0869	9		1	JS	02/10/2024 16:42

Specialties will have different regulators in AI.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	08/08/2024 14:20

Two implications for redesigning patient experience: 1) recognising that clinical context might be very different from GP; 2) AI-human collaboration is important and that it should be explained – how can you talk to patients about the impact to understand the outcomes?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	02/10/2024 16:42

How do we deploy this technology to take standardisation into account? I question marketisation and profit-driven decisions influencing reliability positively.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:47

There is some form of data governance by which companies need to operate. Companies govern their own data. There might be a EU-based GDPR but how much do companies adhere and interact with that? Not sure.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:48

Optimistic about AI but I am a bit shaken not stirred. A grand tool but we have to be wary - the earth is imperfect so as with everything there might be fear, a lack of empathy and error but we will take it as it comes. We must police AI - Take all the goodness from it and put up with the bad. The police are good but there might be some bad police officers. However, the good far outweighs the bad. AI is the same. We have to use the same analogy - deal with all the problems and go forward.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:48

We are already living in a world which depends a lot on AI.

Very difficult to completely rely on AI. AI can sometimes make mistakes. It is difficult to understand that we can trust AI but not completely rely on it.

It is a journey to get people to understand and we need to take people through the journey to understand that balance.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	08/08/2024 15:26

Systems need to be in place – there needs to be awareness of the 1% chance – there needs to be transparency in performance of AI e.g.: NHS – needs to have proper security – public perception of data security: banking is safer than a NHS medical system – data system in NHS is fragmented to "localised" region.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				8	JS	08/08/2024 15:32

Want quality control to be explicit, open and with a human in the loop. Building policies for this quality control is one thing, it is important to enforce it in practice.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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9 JS 09/10/2024 15:34

Data silos hurt imposition of national standards on data quality, security and privacy.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies

No 0.0548 6

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:42

Specialties will have different regulators in AI.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:47

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5 JS 08/08/2024 15:32

Want quality control to be explicit, open and with a human in the loop. Building policies for this quality control is one thing, it is important to enforce it in practice.

6 JS 09/10/2024 15:34

Data silos hurt imposition of national standards on data quality, security and privacy.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No 0.0254 2

1 JS 08/08/2024 14:20

Two implications for redesigning patient experience: 1) recognising that clinical context might be very different from GP; 2) AI-human collaboration is important and that it should be explained – how can you talk to patients about the impact to understand the outcomes?

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Very difficult to completely rely on AI. AI can sometimes make mistakes. It is difficult to understand that we can trust AI but not completely rely on it.

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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Standards

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0066	1		1	JS	02/10/2024 16:42

How do we deploy this technology to take standardisation into account? I question marketisation and profit-driven decisions influencing reliability positively.

Codes\\Reliability

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0180	4		1	JS	25/11/2024 15:16

It should be possible to learn about AI. To have materials to send to the patient and to the GP about AI.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	08/08/2024 14:16

Reliability – how can we ensure that data is reliable?
Something can't never be 100% accurate.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	08/08/2024 14:19

Humans are fallible too, they are not open about their methods.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	08/08/2024 15:23

Trust inspired by statistical methods – confidence intervals can be used to educate reliability – medicine has fuzzy logic (not 100%) - no 100% accurate diagnosis in AI.

Codes\\Transparency

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0487	10		1	JS	08/08/2024 14:05

Talking about stuff and putting it out there – is going to be so transparent as to bombard ourselves with this – because it is everywhere.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:41

Visibility and blackbox: when you interact with a human the decision is more understandable.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	08/08/2024 14:16

How data is used needs to be made open and transparent.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	08/08/2024 14:17

Transparency and openness: things need to be simplified.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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5 JS 02/10/2024 16:44

When my condition was discussed, I didn't have the full picture. I didn't understand how the decision was arrived at.

6 JS 02/10/2024 16:46

The transparency and complexity from simple algorithms should also exist in the AI models today to give us a better-informed decision from a medical standpoint and outcomes for patients.

7 JS 02/10/2024 16:46

AI continues to learn- software using AI, researchers often use AI in a static form where no further data is supplied for training. As technologies adapt/update where does the data come from?

8 JS 02/10/2024 16:47

Is there a need for greater transparency when we use AI to make these decisions?

9 JS 08/08/2024 15:25

Systems need to be in place – there needs to be awareness of the 1% chance – there needs to be transparency in performance of AI

10 JS 08/08/2024 15:31

Openness and transparency – public perception have good trust in NHS due to good policies and safeguards in place.

Codes\\Trustworthiness

No 0.1330 23

1 JS 25/11/2024 15:16

It should be possible to learn about AI. To have materials to send to the patient and to the GP about AI.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:35

Regulation at the end of the day: to control or know about what AI in patient includes.

3 JS 08/08/2024 14:01

There is lack of trust – regulation may work very well, if you come from a non-standard it cannot be enough – how to empower people who do not trust the system.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:36

Minorities might have a higher level of fear.

5 JS 02/10/2024 16:36

Do I have ADHD? What's the environment like where people get the information?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:36
The importance of environment: it is important to trust if you get information from your GP or from online app.						
				7	JS	02/10/2024 16:37
If you want to get something over to people and them to have trust, then you have to talk about it a lot – top to bottom and the other way around. They must be teaching children about AI – you need all approaches and it is going to affect everybody.						
				8	JS	08/08/2024 14:05
We don't really trust in anything anymore.						
				9	JS	02/10/2024 16:37
Trust has to be earned – we're putting too much faith – give it time; bit worrying, what if the system collapses?						
				10	JS	02/10/2024 16:37
Occasionally humans make mistakes – outside the surgery it is harder to discover.						
				11	JS	02/10/2024 16:41
We already trust humans, and we don't even know if it is going to be this person doing the exam – it's really getting transition from trusting in a person to trusting in AI.						
				12	JS	08/08/2024 14:16
Data bridges in NHS and in banks.						
				13	JS	02/10/2024 16:43
I am aware that for my age I am much more IT literate because of my background. In spite of this I am still frustrated and have found myself typing "I want to speak to a human!". And this doesn't advance the case for AI in some cases.						
				14	JS	02/10/2024 16:43
We nowadays have declining trust in decision-makers whether these are politicians or pharmaceutical companies and these are the bodies feeding AI.						
				15	JS	02/10/2024 16:43
The presentation touched a lot on how AI has gone wrong. We already have quite a lot of mistrust. Maybe we need to hear about more success stories.						
				16	JS	02/10/2024 16:43
Obviously, we're going to be mistrustful of a machine making decisions. But we need to also remember that poor decisions are sometimes made by humans.						
				17	JS	02/10/2024 16:44
Yes, we are probably holding AI to a much higher standard. Better to think of AI as something that might aid human judgements.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				18	JS	02/10/2024 16:44
In retail banking, and internet banking, AI was hailed as super convenient, but choice was quietly phased out. Profit is at the core of everything. How much contingency plans are we going to have? If anything goes wrong, how are we going to mitigate that?						
				19	JS	02/10/2024 16:45
How can we make AI trustworthy?						
				20	JS	02/10/2024 16:45
Glossary of language to understand what is being shown and talked about with AI. AI has the element of being power-driven and having no human control so we need to understand the process so that we can give our data and understand what we have given our data to. We need to make sure that everyone understands the terms.						
				21	JS	08/08/2024 14:54
Trustworthiness may come from transparency of data sources. That might not be possible because these are private companies. Where is the incentive for them to make that open? They need to put regulations and laws in place for this to happen.						
				22	JS	08/08/2024 15:06
Very difficult to completely rely on AI. AI can sometimes make mistakes. It is difficult to understand that we can trust AI but not completely rely on it.						
				23	JS	08/08/2024 15:21
AI as a blackbox does not inspire trust – does not go into root cause of medical diagnosis						

Files\\Notes W2 S3 - Challenges of Reliability

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No	0.0342	8				
			1	JS	02/10/2024 16:54	
If it goes wrong who will push the plugs?						
			2	JS	02/10/2024 16:54	
Who is accountable?						
			3	JS	02/10/2024 16:54	
The drug company. It already happened. There is no precedence in AI.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:55
There is a lack of accountability as well as just trust.						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:55
What are the consequences going to be if you operate outside of these regulations? We realise we have to do something as AI is moving so fast.						
				6	JS	02/10/2024 17:15
Who is accountable for the final outcome following a medical decision?						
				7	JS	02/10/2024 17:15
It is the clinical decision by the clinician.						
				8	JS	02/10/2024 17:15
AI should be used like a doctor's stethoscope. AI is an advanced aid for doctor but decision should always be made by clinicians. There should also be penalties for doctors who do not do their job and rely too heavily on AI.						

Codes\\AI

No	0.0560	10				
				1	JS	08/08/2024 15:39
AI act. Compliance with data protection. Take into account patient perspective. Unbiased and comprehensible decisions. Can be controlled by humans.						
				2	JS	08/08/2024 15:44
Enforcing legislation.						
				3	JS	02/10/2024 16:52
Danger to treat AI as the new God.						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:52
Diagnostic process and procedure ... include three lines in it about AI.						
				5	JS	22/10/2024 11:40
What are the consequences going to be if you operate outside of these regulations? We realise we have to do something as AI is moving so fast.						
				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
NHS England are probably open to digitisation. There is a report by Thompson on achieving this type of digitisation which covers aspects of AI.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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7 JS 08/08/2024 16:20

Notes inserted by AI to be used by GP and help to try to eliminate human errors due to simple mistakes.

8 JS 02/10/2024 17:15

AI can be used for simple decisions. More complex decisions that consider real -world effects - traffic, machine availability etc need humans.

9 JS 08/08/2024 16:20

AI lacks nuance for considering patient characteristics but is more objective as it does not consider anything else other than the information given.

10 JS 08/08/2024 16:45

Develop an AI interface that ["self-understands"] to explain to users the medical decision-making process – to be developed by medical doctors and developer together.

Codes\\Bias (data, model...)

No 0.0248 4

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:55

Maybe we need to start using bias.
It is very easy to say "AI must do this", but might that mean...
All bias is bad -
It is much harder to do diagnosis with darker skin.
A good model will say – in confidence.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:55

If you did a representative sample of African people.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:55

It depends, if your bias is due to sample or if it is based in being harder

4 JS 22/10/2024 11:44

I don't think there is a tool that will be completely unbiased. It's how that data is interpreted that on the whole needs to strive for unbiasedness.

Codes\\Collaboration

No 0.0432 4

1 JS 28/11/2024 13:45

:There is an obligation for clinicians, researchers and tech people to come together.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 28/11/2024 13:45

In patients with co-morbidities, end of bed tests were performed by doctors - doctors formed opinions from looking at patients considering not only medical considerations but also his own opinion and incorporating patient's attitude and willpower. These factors contribute to patient success as well (holistic view) and cannot be seen by AI.

3 JS 28/11/2024 13:45

Mistakes can happen due to stress and external factors and there is a study looking into how stress affects surgery performance. This study can give you an idea how human performance can vary. AI is consistent and more accurate. We need to combine AI with human experience.

4 JS 28/11/2024 13:45

What can patients do in terms of improving reliability?
The presence of doctors brings a human element to AI
In summary: [AI – Human partnership is required]

Codes\\Data

Yes 0.0261 4

1 JS 08/08/2024 15:44

Art. 22 GDPR.

2 JS 08/08/2024 15:51

Some people may want it, to have their privacy but that may work against you. I believe people who are not sharing their care record will receive inferior treatment.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:54

These are unattainable– it is not possible to explain all AI.
Bias – sometimes we have to be biased ; some of these things are biased because there are plausible difficulties.

4 JS 08/08/2024 16:47

Audit the data to ensure that it is of good quality, i.e., it is representative enough and independently sampled, and its limitations are properly reported and recorded.

Codes\\Data\\Data challenges

No 0.0088 1

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:54

These are unattainable– it is not possible to explain all AI.
Bias – sometimes we have to be biased ; some of these things are biased because there are plausible difficulties.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Data quality

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0084	1	1	JS	08/08/2024 16:47	

Audit the data to ensure that it is of good quality, i.e., it is representative enough and independently sampled, and its limitations are properly reported and recorded.

Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0089	2	1	JS	08/08/2024 15:44	

Art. 22 GDPR.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	08/08/2024 15:51	

Some people may want it, to have their privacy but that may work against you. I believe people who are not sharing their care record will receive inferior treatment.

Codes\\Expectations

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.0242	5	1	JS	02/10/2024 16:53	

If we were building something from scratch, what might we ask for?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	02/10/2024 16:53	

Engagement, we're here we learned so much! Workshops, GP participants.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			3	JS	02/10/2024 16:56	

AI-supplemented knowledge could have value.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			4	JS	02/10/2024 16:56	

Some people just want something or are comforted by one authoritative source of information. Don't want the burden of making decisions.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			5	JS	02/10/2024 16:57	

But that is something that is plastic and malleable. Over your patient journey you may question more or have more agency. And your level of engagement can fluctuate.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Expectations\Patient and Public involvement

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0242	5				
				1	JS	02/10/2024 16:53
If we were building something from scratch, what might we ask for?						
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:53
Engagement, we're here we learned so much! Workshops, GP participants.						
				3	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
AI-supplemented knowledge could have value.						
				4	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
Some people just want something or are comforted by one authoritative source of information. Don't want the burden of making decisions.						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:57
But that is something that is plastic and malleable. Over your patient journey you may question more or have more agency. And your level of engagement can fluctuate.						

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.1485	19				
				1	JS	02/10/2024 16:53
How do we keep up about things that are moving quite quickly?						
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:53
Improve data protection.						
				3	JS	08/08/2024 16:01
Role of the public – challenging point ; depends on the patient experience (motivation related to familiarity and health). Participation as patient experience through forums like these.						
				4	JS	08/08/2024 16:01
There are more people that should be listened to.						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
"...consistency, unbiased, controlled by humans, fair, no harm". Do we have an OFSTED [Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills] version for AI in medicine?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
				Is it important to enforce these ideals or to set standards?		
				7	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
				Less rules and more guidance.		
				8	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
				Some of the regulations are incredibly generic and non-specific to AI. "Environmentally sustainable". That means very little.		
				9	JS	08/08/2024 16:12
				More people involved in research will help to enrich the understanding of AI.		
				10	JS	02/10/2024 17:06
				I was involved in a project on air quality with Imperial. This involved members of the local community. They trained them. There has to be commitment to invest in the community's understanding.		
				11	JS	02/10/2024 17:12
				Healthcare is such a time-poor sector. How do we make space for these levels of engagement?		
				12	JS	02/10/2024 17:13
				EU law mentioned -what about the UK specifically? What about our future and how will we move forward?		
				13	JS	02/10/2024 17:13
				UK clinical guidelines same as USA, EU and all countries follow the same guideline enables sharing and communication ensuring that everyone adheres to similar standards.		
				14	JS	09/10/2024 16:48
				What is the role of patients and public in a world where AI is used for diagnosis and treatment? To make the AI better so that the clinicians can make a better decision. If patients are not honest or not compliant will treatment that affects the data collected from them. So data integrity presents a challenge.		
				15	JS	02/10/2024 17:15
				Patient ability to describe pain and feelings can also play a role - and should be acknowledged.		
				16	JS	08/08/2024 16:27
				Patient should proactively familiarise themselves with AI. What does people think of this statement? AI should be integrated into the education curriculum from primary school-level – pertinent. A top-level driven by the education sector, to train the required teaching skills and resources for primary/secondary school students. Need to learn to ask and critique the AI with the right questions. Aware of rights on [data] related to AI, in terms of the public health. A gap to fill – a simplified version of NHS data webpage on medical AI-related topic. Responsible by the NHS experts and community-driven for relevant information (e.g.: not about fine-grain details of neural networks but about a broad but relevant scope in the NHS webpage)		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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17 JS 08/08/2024 16:41

Patients need to encourage and demand medical sector to have a good data management system.

18 JS 08/08/2024 16:43

Patient involved in patient participation group – helps local healthcare to gain funding for infrastructure.

19 JS 08/08/2024 16:47

Do you see a role for the involvement of the public and patients?
 Providing the critical patient feedback and concerns through multiple forums, committees.
 Can ask the government to do and release the checks made for the AI dataset, models, etc.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies

No 0.0123 4

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

How do we keep up about things that are moving quite quickly?

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

Improve data protection.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:56

Less rules and more guidance.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:56

Some of the regulations are incredibly generic and non-specific to AI. "Environmentally sustainable". That means very little.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No 0.1103 11

1 JS 08/08/2024 16:01

Role of the public – challenging point ; depends on the patient experience (motivation related to familiarity and health).
 Participation as patient experience through forums like these.

2 JS 08/08/2024 16:01

There are more people that should be listened to.

3 JS 08/08/2024 16:12

More people involved in research will help to enrich the understanding of AI.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	02/10/2024 17:06
I was involved in a project on air quality with Imperial. This involved members of the local community. They trained them. There has to be commitment to invest in the community's understanding.						
				5	JS	02/10/2024 17:12
Healthcare is such a time-poor sector. How do we make space for these levels of engagement?						
				6	JS	09/10/2024 16:48
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				7	JS	02/10/2024 17:15
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				8	JS	08/08/2024 16:27
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				9	JS	08/08/2024 16:41
Patients need to encourage and demand medical sector to have a good data management system.						
				10	JS	08/08/2024 16:43
Patient involved in patient participation group – helps local healthcare to gain funding for infrastructure.						
				11	JS	08/08/2024 16:47
Do you see a role for the involvement of the public and patients? Providing the critical patient feedback and concerns through multiple forums, committees. Can ask the government to do and release the checks made for the AI dataset, models, etc.						
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Standards						
	No	0.0258	4			
				1	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
"...consistency, unbiased, controlled by humans, fair, no harm". Do we have an OFSTED [Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills] version for AI in medicine?						
				2	JS	02/10/2024 16:56
Is it important to enforce these ideals or to set standards?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 02/10/2024 17:13

EU law mentioned -what about the UK specifically? What about our future and how will we move forward?

4 JS 02/10/2024 17:13

UK clinical guidelines same as USA, EU and all countries follow the same guideline enables sharing and communication ensuring that everyone adheres to similar standards.

Codes\\Reliability

No 0.1358 16

1 JS 08/08/2024 15:47

Confidence and reliability works both ways, between AI and human.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

AI is not perfect, but it can be better if the sample is bigger.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

The threshold of reliability:
Failures will happen in AI though we are not yet in hallucinations.

4 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

Every time a patient drops out, - they emphasise how safe is our patient care is and it is just not true.

5 JS 02/10/2024 16:54

Reliability – accountability, regulation, legislation.

6 JS 22/10/2024 11:39

There is a lack of accountability as well as just trust.

7 JS 22/10/2024 11:40

Do we have an OFSTED [Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills] version for AI in medicine?

8 JS 22/10/2024 11:48

The organisations that are building models, are they having the type of conversations we are having today in this room? Having more opportunities like this would be amazing

9 JS 02/10/2024 17:13

AI prescribing - more or less reliable?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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10 JS 02/10/2024 17:13

I feel sceptical - I feel that human intervention is necessary.

11 JS 02/10/2024 17:14

In clinical trials, drug companies must include all side-effects even though very unlikely. Trust in AI depends on how robust the model is. Does it understand complexity of disease and drugs and will it take into account ongoing medicines etc? Would human interventions be necessary for patients with more complex needs to understand drug interactions etc.? I believe a multidisciplinary team is needed to look at it with a holistic view.

12 JS 02/10/2024 17:14

Algorithms can incorporate complex inputs regarding drugs and drug interactions. AI can have a lot of value there. Computer cannot make human error. If we have holistic health records that incorporate all patient info, AI can recommend and facilitate discussion after AI recommends drug. Essentially, an AI decision tree

13 JS 08/08/2024 16:21

Reliability at a technology level is just based on the reliability of the information. But ultimate judgement has to be from the clinician. If something goes wrong, the clinician is accountable.

14 JS 08/08/2024 16:28

Implications of Unreliable AI:
Wrong medical diagnosis – needs regulation to ensure final decision made by human practitioners to avoid biases – doctors need to monitor AI decisions;
GP needs to actually check patients instead of over-reliance of technology – leads to mistreatment of patients (wrong treatment due to lack of transparency of data used for decision-making) - AI medical systems de-humanise the medical system.

15 JS 08/08/2024 16:46

What does reliability mean to you?
Classically, success as observed in the clinical trials. In context of NN, its performance based on the agreed, constantly updated, performance thresholds and checks.

16 JS 22/10/2024 12:06

Consensus that AI tested on real-world data as in clinical trials would increase the trustworthiness in it and help record its reliability on similar standards as those for testing drugs. Though, it can also just be evidence based rather than a clinical trial based for certain cases.

Codes\\Transparency

No 0.0493 6

1 JS 02/10/2024 16:53

GPs may not mention the use of AI to patients.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:57

I feel that motivations arounds costs and profit dictate a lot of decision-making. I wish this wasn't the case.

3 JS 02/10/2024 16:57

The organisations that are building models, are they having the type of conversations we are having today in this room? Having more opportunities like this would be amazing.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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4 JS 02/10/2024 17:14

AI decision tree - can have objective decision. We should combine human and AI decision. But where does validation come in? We need to make sure human and AI align and if they don't, we need transparency as to why. Transparent decision tree would allow understandability and synergy between the two.

5 JS 08/08/2024 16:41

A transparent decision-making process: doctors and patients are on the same page when it comes to the decision-making process, e.g.: doctors spend time explaining to patients on their diagnoses.

6 JS 08/08/2024 16:44

Doctor explains to patient in detail level, the ramifications on AI decision-making, to make the system less opaque – [but hard due to being resource-heavy].

Codes\\Trustworthiness

No 0.0497 4

1 JS 02/12/2024 10:14

In what forum can you actually make these comments? With your GP, it is very difficult to question them. We're in a culture where we don't question the GP.

2 JS 02/10/2024 16:55

Lack of trust in the big decision-makers, yes those rules and regulations are established but how much are they really being followed?

3 JS 02/10/2024 17:14

Unsatisfactory GP experience is common. It is difficult for GP to keep up with patient volume and GPs often change. AI can always be looking at everything and take on so much more information.
I would trust AI over GP if model is robust

4 JS 08/08/2024 16:46

Does it relate to (a) trustworthiness, (b) whether an AI tool has been tested in the real-world, (c) whether outcomes for patients are better compared to what was done before?
Consensus that AI tested on real-world data as in clinical trials would increase the trustworthiness in it and help record its reliability on similar standards as those for testing drugs. Though, it can also just be evidence based rather than a clinical trial based for certain cases.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Files\\Notes W3 S1 - Making Data Fair

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No	0.0093	1				
			1	JS	14/10/2024 14:31	

: So it's accountability?

Yes.

The study could be audited?

Yes with patient studies. But with data collection for the use of software. That's probably less likely to be policed.

Codes\\AI

No	0.0115	3				
			1	JS	04/10/2024 10:00	

How do you think AI might change FAIR principles?

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:00

A lot of challenges = every society may have things that are not perfect = AI may amplify those imperfections.

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:00

If you don't provide AI with full data how can we have trust in AI?

Codes\\Collaboration

No	0.0260	2				
			1	JS	14/08/2024 17:53	

Challenge 1 - lack of standardisation; different use of ontologies and changing meaning over time. Solutions: from proof of concept from TV industry and independent organisation to set international standards. Also, use of AI to identify variance and standardised approach.

Challenge 2 - many ways of sharing data: which organisations should we follow? How can connect between them?

2 JS 28/11/2024 13:45

[Member of the public]: What is the difference between data and metadata?

Professional staff member explained the difference.

Codes\\Data

Yes	0.0490	9				
			1	JS	14/08/2024 17:45	

Making sure that the person responsible for data protection is trained rigorously.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 14/08/2024 17:46

The person responsible for data protection should have sufficient institutional and community knowledge.

3 JS 04/10/2024 09:57

The principles help us identifying the quality of the data.

4 JS 04/10/2024 09:58

The principles are not new, how do you work it? If you use apps that use data you should be using those principles, but they're not always used.

5 JS 14/08/2024 17:57

How do we deal with data before FAIR data?

6 JS 04/10/2024 10:02

It's really interesting thinking about that idea of data quality over time.

7 JS 04/10/2024 10:03

A panel review every 5-10 years about the regulation could work? Especially with the descriptions.

8 JS 04/10/2024 10:03

It is going to be hard to make it relevant. So I have data relating to someone who was sectioned for being gay. How do we represent that data now?

9 JS 04/10/2024 10:03

In 2021 there wasn't a Roma-Irish category (census data) but now that is there following some of the consultations that took place. Mental health concepts or ethnicity labels could be discussed and consulted on.

Codes\\Data\Data challenges

No 0.0072 1

1 JS 04/10/2024 09:58

The principles are not new, how do you work it? If you use apps that use data you should be using those principles, but they're not always used.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Data integrity

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0021	1		1	JS	14/08/2024 17:57

How do we deal with data before FAIR data?

Codes\\Data\Data quality

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0354	6		1	JS	14/08/2024 17:46

The person responsible for data protection should have sufficient institutional and community knowledge.

				2	JS	04/10/2024 09:57
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The principles help us identifying the quality of the data.

				3	JS	04/10/2024 10:02
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It's really interesting thinking about that idea of data quality over time.

				4	JS	04/10/2024 10:03
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				5	JS	04/10/2024 10:03
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It is going to be hard to make it relevant. So I have data relating to someone who was sectioned for being gay. How do we represent that data now?

				6	JS	04/10/2024 10:03
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In 2021 there wasn't a Roma-Irish category (census data) but now that is there following some of the consultations that took place. Mental health concepts or ethnicity labels could be discussed and consulted on.

Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0041	1		1	JS	14/08/2024 17:45

Making sure that the person responsible for data protection is trained rigorously.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0319	1		1	JS	04/10/2024 10:08

How accessible are the data? How to ensure a lot of people have the right mechanism to get the data, and do they understand the data? For example, some can't open NHS websites due to absence of good internet, software being used to open the data like Microsoft Word (or Excel) . How do we make sure data are actually accessible? Laptop versus Mobiles? 5G connections versus 4G? Speed and quality of internet matters too. Device does not match (can be only opened on laptop versus mobiles). Researchers should try with different devices and ensure the data can be accessed and opened. If this is not done properly this prevents access.

Codes\\FAIR principles

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.1189	17		1	JS	14/08/2024 17:46

How can a 'data logbook' be standardised?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	03/10/2024 11:27

Science is an international phenomenon, and it benefits us more to share data freely.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	14/10/2024 14:43

Stumbling block is the incorrect use of ontologies, i.e., use of the same words but meaning different things.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	03/10/2024 11:29

[Another participant] raises the question of how this can work across the world -> suggests need for standards (e.g., TV industry independent organisation (SMPTE) that sets the interoperable standard which builds in FAIR). If there is no international standard, then will not work properly.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	03/10/2024 11:29

There is proof concept – can this be implemented or has the horse bolted?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	03/10/2024 11:29

Needs to be set by organisation that is commercially-independent and agreed consensus.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	14/08/2024 17:53

Findable:
Metadata;
Persistent Identifiers (DOI);
Data repositories.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				8	JS	14/08/2024 17:53

Accessibility:
Open access;
Controlled access;
Licensing.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Interoperability: Standards; APIs; Metadata standards (controlled vocabularies, thesaurus).				9	JS	14/08/2024 17:54
Reusability: Detailed metadata; Clear licensing; Provenance.				10	JS	14/08/2024 17:54
How can you make data FAIR when it is unfair form the beginning? Accessibility etc. How do we bring this to reality when we live in a mixed world?				11	JS	07/10/2024 15:59
Concern: people creating accessibility are those who are actually digitally-active, what about those who are not?				12	JS	04/10/2024 09:58
Findability: how are the standards and legal requirements connected at each stage so everybody is working on the same page, to the same standards, etc.? What are the different licenses?				13	JS	14/08/2024 18:00
Gigabytes/terabytes of data (is generated) in real life. I suspect there are many databases (that store data). Research databases are also many. Data is more for research or academic rather than real world.				14	JS	14/08/2024 18:16
Challenges: Starting point - databases. This presentation helped. Building a data repository by the university aims to solve this challenge by making the data available. Meta data question is challenging. Having metadata readable by machines across domain is challenging. People with different roles work on research projects. People in different domains need to agree what the metadata need to look like. How do we best bring interoperability is a question.				15	JS	04/10/2024 10:06
[Member of the public asks PTO staff] How confident are you - on building systems for collaboration, sooner or later?				16	JS	04/10/2024 10:08
It is complex. Need to work on standards. We can use novel technologies such as AI or other techniques to process and integrate data.				17	JS	04/10/2024 10:08
Codes\\FAIR principles\Accessibility						
No		0.0311	5			
Science is an international phenomenon, and it benefits us more to share data freely.				1	JS	03/10/2024 11:27

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 14/08/2024 17:53

Accessibility:
Open access;
Controlled access;
Licensing.

3 JS 07/10/2024 15:59

How can you make data FAIR when it is unfair from the beginning?
Accessibility etc. How do we bring this to reality when we live in a mixed world?

4 JS 04/10/2024 09:58

Concern: people creating accessibility are those who are actually digitally-active, what about those who are not?

5 JS 14/08/2024 18:16

Gigabytes/terabytes of data (is generated) in real life. I suspect there are many databases (that store data). Research databases are also many. Data is more for research or academic rather than real world.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Findability

No 0.0131 2

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:53

Findable:
Metadata;
Persistent Identifiers (DOI);
Data repositories.

2 JS 14/08/2024 18:00

Findability: how are the standards and legal requirements connected at each stage so everybody is working on the same page, to the same standards, etc.? What are the different licenses?

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Interoperability

No 0.0713 9

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:46

How can a 'data logbook' be standardised?

2 JS 14/10/2024 14:43

Stumbling block is the incorrect use of ontologies, i.e., use of the same words but meaning different things.

3 JS 03/10/2024 11:29

[Another participant] raises the question of how this can work across the world -> suggests need for standards (e.g., TV industry independent organisation (SMPTE) that sets the interoperable standard which builds in FAIR). If there is no international standard, then will not work properly.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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4 JS 03/10/2024 11:29

There is proof concept – can this be implemented or has the horse bolted?

5 JS 03/10/2024 11:29

Needs to be set by organisation that is commercially-independent and agreed consensus.

6 JS 14/08/2024 17:54

Interoperability:
Standards;
APIs;
Metadata standards (controlled vocabularies, thesaurus).

7 JS 04/10/2024 10:06

Challenges: Starting point - databases. This presentation helped. Building a data repository by the university aims to solve this challenge by making the data available. Meta data question is challenging. Having metadata readable by machines across domain is challenging. People with different roles work on research projects. People in different domains need to agree what the metadata need to look like. How do we best bring interoperability is a question.

8 JS 04/10/2024 10:08

[Member of the public asks PTO staff] How confident are you - on building systems for collaboration, sooner or later?

9 JS 04/10/2024 10:08

It is complex. Need to work on standards. We can use novel technologies such as AI or other techniques to process and integrate data.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Reusability

No 0.0033 1

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:54

Reusability:
Detailed metadata;
Clear licensing;
Provenance.

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.0205 3

1 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

In principle, data would be made open access at some point.
Publications are one way to have controlled access to data.

2 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

'Free data' is generally a more altruistic idea, but pragmatically we should charge when we can.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 04/10/2024 10:04

It's not fundamental to your goals as researchers. This will probably lead to further discussions about healthy incentives in research. We are constantly chasing a funding hamster wheel.

Codes\\Open Research\\Obstacles to Open Research

No 0.0094 1

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:04

It's not fundamental to your goals as researchers. This will probably lead to further discussions about healthy incentives in research. We are constantly chasing a funding hamster wheel.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Yes 0.0111 2

1 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

In principle, data would be made open access at some point. Publications are one way to have controlled access to data.

2 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

'Free data' is generally a more altruistic idea, but pragmatically we should charge when we can.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data

No 0.0111 2

1 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

In principle, data would be made open access at some point. Publications are one way to have controlled access to data.

2 JS 03/10/2024 11:27

'Free data' is generally a more altruistic idea, but pragmatically we should charge when we can.

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Yes 0.1144 12

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:46

Require good documentation to use data that may be used by external persons.

2 JS 14/08/2024 17:46

Currently working with an ISO in Chemistry to create a standardised log/book or finding aid.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	14/08/2024 17:47
						Scope for customisation in specific sub-domains.
				4	JS	04/10/2024 09:55
						It is challenging to standardise data of different variables in different formats. To what extent should we standardise data and how to treat new variables? And how to ensure for changing terminologies and how aspects change over time?
				5	JS	26/11/2024 09:47
						In complex issues, it might be limiting trying to use standardised approach.
				6	JS	26/11/2024 09:47
						Infrasctructure to share data – issue: standardising the way in which we share data. There are multiple solutions already, there's not a standard way of placing data and there are competing solutions. Who do we follow? How do we connect between the organisations?
				7	JS	26/11/2024 09:47
						TV archives searching engines are using language models to look up tables/data dictionaries to produce standard meta-data.
				8	JS	04/10/2024 09:58
						Open standards, API, what is an open standard, there is some proprietary software so, it might not be totally accessible.
				9	JS	04/10/2024 10:03
						Part of [PTO Name] job is to support staff and researchers around these thornier questions with incentives and levers.
				10	JS	04/10/2024 10:04
						Standard operating procedures are in place. And people do review these SOPs and update them accordingly as times change and updates occur. So if the MHRA [Medicines Healthcare products Regulatory Agency] have new developments we monitor that.
				11	JS	14/08/2024 18:16
						How do we combine multiple databases, into a full stream of data? From my past experience, biggest challenge was to convert data into usable information. How do we take academic information and make it usable in real world? How do we bring the data together and make an impact in real world? We are here (research setting) and we need to be there (out there in real world). Move further along to make the data usable in real world. One end - academic, to the other end - to the real world?
				12	JS	04/10/2024 10:06
						Process - need to set national standards if not global standards. What fields need to be published, words, vocab and make databases comply to those standards. Global standards exist as of today (conformance does not). We have got trillions of data everywhere. Setting standards and cleaning the data. How do we clean the data to adhere to new standards, how do we integrate the data?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0059	1	1	1	JS	04/10/2024 10:03

Part of [PTO Name] job is to support staff and researchers around these thornier questions with incentives and levers.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0245	1	1	1	JS	14/08/2024 18:16

How do we combine multiple databases, into a full stream of data? From my past experience, biggest challenge was to convert data into usable information. How do we take academic information and make it usable in real world? How do we bring the data together and make an impact in real world? We are here (research setting) and we need to be there (out there in real world). Move further along to make the data usable in real world. One end - academic, to the other end - to the real world?

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Standards

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	1	1	JS	14/08/2024 17:46

Require good documentation to use data that may be used by external persons.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	2	2	JS	14/08/2024 17:46

Currently working with an ISO in Chemistry to create a standardised log/book or finding aid.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	3	3	JS	14/08/2024 17:47

Scope for customisation in specific sub-domains.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	4	4	JS	04/10/2024 09:55

It is challenging to standardise data of different variables in different formats. To what extent should we standardise data and how to treat new variables? And how to ensure for changing terminologies and how aspects change over time?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	5	5	JS	26/11/2024 09:47

In complex issues, it might be limiting trying to use standardised approach.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	6	6	JS	26/11/2024 09:47

Infrasctructure to share data – issue: standardising the way in which we share data. There are multiple solutions already, there's not a standard way of placing data and there are competing solutions. Who do we follow? How do we connect between the organisations?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0838	10	7	7	JS	26/11/2024 09:47

TV archives searching engines are using language models to look up tables/data dictionaries to produce standard meta-data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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8 JS 04/10/2024 09:58

Open standards, API, what is an open standard, there is some proprietary software so, it might not be totally accessible.

9 JS 04/10/2024 10:04

Standard operating procedures are in place. And people do review these SOPs and update them accordingly as times change and updates occur. So if the MHRA [Medicines Healthcare products Regulatory Agency] have new developments we monitor that.

10 JS 04/10/2024 10:06

Process - need to set national standards if not global standards. What fields need to be published, words, vocab and make databases comply to those standards. Global standards exist as of today (conformance does not). We have got trillions of data everywhere. Setting standards and cleaning the data. How do we clean the data to adhere to new standards, how do we integrate the data?

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.0391 5

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:55

Design and DMP
What outputs will you be creating?
How will you document these?
What ethical or legal requirements if any apply to those outputs?
How will you organise, store, secure and share these outputs?
Who is responsible?

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:00

In my role it is something we do try to implement with the study teams. But they do need support and guidance. A lot of people are involved.

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:00

The main thing is that the steps have to be put in place.

4 JS 04/10/2024 10:00

Yes, with the DMP everything has to be put in place in advance.

5 JS 04/10/2024 10:04

Obviously the FAIR principles are beneficial and useful but are not entirely sold to researchers. We work with secure data environments, as researchers our goals are publications and we will do what we need to do to demonstrate that we are following these principles.

Codes\\Reliability

No 0.0016 1

1 JS 14/08/2024 17:56

Who does the background checks?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Research culture

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0025	1	1	JS	28/11/2024 13:53	

The FAIR principles will be changed in the future.

Codes\\Sustainability

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0581	8	1	JS	26/11/2024 09:54	

Cost. How is data depositing for the benefit for society when there is no reward? What's the incentive for people to do that?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	26/11/2024 09:54	

Example from conservation research – not economically productive but understanding of broader good.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			3	JS	26/11/2024 09:55	

The BOR initiative highlights the gap in resources to funders so that these activities are properly funded.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			4	JS	26/11/2024 09:55	

We're using the practical knowledge applying it to the digital world, how can it be further enhanced and augmented if we cannot have more human resources?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			5	JS	28/11/2024 13:53	

Maintenance of these resources – what is fair today can be unfair tomorrow – historical context.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			6	JS	04/10/2024 10:01	

Yes, with grants. We make lots of noble commitments. But with the reality of the research, we lose sight of the data management plan. A lot of these things for example could end up being very expensive to do. Saying you will do it doesn't necessarily mean anything.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			7	JS	04/10/2024 10:02	

Interoperability can take up resources. This is something that you mentioned too.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			8	JS	04/10/2024 10:02	

Researchers can work with software that goes out of date. If you have an out of date, defunct software and you could only use it within a bubble that kept that software alive, how do you interpret that data more widely?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Files\\Notes W3 S2 - Scrutinising Data Quality

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On	
	0.0125	4				
			1	JS	04/10/2024 10:13	
Retractions are concerning since they indicate that fraud exists in academia. If the nation comes to know about this, this will have terrible consequences.						
			2	JS	26/11/2024 10:00	
Patients must have a choice as to whether AI is used or not.						
			3	JS	04/10/2024 10:21	
Discussion points led to questions of reliance and accountability.						
			4	JS	04/10/2024 10:21	
What does someone need to know about the AI to accept responsibility/be held accountable?						

Codes\\AI

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On	
	0.0130	6				
			1	JS	04/10/2024 10:20	
Discussion about use of AI and recognition of responsible use of AI decisions.						
			2	JS	04/10/2024 10:20	
Over reliance of AI?						
			3	JS	04/10/2024 10:20	
No system is perfect – need an in-depth understanding.						
			4	JS	04/10/2024 10:22	
Are AI concepts training provided within institutions?						
			5	JS	04/10/2024 10:22	
How do you incorporate AI training into current teaching modules/training?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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6 JS 04/10/2024 10:22

Clinical trial focus: problem with AI is that a lot of the research is done on retrospective data.

Codes\\Assessment

No 0.0080 2

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:32

Could there be data overload nowadays? The truth can be difficult to verify now because of the volume of data.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

I think where we have hope in research is around independent auditing with the MHRA. All the consent forms need to be accurate.

Codes\\Bias (data, model...)

No 0.0210 3

1 JS 14/10/2024 15:35

Some stakeholders of research may be interested in one of the favourable outcomes, thus inducing bias in one or more stages of the research process. Measures should be taken to prevent such biases and selective publication - (publish only part so that the research outcome 'appears' favourable to one or more of the stakeholders instead of the overall society). Full data should be collected, analysed, reported for being FAIR.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:48

Maybe this happened with COVID results (a reference to trials conducted for COVID-19 vaccines).

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:48

How do we trust that such biases are not happening? Bias - backdoor influences may come through sponsors.

Codes\\Data

Yes 0.2579 41

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:12

Chemistry journals have a platinum standard whereby data needs to be submitted for data-quality review.

If data isn't good enough, the authors get a chance to rectify this.

This however requires money to the tune of 5 million pounds.

Recovered from pharmaceutical companies and universities.

At that point, peer review/QA is not necessarily free.

Can adversely affect developing economies who don't have ready access to capital.

World wide web has considerably simplified this process.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:14

"The only people who don't make mistakes are the people who don't do anything".

Being able to freely say that we've made a mistake is very important.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	04/10/2024 10:14
<p>Fraud is harder in larger collaborations where the cross checks are much more rigorous. In Physics, you also publish numerical versions of each figure, which helps in corroboration of results. Typically submitted to a community repository. Definition of quality of data is very discipline-specific and can change over time.</p>						
				4	JS	04/10/2024 10:17
<p>Which results should you report? By having pre-registration of clinical trials, it helps in filling gaps of knowledge even for medicines that may have failed.</p>						
				5	JS	04/10/2024 10:17
<p>Figshare is a piece of software used for corroborating figures in academic literature. This is useful since most fraudulent results arise from manipulation of figures. Most scientists don't engage in fraud though.</p>						
				6	JS	04/10/2024 10:17
<p>Most patients don't understand the intricacies of clinical trials. Some communities have systemic distrust on clinical trials. We work with communities in NW London to bridge this gap. Technicians don't necessarily have the technical knowhow to ensure data quality.</p>						
				7	JS	04/10/2024 10:18
<p>Even simple questions such as 'Are you disabled?' are not black and white but much more nuanced. "Data quality is dependent on the social context".</p>						
				8	JS	04/10/2024 10:18
<p>Some metrics exist to audit data – what do we want to check? Comparison of datasets, or comparison to 'gold standard' that doesn't always exist? For generative data, the metrics are not well defined, i.e., modelling performing to certain expectations. Need to have a benchmark.</p>						
				9	JS	04/10/2024 10:19
<p>Need for experts and domain knowledge to identify quality measures.</p>						
				10	JS	14/08/2024 20:44
<p>They only publish when the results are good.</p>						
				11	JS	14/08/2024 20:44
<p>Lobbying – how powerful are pharmaceuticals?</p>						
				12	JS	04/10/2024 10:22
<p>Bit that hasn't been mentioned: the culture. If the culture isn't right, how do you get the integrity?</p>						
				13	JS	14/10/2024 16:14
<p>What would quality of research data mean to you?</p>						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				14	JS	14/10/2024 16:14
				Updating it. Obviously these things do take time. Do we have a committee of researchers who interrogate that data?		
				15	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
				Yes, I don't know if everyone has those levers in place. For me it's about reproducibility.		
				16	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
				And trust.		
				17	JS	14/10/2024 15:38
				I was thinking that having regular reviews for people to check the data to make sure that it is FAIR. That could be really important.		
				18	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
				That's a really important practical point [people checking the data regularly] that could perhaps be embedded although it would require resourcing.		
				19	JS	04/10/2024 10:33
				There are lots of data that do not fall under clinical trials and don't need to be pre-registered and are not subject to the same stringent requirements.		
				20	JS	04/10/2024 10:37
				You added an extra point about the quality of the analysis as well as the data itself.		
				21	JS	04/10/2024 10:36
				In clinical trials studies there is this concept called patient-centric design to determine whether certain data collection is proportionate.		
				22	JS	04/10/2024 10:37
				As [someone] pointed out from an ethics perspective, you need to justify what data you are collecting and for what purpose. You can't now go on a full fishing expedition.		
				23	JS	04/10/2024 10:42
				Domain-specific problems need specific data. Domain experts need to validate the data used in research. All of them should ask questions to check if the data is consistent with the research.		
				24	JS	04/10/2024 10:42
				Quality depends on the sample size. Say 20 vs 10000. There is a difference. Larger the sample the better. Depending on the situation - for example, research on 10000 people looking at ABC medical condition, at the end of the research, what was the outcome research, how did the data change (from beginning to end of research)? Start off with good set of data to current situation. What are the health parameters (being measured)? End of the study: what was the outcome for those 10K people? Start with set of parameters, measure the parameters at the end and look at the change. (These should be published transparently throughout the process of research).		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				25	JS	04/10/2024 10:44
				Are you saying - do we need a comparator group?		
				26	JS	04/10/2024 10:44
				Yes, it would help. However, there are challenges measuring the parameters. Patients may lie. I may have a drink on the side. Not be fully honest during the study. Sample size gives a representative view of the change. (Making sure the parameters are measured honestly is important).		
				27	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				If there are 50 patients in total in the country, and we're sampling 30, this proportion is high. We need to strive for representativeness, not necessarily absolute numbers. Having a good coverage in terms of the representative population is important.		
				28	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				Double-blind process may help here, to rule out bias. That is, patients don't know what treatment they are receiving, and the administrator of treatment also does not know what they are administering - a placebo or the real medicine.		
				29	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				Transparency and quality. How to achieve transparency - most of research is coming outside the country. How to guarantee that the data is legit, research data may be false. Different countries may not give correct information (due to reasons such as), they do not want their ideas or research to leak out. How do we guarantee that data comes through correctly? How can we be confident in the data from other countries?		
				30	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				(Clarification) Countries may give out data selectively.		
				31	JS	04/10/2024 10:46
				With respect to quality, errors might creep in. Accuracy of the data is important - how the data was captured, how do you validate the data, how do you ensure integrity and completeness? Difficult to assess in terms of size. People are affected by different issues. Uncertainties of data. We can only do statistical analysis. We cannot be 100% sure about the outcomes.		
				32	JS	04/10/2024 10:47
				There are different types of errors. Systemic errors. And human errors. Biases by researchers from the beginning cause systemic errors. Whereas human errors are due to lapse in people following processes (people who conduct the trials may induce these human errors).		
				33	JS	04/10/2024 10:50
				FAIR and transparency. I am a patient - my sample is recorded - researchers release results based on the recorded data. How can I guarantee that the recording of each sample is correct?		
				34	JS	26/11/2024 10:21
				[Participant Name] was alluding to the trustworthiness of the people and processes involved in 'collecting' the data, processes followed by the administrator recording the data.		
				35	JS	04/10/2024 10:56
				Can you clarify who are 'they' here?		
				36	JS	04/10/2024 10:56
				They = hospitals. If they write the measurements wrongly and if we proceed with research, then results cannot be trusted.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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37 JS 14/10/2024 16:22

Discussion's intention was that there should be a process to verify and correct individual information to improve data quality. Recording of information should be verifiable and correct. The research should make sure recording details is accurate.

38 JS 04/10/2024 10:56

During research, inclusion and exclusion of data sets may happen. They must publish all these details too.

39 JS 04/10/2024 10:56

Aggregate data is published sometimes, hiding details about included/excluded individual data, due to confidentiality.

40 JS 04/10/2024 10:56

For example, if you are cleaning data which cannot be explained, not errors, just because it does not look good, I as a researcher, am running the risk of bias.

41 JS 04/10/2024 10:57

For example, a consultant walked in to check how the data was captured, only then they figured that the data captured was not correct. They had to repeat and collect data from the beginning. Imagine a situation where the consultant had not visited, but the research continued and concluded on the basis of wrong data.

Codes\\Data\Data challenges

No 0.1145 19

1 JS 14/08/2024 20:44

They only publish when the results are good.

2 JS 14/08/2024 20:44

Lobbying – how powerful are pharmaceuticals?

3 JS 14/10/2024 15:38

I was thinking that having regular reviews for people to check the data to make sure that it is FAIR. That could be really important.

4 JS 04/10/2024 10:32

That's a really important practical point [people checking the data regularly] that could perhaps be embedded although it would require resourcing.

5 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

There are lots of data that do not fall under clinical trials and don't need to be pre-registered and are not subject to the same stringent requirements.

6 JS 04/10/2024 10:42

Domain-specific problems need specific data. Domain experts need to validate the data used in research. All of them should ask questions to check if the data is consistent with the research.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	04/10/2024 10:44
				Are you saying - do we need a comparator group?		
				8	JS	04/10/2024 10:44
				Yes, it would help. However, there are challenges measuring the parameters. Patients may lie. I may have a drink on the side. Not be fully honest during the study. Sample size gives a representative view of the change. (Making sure the parameters are measured honestly is important).		
				9	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				Transparency and quality. How to achieve transparency - most of research is coming outside the country. How to guarantee that the data is legit, research data may be false. Different countries may not give correct information (due to reasons such as), they do not want their ideas or research to leak out. How do we guarantee that data comes through correctly? How can we be confident in the data from other countries?		
				10	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
				(Clarification) Countries may give out data selectively.		
				11	JS	04/10/2024 10:46
				With respect to quality, errors might creep in. Accuracy of the data is important - how the data was captured, how do you validate the data, how do you ensure integrity and completeness? Difficult to assess in terms of size. People are affected by different issues. Uncertainties of data. We can only do statistical analysis. We cannot be 100% sure about the outcomes.		
				12	JS	04/10/2024 10:47
				There are different types of errors. Systemic errors. And human errors. Biases by researchers from the beginning cause systemic errors. Whereas human errors are due to lapse in people following processes (people who conduct the trials may induce these human errors).		
				13	JS	04/10/2024 10:50
				FAIR and transparency. I am a patient - my sample is recorded - researchers release results based on the recorded data. How can I guarantee that the recording of each sample is correct?		
				14	JS	26/11/2024 10:21
				[Participant Name] was alluding to the trustworthiness of the people and processes involved in 'collecting' the data, processes followed by the administrator recording the data.		
				15	JS	04/10/2024 10:56
				Can you clarify who are 'they' here?		
				16	JS	04/10/2024 10:56
				They = hospitals. If they write the measurements wrongly and if we proceed with research, then results cannot be trusted.		
				17	JS	14/10/2024 16:22
				Discussion's intention was that there should be a process to verify and correct individual information to improve data quality. Recording of information should be verifiable and correct. The research should make sure recording details is accurate.		
				18	JS	04/10/2024 10:56
				For example, if you are cleaning data which cannot be explained, not errors, just because it does not look good, I as a researcher, am running the risk of bias.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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19 JS 04/10/2024 10:57

For example, a consultant walked in to check how the data was captured, only then they figured that the data captured was not correct. They had to repeat and collect data from the beginning. Imagine a situation where the consultant had not visited, but the research continued and concluded on the basis of wrong data.

Codes\\Data\Data integrity

No 0.0129 2

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

Some metrics exist to audit data – what do we want to check? Comparison of datasets, or comparison to 'gold standard' that doesn't always exist? For generative data, the metrics are not well defined, i.e., modelling performing to certain expectations. Need to have a benchmark.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:22

Bit that hasn't been mentioned: the culture. If the culture isn't right, how do you get the integrity?

Codes\\Data\Data quality

No 0.1227 18

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:12

Chemistry journals have a platinum standard whereby data needs to be submitted for data-quality review.

If data isn't good enough, the authors get a chance to rectify this.

This however requires money to the tune of 5 million pounds.

Recovered from pharmaceutical companies and universities.

At that point, peer review/QA is not necessarily free.

Can adversely affect developing economies who don't have ready access to capital.

World wide web has considerably simplified this process.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:14

"The only people who don't make mistakes are the people who don't do anything".

Being able to freely say that we've made a mistake is very important.

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:14

Fraud is harder in larger collaborations where the cross checks are much more rigorous.

In Physics, you also publish numerical versions of each figure, which helps in corroboration of results.

Typically submitted to a community repository.

Definition of quality of data is very discipline-specific and can change over time.

4 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

Which results should you report?

By having pre-registration of clinical trials, it helps in filling gaps of knowledge even for medicines that may have failed.

5 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

Figshare is a piece of software used for corroborating figures in academic literature.

This is useful since most fraudulent results arise from manipulation of figures.

Most scientists don't engage in fraud though.

6 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

Most patients don't understand the intricacies of clinical trials.

Some communities have systemic distrust on clinical trials.

We work with communities in NW London to bridge this gap.

Technicians don't necessarily have the technical knowhow to ensure data quality.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	04/10/2024 10:18
						Even simple questions such as 'Are you disabled?' are not black and white but much more nuanced. "Data quality is dependent on the social context".
				8	JS	04/10/2024 10:19
						Need for experts and domain knowledge to identify quality measures.
				9	JS	14/10/2024 16:14
						What would quality of research data mean to you?
				10	JS	14/10/2024 16:14
						Updating it. Obviously these things do take time. Do we have a committee of researchers who interrogate that data?
				11	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
						Yes, I don't know if everyone has those levers in place. For me it's about reproducibility.
				12	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
						And trust.
				13	JS	04/10/2024 10:37
						You added an extra point about the quality of the analysis as well as the data itself.
				14	JS	04/10/2024 10:36
						In clinical trials studies there is this concept called patient-centric design to determine whether certain data collection is proportionate.
				15	JS	04/10/2024 10:37
						As [someone] pointed out from an ethics perspective, you need to justify what data you are collecting and for what purpose. You can't now go on a full fishing expedition.
				16	JS	04/10/2024 10:42
						Quality depends on the sample size. Say 20 vs 10000. There is a difference. Larger the sample the better. Depending on the situation - for example, research on 10000 people looking at ABC medical condition, at the end of the research, what was the outcome research, how did the data change (from beginning to end of research)? Start off with good set of data to current situation. What are the health parameters (being measured)? End of the study: what was the outcome for those 10K people? Start with set of parameters, measure the parameters at the end and look at the change. (These should be published transparently throughout the process of research).
				17	JS	04/10/2024 10:45
						If there are 50 patients in total in the country, and we're sampling 30, this proportion is high. We need to strive for representativeness, not necessarily absolute numbers. Having a good coverage in terms of the representative population is important.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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18 JS 04/10/2024 10:45

Double-blind process may help here, to rule out bias. That is, patients don't know what treatment they are receiving, and the administrator of treatment also does not know what they are administering - a placebo or the real medicine.

Codes\\Data\\Sensitive personal data

No 0.0076 2

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:56

During research, inclusion and exclusion of data sets may happen. They must publish all these details too.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:56

Aggregate data is published sometimes, hiding details about included/excluded individual data, due to confidentiality.

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

No 0.0161 3

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

Difficult to build consensus since a lot of the information that is exposed to the public is not in lay language. Concerns are very legitimate since that could adversely affect opportunities for many communities.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:41

What questions would you ask - to get the quality? Confidence?

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:41

What pool of the number of people are used to collect data? Number, geography... What is representative of the population we want to study? Not only about size (but also include the quality of sample).

Codes\\Expectations

Yes 0.0218 3

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

What steps do we need to take to bridge this gap?
Is there a benefit of having someone at the grassroot level to build trust in communities?

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

My main concern with data is the cybersecurity aspect of it.
How do companies ensure that their data is protected from hacking?
If there is a breach, what are their contingency procedures?
Can data be used to exclude or judge you from opportunities due to the personal nature of your information?
Generally I have a feeling of distrust whenever asked for data.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

Data is generally very well-handled especially in terms of not identifying personal information. Data breaches do occur but they are rare.

Codes\\Expectations\\Information security

No 0.0169 2

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

My main concern with data is the cybersecurity aspect of it.
 How do companies ensure that their data is protected from hacking?
 If there is a breach, what are their contingency procedures?
 Can data be used to exclude or judge you from opportunities due to the personal nature of your information?
 Generally I have a feeling of distrust whenever asked for data.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

Data is generally very well-handled especially in terms of not identifying personal information. Data breaches do occur but they are rare.

Codes\\Expectations\\Patient and Public involvement

No 0.0048 1

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:17

What steps do we need to take to bridge this gap?
 Is there a benefit of having someone at the grassroot level to build trust in communities?

Codes\\FAIR principles

Yes 0.0088 2

1 JS 14/08/2024 20:50

FAIRness of data and accessibility of data.
 The only way we would be able to make data is accessible: the public is one of the solutions – they could get involved.
 Solution – to put up a group like these with public and experts

2 JS 14/08/2024 21:00

For me it's about reproducibility.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Accessibility

No 0.0077 1

1 JS 14/08/2024 20:50

FAIRness of data and accessibility of data.
 The only way we would be able to make data is accessible: the public is one of the solutions – they could get involved.
 Solution – to put up a group like these with public and experts

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\FAIR principles\\Reusability

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	No	0.0011	1	1	JS	14/08/2024 21:00

For me it's about reproducibility.

Codes\\Open Research

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	Yes	0.0171	4	1	JS	14/08/2024 20:47

How do we get the culture right? How does somebody external to Imperial check that culture – how to get an external check?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	04/10/2024 10:34

It also becomes tricky where that data can be cross-referenced with publicly available data. There is a bit of a worrying thing about opening this kind of thing to anybody.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	04/10/2024 10:34

Only the aggregated level data would at most be made available.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	04/10/2024 10:38

There are some occasions where the data cannot realistically ever be made completely open but the main important thing is that the data is reproducible.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	Yes	0.0130	3	1	JS	04/10/2024 10:34

It also becomes tricky where that data can be cross-referenced with publicly available data. There is a bit of a worrying thing about opening this kind of thing to anybody.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	04/10/2024 10:34

Only the aggregated level data would at most be made available.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				3	JS	04/10/2024 10:38

There are some occasions where the data cannot realistically ever be made completely open but the main important thing is that the data is reproducible.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data

No	0.0130	3
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1	JS	04/10/2024 10:34
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It also becomes tricky where that data can be cross-referenced with publicly available data. There is a bit of a worrying thing about opening this kind of thing to anybody.

2	JS	04/10/2024 10:34
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Only the aggregated level data would at most be made available.

3	JS	04/10/2024 10:38
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There are some occasions where the data cannot realistically ever be made completely open but the main important thing is that the data is reproducible.

Codes\\Peer-review

No	0.0368	5
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1	JS	14/08/2024 20:50
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Research and findings we all have our own narrative, but if we make sure that the data is open to peer-review – there is one way to debunk theories.

2	JS	04/10/2024 10:32
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Yes and peer review can introduce bias if editors default to using author peers. So I'm cynical about how that could influence quality positively.

3	JS	04/10/2024 10:57
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What exactly do they want to put on the data? Only good, or what looks good, or mainly include all data? To what extent is the data recorded and shared? Data - needs to have all data sets. Data set should be complete.

4	JS	04/10/2024 10:57
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I would like to see independent peer reviews of the outcomes of the research. Data was peer reviewed. Outcomes of the clinical trials. By multiple independent reviewers. I would purchase external bodies who are not biased to verify and review the results.

5	JS	14/10/2024 16:17
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Peer reviews should happen to scrutinise everything about the data - sample, administering the trials, collection of necessary data, verify the processes, analysis methods, results and suggestions. In addition, the interests of stakeholders need to be 'managed' so that no one or more stakeholders influence the research outcomes.

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Yes	0.0087	2
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1	JS	04/10/2024 10:18
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Public trust in quality of data is definitely going to affect their willingness to participate.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 14/10/2024 16:14

Experience of workshop with many different fields. One way to change this culture is to expose it, to present it, duty of public involvement, giving back to society.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No 0.0087 2

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:18

Public trust in quality of data is definitely going to affect their willingness to participate.

2 JS 14/10/2024 16:14

Experience of workshop with many different fields. One way to change this culture is to expose it, to present it, duty of public involvement, giving back to society.

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.0419 9

1 JS 14/10/2024 16:13

To think outside the laboratory.

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

So the database that I work with, they do have a yearly meeting. They have some sway with how some data are collected. It's a team of patients and public partners, clinicians, technical staff and software engineers.

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:34

Data management plans have been identified as something that are beneficial for us. We also give people a way to access the data. It used to be that we would have to give people honorary contracts which is quite tricky.

4 JS 04/10/2024 10:37

That is probably the main thing that could never completely be open access is the integrity of the analysis. We're working with GitHub at the moment to achieve this so other people can check our methods. It's like a standard now. We don't have to but our team has found it beneficial to do so.

5 JS 14/10/2024 16:20

Data has been digitalised.

6 JS 14/10/2024 16:21

We are all moving towards digital. For example, eVISA, mortgages, etc. Similarly, research data should be digitalised and shared.

7 JS 14/10/2024 16:21

Clinical trials COVID.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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8 JS 14/10/2024 16:21

Existing learnings were used. Publishing them helps.

9 JS 26/11/2024 11:04

Discussion is alluding to processes to publish how the data was collected, what data clean-up operations were done including the details on inclusion and exclusion, aggregation methods, etc. Overall, a process to verify data also should be published.

Codes\\Research culture

No 0.0423 11

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:22

Bit that hasn't been mentioned: the culture. If the culture isn't right, how do you get the integrity?

How do we get the culture right? How does somebody external to Imperial check that culture – how to get an external check?

2 JS 04/10/2024 10:23

Universities are so big that the culture might vary a lot.

3 JS 04/10/2024 10:23

Culture –Imperial values the framework – it's up to individual (it depends on the PI).

4 JS 04/10/2024 10:23

If it were approved at the first stage why is it not that in the beginning?
At Imperial there is a department for Ethics Approval.

5 JS 14/10/2024 16:13

It's probably a good idea to do more activities like this.
This was publicly funded, what did you do with that money?

6 JS 14/10/2024 16:13

The discussion of culture, integrity, Imperial values: why you do things you do, and how you do it?

7 JS 14/10/2024 16:13

Mission and values from the beginning – what does this mean? Really challenging but this can be meaningful. How to make sure those values are going through?

8 JS 14/10/2024 16:13

Checking how many publications this person has?
Evidence of money – it must be evidenced.
Other activities: outreach, dissemination, interaction with general public, etc.

9 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

What you're suggesting has basically to do with accountability.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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10 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

That could result in behavioural change as well, knowing that the work will be checked.

11 JS 04/10/2024 10:33

Yes and particularly now with the advent of AI.

Codes\\Transparency

No 0.0350 8

1 JS 04/10/2024 10:19

Transparency of data cleaning too and standardised meta-data.

2 JS 14/08/2024 20:45

Economic drive of pharmaceuticals – a massive lobby: how are we actually going to be able to fight that back? True transparency and manipulation of transparency.

3 JS 14/08/2024 20:45

There is a lot of regulation and yet still a lack of transparency (based on the presentation).

4 JS 14/08/2024 20:51

Can I trust the data – preregistering as a way to make sure data is FAIR and trustworthy and transparent.

5 JS 04/10/2024 10:45

COVID is a classic example. Countries and borders were closed. South Africa: SA published a lot of information, but instead suffered badly due to transparency (reference to a new variant that originated).

6 JS 04/10/2024 10:48

COVID study - there may be history in the way the vaccines developed - reused science that was developed over many years. What information was reused and what information is new becomes important here.

7 JS 04/10/2024 10:48

Why they keep pushing us to do this [vaccination]. No transparency for what this is for.

8 JS 04/10/2024 10:49

For vaccines - The medical reasons are shared. Example: The COVID vaccines are to build immunity, but not to prevent infection.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Files\\Notes W3 S3 - Asking the Right Questions

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0191	1	1	JS	18/10/2024 09:54

In the public domain, you never really get an opportunity to discuss accountability until something goes wrong. The racist Twitter bot is a good example of where a bot was just replicating a lot of very harmful, herd mentality behaviour that already exists online.

Codes\\AI

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0549	8	1	JS	26/11/2024 11:23

AI can be used to facilitate checking but the challenge is that somebody should be accountable.

			2	JS	04/10/2024 11:26
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Reliability and AI.

			3	JS	04/10/2024 11:26
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Quality of data = quality of AI model.
Having a good process for data collection.

			4	JS	04/10/2024 11:26
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AI and health sector - the human element has to be present; AI is only a tool.
As long as you feed AI with accurate, transparent info.

			5	JS	04/10/2024 11:26
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If you train an AI into detecting cancer it won't give you MRI and CTs.
There is also an element of computer science; we do not understand the reasoning of AI.

			6	JS	04/10/2024 11:28
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AI doomers and existential risks, fake news.

			7	JS	18/10/2024 09:53
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IT devils and dark web, risks of hacking.

			8	JS	18/10/2024 09:55
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Video and audio generation - see them happening after they login to help them understand the model better. Open training on AI to address objections and criticisms by the public.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Collaboration

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	No	0.0658	8			
				1	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
What are some of the innovative things people are doing to involve the public?						
				2	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
The Imperial College Press Office has been doing interesting things to involve the public, e.g. things like press releases may help in involving the public.						
				3	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
Imperial College Healthcare Trust has a number of lay partners who help a lot.						
				4	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
Imperial College Community Engagement Team also plays an excellent role in this regard.						
				5	JS	04/10/2024 11:27
Trying to work out from the public their wants and needs as to the production of an AI.						
				6	JS	18/10/2024 09:38
Giving the users a choice of an output: let the patient decide.						
				7	JS	18/10/2024 09:39
What is the balance here? Individuals want different things. There should be a way to make informed choices.						
				8	JS	18/10/2024 09:53
Every time they're profit driven only (e.g. banking); it's actually making decision about people's lives. Necessity of the human factor; the officer thinking and experience is not taken into account (for instance in mortgages)						

Codes\\Data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	Yes	0.0159	2			
				1	JS	15/08/2024 10:00
No matter what the output is, one needs to be able to know where the data has come from and to be able to check it.						
				2	JS	18/10/2024 09:27
Q: How do you know there is enough data? A: Problem is not the amount of data but the quality of data.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Data\Data integrity

No	0.0083	1	1	JS	15/08/2024 10:00
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No matter what the output is, one needs to be able to know where the data has come from and to be able to check it.

Codes\\Data\Data quality

No	0.0075	1	1	JS	18/10/2024 09:27
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Q: How do you know there is enough data?

A: Problem is not the amount of data but the quality of data.

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

No	0.0456	2	1	JS	18/10/2024 09:29
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Pool of representation of the data used. Can it be done?

			2	JS	18/10/2024 09:30
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There are tools for summarising, etc. Surveys, ask questions and collect information to publish. Who has more power - who is heard - is it the community's feedback, or government (regulations), or researcher (AI development and science)? Who is the one who is heard more? For example, in [Name] borough - we fought for space, but it was allocated for building parking space. There is a place behind our home. Plenty of us complained, never giving up the space for parking. They offered it to people to make an apartment, this shows level of complexity. Whose words are heard?

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Yes	0.1998	19	1	JS	04/10/2024 11:08
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What do we need to do to involve the public with researchers in terms of data gathering?

			2	JS	04/10/2024 11:09
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Most of the public is busy and may not be able to get involved easily on regular workdays.

Could use celebrities (such as David Attenborough) to ask important questions.

May need to offer some sort of training to people who sign up for data gathering.

			3	JS	04/10/2024 11:10
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Regular communication from large bodies like borough councils can help in involving the public.

Things which have large audiences can be used as an avenue to ask the question about social importance (e.g., football programs).

People who are involved in providing data should be salaried.

The governance board of the [Institution name] is not particularly diverse.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	18/10/2024 09:33
Disagree with the viewpoint of using celebrities for asking questions.						
				5	JS	04/10/2024 11:11
Is it worth asking different groups of people some important question?						
				6	JS	04/10/2024 11:11
It depends on the context but would be worth trying.						
				7	JS	04/10/2024 11:12
What do the researchers around the table think about this?						
				8	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
Sampling from populations is always difficult because of the effects of sampling bias. Sometimes the information you need is more complex. Different groups have different response rates to surveys. Data management plans are compulsory as part of grant applications.						
				9	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
You can certainly make an effort using different methods but hard to achieve perfection. A lot more effort now towards nuanced questions to different groups. Reaching out to the target audience may require preparation.						
				10	JS	18/10/2024 10:03
As a researcher it's critical to create the opportunities for the public to be involved throughout the whole process. Communicate complexity in a manner that can be understood. It's a researcher responsibility to bring people in.						
				11	JS	18/10/2024 09:38
How do we engage the public to participate with this issue? Do poster of flyers with some examples of how complex AI impacts us everyday. It depends on the use of the AI (for instance, health etc. is more sensitive).						
				12	JS	18/10/2024 09:39
What are the public needs? About the patient being happy to have AI side by side with my GP; Trying to work out from the public their wants and needs as to the production of an AI						
				13	JS	18/10/2024 09:38
Giving the users a choice of an output: let the patient decide.						
				14	JS	18/10/2024 09:53
The experts who work in engagement could talk to patient and see if the public values the research.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				15	JS	18/10/2024 09:54
The consumer and producer need to come together; engagement with public is crucial; truly talk, without trying to influence Researchers and academics should try to mix with the non-academic.						
				16	JS	18/10/2024 09:55
Feedback from the public is important while building the models.						
				17	JS	15/08/2024 10:45
Being able to work out what questions need to be asked? Engaging the community.						
				18	JS	15/08/2024 10:46
Quality in the data and model - focus on what the community cares about.						
				19	JS	15/08/2024 10:46
Engagement over time - what they care about will change over time.						

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No	0.1998	19				
				1	JS	04/10/2024 11:08
What do we need to do to involve the public with researchers in terms of data gathering?						
				2	JS	04/10/2024 11:09
Most of the public is busy and may not be able to get involved easily on regular workdays. Could use celebrities (such as David Attenborough) to ask important questions. May need to offer some sort of training to people who sign up for data gathering.						
				3	JS	04/10/2024 11:10
Regular communication from large bodies like borough councils can help in involving the public. Things which have large audiences can be used as an avenue to ask the question about social importance (e.g., football programs). People who are involved in providing data should be salaried. The governance board of the [Institution name] is not particularly diverse.						
				4	JS	18/10/2024 09:33
Disagree with the viewpoint of using celebrities for asking questions.						
				5	JS	04/10/2024 11:11
Is it worth asking different groups of people some important question?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	04/10/2024 11:11
						It depends on the context but would be worth trying.
				7	JS	04/10/2024 11:12
						What do the researchers around the table think about this?
				8	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
						Sampling from populations is always difficult because of the effects of sampling bias. Sometimes the information you need is more complex. Different groups have different response rates to surveys. Data management plans are compulsory as part of grant applications.
				9	JS	04/10/2024 11:13
						You can certainly make an effort using different methods but hard to achieve perfection. A lot more effort now towards nuanced questions to different groups. Reaching out to the target audience may require preparation.
				10	JS	18/10/2024 10:03
						As a researcher it's critical to create the opportunities for the public to be involved throughout the whole process. Communicate complexity in a manner that can be understood. It's a researcher responsibility to bring people in.
				11	JS	18/10/2024 09:38
						How do we engage the public to participate with this issue? Do poster of flyers with some examples of how complex AI impacts us everyday. It depends on the use of the AI (for instance, health etc. is more sensitive).
				12	JS	18/10/2024 09:39
						What are the public needs? About the patient being happy to have AI side by side with my GP; Trying to work out from the public their wants and needs as to the production of an AI
				13	JS	18/10/2024 09:38
						Giving the users a choice of an output: let the patient decide.
				14	JS	18/10/2024 09:53
						The experts who work in engagement could talk to patient and see if the public values the research.
				15	JS	18/10/2024 09:54
						The consumer and producer need to come together; engagement with public is crucial; truly talk, without trying to influence Researchers and academics should try to mix with the non-academic.
				16	JS	18/10/2024 09:55
						Feedback from the public is important while building the models.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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17 JS 15/08/2024 10:45

Being able to work out what questions need to be asked? Engaging the community.

18 JS 15/08/2024 10:46

Quality in the data and model - focus on what the community cares about.

19 JS 15/08/2024 10:46

Engagement over time - what they care about will change over time.

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.0163 2

1 JS 18/10/2024 10:04

As a researcher, we need to be open to being questioned. Need to have funders on side so that project can be flexible and change as required.

2 JS 18/10/2024 09:55

Engaging with the public and asking their opinions about the features of the system.

Codes\\Reliability

No 0.0158 3

1 JS 04/10/2024 11:14

At what point can/should questions [about reliability] be asked?

2 JS 04/10/2024 11:14

Continue asking questions of reliability throughout the process.

3 JS 15/08/2024 10:04

"FAIR data doesn't necessary imply reliability".
AI safety and AI safety evaluation.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Research culture

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0098	1	1	JS	04/10/2024 11:31	

We are giving opinions to the research team. They are researcher or government. But we need clarity on whose ideas are prioritised more?

Codes\\Sustainability

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0457	4	1	JS	26/11/2024 11:56	

Sustainability: [who is, or should be, responsible for asking these questions?]. Who is checking it once it is open and accessible? How do you maintain validity and governance? Links to earlier point about independent governance. We shouldn't be making our own homework.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	26/11/2024 11:57	

What do we need to be confident about? Is the model considering the real-world scenarios, e.g. what are the conditions for the level of traffic, speed restrictions, tunnels, rivers, busiest time periods, etc.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			3	JS	18/10/2024 09:54	

Completeness of the models. In real time is the big question.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			4	JS	18/10/2024 10:04	

Engaging with the community is the key point. Richness in openness gives information.

Files\\Notes W4 S1 - DORA, recognition, incentives and assessment

Code

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0280	4	1	JS	18/10/2024 10:08	

No support for neuro-diversity in academia. Currently no funds around this - up to discretion of PI

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	18/10/2024 10:08	

I believe that support for individual needs varies by department possibly - for example in Library services, budget exists to support a variety of needs.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 15/08/2024 16:34

Also people evaluating have no knowledge on how to evaluate an EDI statement.
 Funders and large bodies need to do more than just tick the EDI box and make people write it without really considering it.
 If they want to do more than just ticking the "box" of being seen to be seen doing it.
 Need to train people evaluating the EDI on how to evaluate it.
 People writing the EDI need to train them on how to write it well.

4 JS 07/10/2024 11:37

There is an EDI centre, library, all of these resources at Imperial can help with EDI statements – if academics at Imperial look for it, they can support you and show how it can be done.
 People who are submitting a grant can care about EDI, but the people who evaluate don't care and don't have the knowledge to evaluate them (suggests from personal experience none of them truly care about EDI).

Codes\\FAIR principles

Yes 0.0107 3

1 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

No support for neuro-diversity in academia. Currently no funds around this - up to discretion of PI.

2 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

I believe that support for individual needs varies by department possibly - for example in Library services, budget exists to support a variety of needs.

3 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

I believe that funds are available for general use that may be up to discretion.
 However, issues exist around accessibility when it is up to discretion.

Codes\\FAIR principles\\Accessibility

No 0.0107 3

1 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

No support for neuro-diversity in academia. Currently no funds around this - up to discretion of PI.

2 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

I believe that support for individual needs varies by department possibly - for example in Library services, budget exists to support a variety of needs.

3 JS 18/10/2024 10:08

I believe that funds are available for general use that may be up to discretion.
 However, issues exist around accessibility when it is up to discretion.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Peer-review

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No		0.0010	1	1	JS	15/08/2024 16:09

The assessment of journal is not clear.

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes		0.1845	38	1	JS	15/08/2024 15:31

Rewards and incentives in academia should not be a one size fits all model.

Of course, this is not new. You are probably all familiar with these documents, DORA, Leiden Manifesto and the Metric tide. We all know that we shouldn't use impact factors for hiring, promotion or tenure-based decisions.

So what you see here is that there is a very skewed distribution. Another illustration of how the H index is not appropriate.

				2	JS	18/10/2024 10:17
				Within some British institutions there is an element of conservatism. If there was one thing you could recommend to an institution, what would that be?		

				3	JS	18/10/2024 10:17
				Speaking about it. Policies on paper are one thing but developing the committees and cultivating those conversations are another. I hope that this event today will help to broaden the discussions.		

				4	JS	18/10/2024 10:18
				I am an international student so I am not based in the UK, (so I haven't done my BA here but my Mphil I did do here). But I was under the impression that it was important to publish our work in a high impact factor journal. We did have some training on how to write a good research paper. Through the graduate school course, I came to learn that it wasn't necessarily the high impact factor that matters but the quality of the paper, so it planted that seed and I am grateful.		

				5	JS	07/10/2024 09:53
				There is a strong narrative around high impact journals which you have to reframe in terms of excellence and quality. I felt like the programme was sending a misleading message to students. That conversation we just had about bibliometrics in the introduction for participants.		

				6	JS	18/10/2024 10:19
				We need to have these conversations [on academic publishing] with student partners. I am working from the real bottom-up. And how lucky we are to have [a PhD Student] at this table so that we can share some of that message.		

				7	JS	07/10/2024 11:07
				High vs. low impact factor journal. Different experiences in the journal submission process - asking for data, requirement for open source, open access data. So I believe that more recognition is needed for high impact to reflect the difficulty in submission process - more questions, more peer review. The submission process forces you to up your work to fit their journal.		

				8	JS	07/10/2024 11:09
				I believe that the difficulty surrounding access reflects a much broader problem: DORA, CoARA are sometimes hampered by structures in place in institutions like Imperial. We need to recognise different people and that there are not structures in place to support these people. Long-established structures that do not allow for flexibility.		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				9	JS	15/08/2024 16:12
Challenges around career progression - people are sometimes pushed into roles because it is all that exists. There is not much incentive to change as it supports the majority.						
				10	JS	15/08/2024 16:12
Separation between professional service staff and research staff. Systemic structures hampering different descriptors of quality.						
				11	JS	18/10/2024 10:08
REF is a driver for change.						
				12	JS	07/10/2024 11:14
REF could include software and software was not really submitted. Difficulty to change from traditional practices.						
				13	JS	07/10/2024 11:16
Maybe diversity in output types at more general universities as opposed to Imperial. Proxy for quality is easier to assess in a paper as opposed to code, for example.						
				14	JS	07/10/2024 11:16
Perceived as more well-understood using paper.						
				15	JS	07/10/2024 11:17
How to determine value of code?						
				16	JS	07/10/2024 11:17
Resistance to quantification metrics in different fields.						
				17	JS	18/10/2024 11:51
Two participants in one of the groups have heard of DORA, but not CoARA.						
				18	JS	07/10/2024 11:19
Sitting on a panel to determine who would be elected FRS - Fellow of Royal Society, the people wrote to Nature and saw who got the most paper citations and went to UKRI to see who got the most grants. People often say the right things, but do they really take it seriously when it comes to practice? Do academics take it seriously when discussing promotion? How much of DORA/CoARA is it really embedded in the discussion?						
				19	JS	07/10/2024 11:23
What about considering public engagement?						
				20	JS	07/10/2024 11:23
What does it actually mean when people say public engagement? What does public engagement do and how do we measure how effective it is?						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				21	JS	07/10/2024 11:23
				<p>How do you know how much you have changed someone's mind? Should you be focusing a lot of attention on a few people rather than trying to target a large number of people? Question of quality vs. quantity? Should you focus on a few people and making a big impact on them or more people and maybe not be as impactful? What metrics should we be using to understand the impact of public engagement?</p>		
				22	JS	07/10/2024 11:25
				<p>[What is the experience of reward in Imperial?] PTO staff don't get recognition on being ambassadors or other work they do that takes up their time but doesn't have a direct research output. People who decide on promotions do not care about work as ambassadors, etc.</p>		
				23	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
				<p>There also is no budget for some of the public engagement work.</p>		
				24	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
				<p>Imperial doesn't allow PTO and support staff on grants – really huge failing of this university.</p>		
				25	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
				<p>What should be changed: Imperial should allow staff to be named on a grant. There is a lack of transparency. There is a lack of consistency across the Imperial.</p>		
				26	JS	07/10/2024 11:28
				<p>Where are PTO and technical staff in this discussion? Are they not part of Imperial? Often they are not included in many discussions. PTO staff are still encouraged to do things outside of their job scope, but why should they have to do this in their own time? On their own budget? Imperial needs to allow the staff to be recognised. Grants: Funders ask for these types of grants on infrastructure. Trying to write grants on infrastructure but the Faculty of [X] says no.</p>		
				27	JS	18/10/2024 11:58
				<p>These grants come from non-research staff. [Faculty name] is terribly risk averse to submitting these grants. They won't have technical staff on the grants. Can't have them as Co-Is on the application. Possibly because they can't pay overheads for them, which doesn't make any sense. [The Faculty above mentioned] also has mostly non-academic staff.</p>		
				28	JS	07/10/2024 11:34
				<p>An institution can't change things on their own because funding bodies drive the agenda. Internally, an insitution can change things.</p>		
				29	JS	07/10/2024 11:35
				<p>Narrative CV: not about contribution to research, but your scientific vision. No one knows how to evaluate a CV.</p>		
				30	JS	07/10/2024 11:35
				<p>Also no support to write a narrative CV.</p>		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				31	JS	07/10/2024 11:35
What should be done on narrative CV?						
				32	JS	07/10/2024 11:36
Funding council should train people on how to evaluate.						
				33	JS	07/10/2024 11:36
Need a cross-funding evaluation so everyone evaluates on the same model. Needs training, but the same training and the same guidelines.						
				34	JS	07/10/2024 11:36
Narrative CV is unclear on how to write an excellent CV - Royal Society should be putting out guidelines. Funders should also tell people who evaluate proposals how to evaluate narrative CVs						
				35	JS	07/10/2024 11:38
You can change application process, but still get 5 white middle-aged professors evaluating the application. Maybe you need to change the assessors more than the application.						
				36	JS	18/10/2024 11:28
When I'm hiring researchers I'm looking to see if they're capable and interested in the job I'm hiring them for. In interview I test if they have the skills we need.						
				37	JS	07/10/2024 11:42
Computational Dynamics – recognition : moved since Covid response to where will I go next; the primary outputs weren't papers, but public health and the need to come out to the public.						
				38	JS	18/10/2024 12:05
Look at team, project and ideas, not look at publications.						
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies						
	No	0.0249	8			
				1	JS	18/10/2024 10:17
Within some British institutions there is an element of conservatism. If there was one thing you could recommend to an institution, what would that be?						
				2	JS	18/10/2024 10:17
Speaking about it. Policies on paper are one thing but developing the committees and cultivating those conversations are another. I hope that this event today will help to broaden the discussions.						
				3	JS	18/10/2024 10:08
REF is a driver for change.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	07/10/2024 11:14
REF could include software and software was not really submitted. Difficulty to change from traditional practices.						
				5	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
There also is no budget for some of the public engagement work.						
				6	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
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				7	JS	15/08/2024 16:25
What should be changed: Imperial should allow staff to be named on a grant. There is a lack of transparency. There is a lack of consistency across the Imperial.						
				8	JS	07/10/2024 11:34
An institution can't change things on their own because funding bodies drive the agenda. Internally, an insitution can change things.						
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Enhance practices						
	No	0.0453	10			
				1	JS	18/10/2024 10:18
I am an international student so I am not based in the UK, (so I haven't done my BA here but my Mphil I did do here). But I was under the impression that it was important to publish our work in a high impact factor journal. We did have some training on how to write a good research paper. Through the graduate school course, I came to learn that it wasn't necessarily the high impact factor that matters but the quality of the paper, so it planted that seed and I am grateful.						
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				10	JS	18/10/2024 11:28
When I'm hiring researchers I'm looking to see if they're capable and interested in the job I'm hiring them for. In interview I test if they have the skills we need.						
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition						
	No	0.0986	17			
				1	JS	15/08/2024 15:31
Rewards and incentives in academia should not be a one size fits all model. Of course, this is not new. You are probably all familiar with these documents, DORA, Leiden Manifesto and the Metric tide. We all know that we shouldn't use impact factors for hiring, promotion or tenure-based decisions. So what you see here is that there is a very skewed distribution. Another illustration of how the H index is not appropriate.						
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High vs. low impact factor journal. Different experiences in the journal submission process - asking for data, requirement for open source, open access data. So I believe that more recognition is needed for high impact to reflect the difficulty in submission process - more questions, more peer review. The submission process forces you to up your work to fit their journal.						
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	07/10/2024 11:16
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				8	JS	07/10/2024 11:17
How to determine value of code?						
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You can change application process, but still get 5 white middle-aged professors evaluating the application. Maybe you need to change the assessors more than the application.						
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Computational Dynamics – recognition : moved since Covid response to where will I go next; the primary outputs weren't papers, but public health and the need to come out to the public.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				17	JS	18/10/2024 12:05

Look at team, project and ideas, not look at publications.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

No	0.0154	3			
			1	JS	07/10/2024 11:23

What about considering public engagement?

			2	JS	07/10/2024 11:23
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What does it actually mean when people say public engagement? What does public engagement do and how do we measure how effective it is?

			3	JS	07/10/2024 11:23
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How do you know how much you have changed someone's mind?
Should you be focusing a lot of attention on a few people rather than trying to target a large number of people? Question of quality vs. quantity?
Should you focus on a few people and making a big impact on them or more people and maybe not be as impactful?
What metrics should we be using to understand the impact of public engagement?

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No	0.0289	5			
			1	JS	15/08/2024 15:33

Position paper – what we hoped to change in academia:
Diversifying and vitalising career paths;
Balance between individual and team;
More focus on quality of work;
Stimulating Open Science;
Stimulating good leadership in academia.

			2	JS	18/10/2024 12:08
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What does the focus need to be for impact? It depends on who is defining impact. In terms of the REF, they talk about "going beyond academia". To be able to have better quality in research, you need to be able to engage effectively. Who is that group you want to engage with? Is it a lay audience on social media, or an MP? Sharing information about your research in terms of leaflets for example is dissemination, but are people engaging with it? I see myself as a connector in getting the experts to co-create training.

			3	JS	07/10/2024 11:39
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Need to increase diversity and train people who are important.

			4	JS	07/10/2024 11:39
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Get young people involved!
Small pool of people who are expert enough to do the assessment.
Bring people in from a younger generation and see how things can go forward.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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5 JS 07/10/2024 11:39

Get an assessment of people making the assessment.
How do you do it when there is a mess of funding cycle?

Codes\\Research culture

No 0.1347 22

1 JS 15/08/2024 15:31

Our ambition in the Netherlands with our national programme is a 'healthy and inspiring environment for our academic staff. Where all talents are valued: Teaching, research, impact, patient care....'

What we have seen in academia is a mismatch in terms of what we are looking for and what we reward [diagram on slide].

While we see that the work in academia is much broader but they are acknowledged by very narrow indicators (mentions h-index).

2 JS 15/08/2024 15:32

The Dutch perspective - four developments are coming together:

Ambitious Open Science agenda;

Science in transition/movement;

Concerns over work pressure/pressure on the system;

Career tracks with emphasis on teaching;

3 JS 15/08/2024 15:43

Guiding principles of the national programme:

We did not immediately develop different indicators. Developed broad dialogue and set up various committees.

In the Dutch context, different universities have taken different approaches: Rotterdam – Impact; Utrecht – Open Science.

4 JS 18/10/2024 12:08

I can speak a little bit to the academic experience. There is an expectation for a fast publication turn-around, even in a new position. In software, traditional publication is not emphasised in the same way so doesn't fit into the publication metric in the same way. There is a consortium for high performance computing in the UK. They ask you to quantify the number of UK users of your software. The number of worldwide users of your software. They are looking for a way to quantify this. So there are other kind of metrics that can drive these types of decisions in a similar way. So using alternative metrics is a challenge, because there are privacy implications. If they are using Python to download stuff. How do we measure things when we have GDPR, etc.

5 JS 08/10/2024 09:10

My role is to support academics. The low volume of queries regarding bibliometrics may indicate that either researchers are extremely confident in the use of metrics or do not have any significant concerns.

6 JS 07/10/2024 11:18

Has had the space to prioritise quality over quantity due to department being at intersection between engineering and medicine - more industry focused.

Training on a college level as opposed to being dependent on the PI - better towards changing culture.

7 JS 18/10/2024 12:51

Researcher still new at Imperial, only here for a few a couple of months.

Coming back to academia in the UK, spend 6 months postdoc in X and short time in a biotech start up.

PI has not yet published the paper. Can't have academic currency to apply for fellowship since papers have not been published for post-doc work, but also can't make the PI publish until they want to, even though it was their work.

Why not publish? Struggle as being small lab in the genedrive field; other groups smaller with more power who sit on the journal and won't let the paper get published.

Can't get papers out so aren't able to grow in their career.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				8	JS	07/10/2024 11:34
<p>Q: What about bioRxiv? PIs are adverse to this because worry about getting scooped. Without showing research, can't get another job and can't show what they did in 6 years postdoc because they haven't published the paper and so then is very hard to get another job. Some people who are hiring want to see the evidence (i.e. see the unpublished paper, or data) which original PI won't let you.</p>						
				9	JS	07/10/2024 11:37
<p>Same point on data management plans: it's box ticking rather than being implemented and critically evaluated.</p>						
				10	JS	07/10/2024 11:37
<p>Why are scientist doing so much admin on things they don't care about?</p>						
				11	JS	07/10/2024 11:37
<p>If you're asking for taxpayer funding then you should be inclusive (EDI).</p>						
				12	JS	07/10/2024 11:37
<p>Yes, but should have support staff to do this (EDI) for them because they aren't trained in it and you could have support staff with true expertise on how to action what is written and what is feasible and proven effective.</p>						
				13	JS	15/08/2024 16:48
<p>Publication is a way to share our work, but we do have to recognise that when they go to their next job publications is an important factor.</p>						
				14	JS	07/10/2024 11:41
<p>Isn't writing a part of the job, to divulge/develop research?</p>						
				15	JS	07/10/2024 11:41
<p>We have to deliver things not papers.</p>						
				16	JS	18/10/2024 12:04
<p>How do you measure qualitative... and impacts – how do we weight this against something that is easy to measure? People still use metrics.</p>						
				17	JS	18/10/2024 12:04
<p>When you're deciding, you have to think about research culture at an institutional level.</p>						
				18	JS	18/10/2024 12:04
<p>We do look at research type, grants, and teaching and community work. You can't measure these things. And people don't even try. Not look only to impact factor of publications, and evaluate the work in other ways. How robust some CV's are.</p>						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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19 JS 18/10/2024 12:05

You can submit things to REF that are not publications

20 JS 07/10/2024 11:47

University produces very impactful things that are not impacts.

21 JS 15/08/2024 16:55

When the project is done and all stakeholders are happy, why publish?

22 JS 07/10/2024 11:50

We are still in the early stages [working in research security]; very sensitive piece of research that can be applied and misused – there are exceptions; doing things responsibly, if we know that we do want to protect that; the message has to be clear not to confuse the community. Funding applications terms and conditions – about security and open access publishing. It is a smaller percentage of researchers; awareness of research security is the idea, and then navigate how it fits with Open Science pushing forward a message that is not confusing.

Codes\\Sustainability

No 0.0048 2

1 JS 07/10/2024 11:18

Assessing quality of code/software.

2 JS 07/10/2024 11:18

There are journals that look at sustainability of code, real world use. Review process for code - Journal of Open Source Software, SoftwareX, etc.

Files\\Notes W4 S2 - What matters for quality and reliability

Code

Codes\\Accountability

No 0.0050 1

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:12

The whole point of these research assessment exercises is to provide that accountability, but they are not perfect. The good thing is that these are changing positively.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Collaboration

No	0.0073	1
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1	JS	07/10/2024 12:12
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From the engineering point of view, the stakeholders are hitting a lot of roadblocks with IP. Sometimes it is difficult to achieve collaborations because there are divergences/tensions between insitution's view and commercial partners' views.

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

No	0.0146	3
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1	JS	07/10/2024 12:08
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What we have been talking about a lot is zooming in on a lot of these issues. But we should also remember to zoom out and not lose sight of issues in terms of EDI, having interdisciplinary teams, etc.

2	JS	28/11/2024 11:28
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EDI, having interdisciplinary teams

3	JS	07/10/2024 12:34
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EPSRC [Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council] webinars don't mention Octopus.

Narrative CVs: Being a non-native English speaker how you approach and structure response might be challenging. It benefits white, western, Oxford/Cambridge.

Codes\\Ethics

No	0.0310	7
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1	JS	07/10/2024 12:04
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I guess there is a question about whether this would be managed institutionally or devolved in some way. For human-based studies, it's not just the peer review, you get a quality check at the ethical review stage. Can you almost beef up some of the ethical review process (before even the peer review process has taken place)?

2	JS	07/10/2024 12:04
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You can probably have even more in there. If research is not well done, would it even be considered as ethical?

3	JS	07/10/2024 12:05
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We do have a process for templates for the documents. Before it goes to ethics it comes to us. We help to determine the appropriateness. So we do have some of these kind of checks and balances in place. It is improving every time.

4	JS	07/10/2024 12:05
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We do have ethical committees for low-risk settings for example (no trials of drugs or human participants).

5	JS	07/10/2024 12:13
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But those tensions [between Imperial and commercial partners] have always existed. I am not sure what infrastructure Imperial manages but these can be resolved.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	07/10/2024 12:13
The ethics of it is really field-dependent.						
				7	JS	07/10/2024 12:13
It's about finding the right level of abstraction.						
Codes\\Open Research						
	Yes	0.0775	19			
				1	JS	07/10/2024 12:13
In an ideal world, I would hope to see more references to Open Science indicators rather than just citations. When researchers publish something, they tend to highlight the journal rather than the research itself (whether the preprint was available early).						
				2	JS	07/10/2024 12:13
Difficult to see how Octopus will work across different disciplines.						
				3	JS	07/10/2024 12:14
Reviewing protocols is difficult and there is a limited pool of researchers for that.						
				4	JS	19/08/2024 09:13
Is it useful to publish components of research? You can break things down but what is the value of each part taken in isolation?						
				5	JS	19/08/2024 09:18
We as a community can take on the role of publishers - Wellcome Open Research.						
				6	JS	07/10/2024 12:24
Would be no enthusiasm for uptake. Takes time to change.						
				7	JS	07/10/2024 12:24
Needs to have long-term value - how do you make it stay valid over time? For example, maintain links that don't break.						
				8	JS	18/10/2024 15:49
Romania, Bulgaria, Turkey: No money for fee paying journals so only get open access journals. Can't publish either because don't have the money. Sweden, Norway, Denmark: They have money. They have the money for publishing the journal.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				9	JS	07/10/2024 12:29
By publishing in Octopus ideas can be stolen in the other country.						
				10	JS	07/10/2024 12:30
Sharks (aka people who steal ideas). Bigger labs with more resources, they will do it faster once they got the idea they have stolen from other people. The sharks steal the ideas and put them in their own grants.						
				11	JS	07/10/2024 12:30
Need to fight for Intellectual Property: if you have put it on Octopus, can prove you logged your idea.						
				12	JS	18/10/2024 16:02
Open review as an early career researcher is scary. Would not want to put your name on your review and say shouldn't be published because it's poor quality etc. Can't criticise a huge group without fear of political pushback.						
				13	JS	18/10/2024 16:02
[Open review] Often find too much quantity and a lack of quality when reviewing and would be too scared to put my name on it. Impacts not only looking for a job, but also submitting a paper, applying for a grant. People at the top cannot accept feedback from people at bottom and it's scary as someone towards the bottom to try to do so.						
				14	JS	18/10/2024 16:07
Huge problem with the original systems. Tried to build a machine learning model to pull from all data to make a super molecule but cannot make it so it tells us if what's online is of poor data quality.						
				15	JS	07/10/2024 12:36
Unintended consequences?						
				16	JS	07/10/2024 12:36
[Octopus as Open reserach process - obstacles:] Amount to review. Will add more work for junior researchers. People like stories.						
				17	JS	07/10/2024 12:36
Loses the big picture but breaks the process into chunks.						
				18	JS	07/10/2024 12:39
I can't help thinking that the professionalisation of roles is something academia is still struggling with.						
				19	JS	07/10/2024 12:40
Let's get rid of library subscriptions.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Codes\\Open Research\Obstacles to Open Research						
	No	0.0435	11			
				1	JS	07/10/2024 12:24
Would be no enthusiasm for uptake. Takes time to change.						
				2	JS	07/10/2024 12:24
Needs to have long-term value - how do you make it stay valid over time? For example, maintain links that don't break.						
				3	JS	07/10/2024 12:29
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				4	JS	07/10/2024 12:30
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				5	JS	07/10/2024 12:30
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				7	JS	18/10/2024 16:07
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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11 JS 07/10/2024 12:39

I can't help thinking that the professionalisation of roles is something academia is still struggling with.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness

Yes 0.0187 4

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:13

Difficult to see how Octopus will work across different disciplines.

2 JS 07/10/2024 12:14

Reviewing protocols is difficult and there is a limited pool of researchers for that.

3 JS 18/10/2024 15:49

Romania, Bulgaria, Turkey:
No money for fee paying journals so only get open access journals.
Can't publish either because don't have the money.
Sweden, Norway, Denmark:
They have money.
They have the money for publishing the journal.

4 JS 18/10/2024 16:02

Open review as an early career researcher is scary.
Would not want to put your name on your review and say shouldn't be published because it's poor quality etc. Can't criticise a huge group without fear of political pushback.

Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open access

No 0.0187 4

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:13

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4 JS 18/10/2024 16:02

Open review as an early career researcher is scary.

Would not want to put your name on your review and say shouldn't be published because it's poor quality etc. Can't criticise a huge group without fear of political pushback.

Codes\\Peer-review

No 0.0321 9

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:06

I would say over half of the research projects have ever had to go through any kind of review. Engineering in jet engines doesn't require any kind of internal review board (no human or animal subjects).

2 JS 07/10/2024 12:07

Would you find any kind of review to be helpful in your view?

3 JS 07/10/2024 12:07

Peer review could be beneficial. We have to be mindful of the workload this adds. As long as this is rewarded somehow within the framework.

4 JS 07/10/2024 12:08

If it's internal, benefit is peer review can be accounted for to address concerns about non-renumerated/free labour.

5 JS 19/08/2024 09:18

Peer review can be influenced by people's relationships.

6 JS 07/10/2024 12:32

Reviewing methods early on is incredible and saves money, time, unnecessary research and improves what is done.

7 JS 07/10/2024 12:38

There are rubbish peer reviews.

Problem of anonymous peer review and retaliation.

8 JS 18/10/2024 16:26

Nature about DeepMind and the peer reviewers: weren't able to review it properly.

9 JS 07/10/2024 12:39

Paying people and separating them entirely from the structure of academia. Trying to improve the metrics about a metric might twist it. If you're not within the structure of academia you are more strict in your evaluation.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Practical recommendations

	Yes	0.0785	15			
				1	JS	18/10/2024 16:48
I think one of the problems at the moment is we check quality at the end of the process. We could spot errors earlier in the process. What Alex (Freeman) does is she disaggregates the process into its component parts allowing for greater scrutiny. Universities would need to take this kind of thing seriously. This costs money. But this model shows that this could be recouped in terms of the ultimate quality that this leads to.						
				2	JS	19/08/2024 09:01
At an institutional level there needs to be a shift from the publication and findings to the method to some extent. Maintaining the existing research infrastructure, once someone's publication is out of the door, they forget about it ("bit rot"). This maintenance of methods and techniques needs to be incentivised by the institution. This is not currently being looked at by any institution.						
				3	JS	19/08/2024 09:09
Funders like the MRC [Medical Research Council] are looking more for people with lived experience in certain areas to be involved on review panels.						
				4	JS	19/08/2024 09:14
Steep uptake before any value might be seen. Platform might provide a tool for clearer reward and recognition.						
				5	JS	19/08/2024 09:15
How would you change recognition for research? Inflation in the number of people in STEM leads to more difficulty for job security.						
				6	JS	19/08/2024 09:16
Imperial agrees to principles of DoRA, how is this implemented in terms of hiring? We fall back on traditional metrics as we do not have any other metrics. Narrative CV could address that potentially but it is not as easy to pull information out of.						
				7	JS	19/08/2024 09:19
University presses can have a role to play - discipline lead- community journal. Rating can help to drive change. How well are adhering to certain standards like DORA etc.? Changing requirements for publishing etc. that comes from funders - must come from a body with power.						
				8	JS	07/10/2024 12:17
No, hadn't heard of it [Octopus]. I can't imagine people actually using it.						
				9	JS	07/10/2024 12:21
Only heard about [Octopus] before in previous Beyond Open Research workshops. Unless it becomes mandatory, I can't see people using it.						
				10	JS	07/10/2024 12:22
Like it [Octopus] as a tool for grants.						
				11	JS	07/10/2024 12:22
[Octopus] would have to be mandatory to get shift.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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12 JS 07/10/2024 12:31

Strongly believe that it should be acknowledged who did what on a paper/in research.
Really important to get credit for exactly the work that you do.
Impact depends on the uptake.

13 JS 07/10/2024 12:40

There is a movement towards valuing professional roles.

14 JS 07/10/2024 12:40

If someone gets a position in a university you would have to get another (being professional, technical, etc.). That would create positions for people who love doing science without the ambition to be a Principal Investigator (PI).

15 JS 07/10/2024 12:42

You don't have many people who lead teams, you need more people who are working on them.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Awareness of what is going on

No 0.0065 2

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:17

No, hadn't heard of it [Octopus].
I can't imagine people actually using it.

2 JS 07/10/2024 12:21

Only heard about [Octopus] before in previous Beyond Open Research workshops.
Unless it becomes mandatory, I can't see people using it.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies

No 0.0324 6

1 JS 19/08/2024 09:01

At an institutional level there needs to be a shift from the publication and findings to the method to some extent. Maintaining the existing research infrastructure, once someone's publication is out of the door, they forget about it ("bit rot"). This maintenance of methods and techniques needs to be incentivised by the institution. This is not currently being looked at by any institution.

2 JS 19/08/2024 09:19

University presses can have a role to play - discipline lead- community journal.
Rating can help to drive change. How well are adhering to certain standards like DORA etc.?
Changing requirements for publishing etc. that comes from funders - must come from a body with power.

3 JS 07/10/2024 12:22

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4 JS 07/10/2024 12:22

[Octopus] would have to be mandatory to get shift.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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5 JS 07/10/2024 12:40

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6 JS 07/10/2024 12:42

You don't have many people who lead teams, you need more people who are working on them.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Enhance practices

No 0.0145 2

1 JS 18/10/2024 16:48

I think one of the problems at the moment is we check quality at the end of the process. We could spot errors earlier in the process. What Alex (Freeman) does is she disaggregates the process into its component parts allowing for greater scrutiny. Universities would need to take this kind of thing seriously. This costs money. But this model shows that this could be recouped in terms of the ultimate quality that this leads to.

2 JS 07/10/2024 12:40

There is a movement towards valuing professional roles.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition

No 0.0205 4

1 JS 19/08/2024 09:14

Steep uptake before any value might be seen.
Platform might provide a tool for clearer reward and recognition.

2 JS 19/08/2024 09:15

How would you change recognition for research?
Inflation in the number of people in STEM leads to more difficulty for job security.

3 JS 19/08/2024 09:16

Imperial agrees to principles of DoRA, how is this implemented in terms of hiring?
We fall back on traditional metrics as we do not have any other metrics.
Narrative CV could address that potentially but it is not as easy to pull information out of.

4 JS 07/10/2024 12:31

Strongly believe that it should be acknowledged who did what on a paper/in research.
Really important to get credit for exactly the work that you do.
Impact depends on the uptake.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0044	1	1	JS	19/08/2024 09:09	

Funders like the MRC [Medical Research Council] are looking more for people with lived experience in certain areas to be involved on review panels.

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0615	11	1	JS	07/10/2024 11:58	

Having a library of established methods to draw on for doing their methods and analysis of their work. If everyone has a different method, it makes it difficult for comparison. You essentially have to reproduce someone else's method.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			2	JS	19/08/2024 09:16	

Community should expand to not only include the community of researchers but also other stakeholders.
Driving force of the commercial publishing industry - to the research community.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			3	JS	07/10/2024 12:22	

[Octopus] makes science more robust and we can be honest in saying what we found didn't align with our hypothesis.
Sounds really nice and would be nice to be more robust.
Spent a lot of time re-doing things other people have done but didn't know they had done because negative results weren't published so would be nice to avoid that.
However, cannot imagine professors she is working with using Octopus.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			4	JS	07/10/2024 12:28	

What do we need to make Octopus look like a scheme?

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			5	JS	07/10/2024 12:28	

[Octopus] needs to be made mandatory.
Early career researchers need to do more because they need to review in Octopus and review main journal.
It might result in increased work for those at the bottom of the triangle.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			6	JS	21/10/2024 10:14	

Professors won't allow it [to make Octopus look like a scheme].

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			7	JS	07/10/2024 12:28	

Make Octopus a requirement instead of grant application. You would submit it and the funding council would look at Octopus first stage instead of grants so you don't get ripped off .

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
			8	JS	07/10/2024 12:31	

Need a repository for negative data, most journals don't follow through on it even though they claim they publish negative data.
Journals don't publish negative impact even though they say they will.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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9 JS 28/11/2024 13:55

So much of what is reported is not reproducible, no one reports everything, usually sloppy, sometimes wrong.

10 JS 28/11/2024 13:55

Things that are published are not high quality enough.

11 JS 19/08/2024 09:36

How to start using Octopus?

- Nobody is willing to take risks and everybody is busy.
- Working with funders and institutions in order to reduce the risks and increasing the benefits.
- Free to read and free to write.
- Start talking to institutions to buy it and make it like a portal.
- Preprint and pre-registration server.

Codes\\Research culture

No 0.0112 3

1 JS 07/10/2024 12:10

The UNESCO definition of Open Science is quite broad and does include principles [such as EDI, having interdisciplinary teams] already mentioned.

2 JS 19/08/2024 09:17

Equity markers of publishers are being developed internationally.
Publish or perish has allowed for predatory publisher practices.

3 JS 19/08/2024 09:36

An opportunity to change the culture.
Preprints has been a game changer in research practices.

Codes\\Sustainability

No 0.0030 1

1 JS 19/08/2024 09:17

Science builds on previous research and current publication process is slowing that down significantly.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Files\\Notes W4 S3 - What is excellence and can we measure it

Code

Codes\\Assessment

No	0.1152	19
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1	JS	07/10/2024 13:53
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Traditionally, you either monitor outputs or process. There are different orientations so there is a challenge when you try to do both. The ethos is good but nailing down how you get there is much more complicated. You could be performing well in terms of the process but not meeting expectations for outputs and is that okay?

2	JS	07/10/2024 13:53
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The whole point of the assessments is to ensure that good work is done. Game-playing emerges and people lose sight of the end-goal. Excellence is obviously one of the values at Imperial which emerged from an institutional survey. But it was intended as a holistic quality.

3	JS	07/10/2024 13:53
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An example of where it is useful when broken down, is where excellence is used in promotional decisions (compared to previous practices where there were not clear standards in place). People do use these as a guide to map out their careers.

4	JS	07/10/2024 13:55
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That is why you don't have one single measure for determining this. If you have multiple measures you can build a more reliable picture.

5	JS	07/10/2024 13:56
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Authors can also drill down into the citations to identify which ones are positive, neutral or negative.

6	JS	20/08/2024 09:56
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Process-based success vs outcome-based success.

7	JS	20/08/2024 10:00
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Evidence-based assessment - demonstrate how you have adhered to guidelines and frameworks to check.

8	JS	07/10/2024 14:08
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At the moment, is excellence being taken into consideration?

9	JS	07/10/2024 14:08
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Paper doesn't have societal impact if it:
a) isn't accessible to people who don't have the money;
b) isn't accessible to people who are not an expert in the field.
What is the translational element?

10	JS	07/10/2024 14:08
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REF = Research Excellence Framework, happens 6-7 years.
Higher score under REF, the more money you get from the government.
Research output is 50% of the REF.
High REF people were traded.
Game universities play to get money.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				11	JS	07/10/2024 14:34
<p>They are paid to manage, it is all about prioritising it. Not evaluated on where people go, who is in your group. You should be training scientists. PIs aren't held responsible.</p>						
				12	JS	07/10/2024 14:35
<p>Teaching is important! PIs should be teaching! Need to evaluate teaching and have PI teach so you can breed excellence. Some put loads of effort into teaching and some put 0 – it is not incentivised. Imperial charges a lot of students lots of money at undergraduate and at the masters level and they aren't always taught well.</p>						
				13	JS	07/10/2024 14:54
<p>From working more than 15 years in research, making something new with AI – given all this history, excellence is about a long cycle, working to do things to work better for society. Im not sure how we could measure some of them.</p>						
				14	JS	07/10/2024 14:55
<p>You couldn't measure excellence?</p>						
				15	JS	21/10/2024 12:24
<p>I don't think it is easy. And we might have got it wrong. It's not like measuring a table. Recognition is human judgement and therefore subjective.</p>						
				16	JS	07/10/2024 15:04
<p>Grant applications modelled on DARPA [Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency] model about trusting the judgement of individual people.</p>						
				17	JS	07/10/2024 15:04
<p>Grants should be given when the project is not straightforward excellent.</p>						
				18	JS	07/10/2024 15:05
<p>Industry might be a source to learn from. It worked in undergraduate admissions, for instance.</p>						
				19	JS	20/08/2024 10:20
<p>Funding decisions, grants, promotions – people in these panels are being asked to measure and to compare, but it is necessary to recognise it is still a subjective task.</p>						

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

	No	0.0072	2			
				1	JS	20/08/2024 09:58
<p>Diversity of thought avoiding 'group think'. Provide culture where upward challenge is possible.</p>						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 JS 20/08/2024 10:00

Equity on government level - social support regarding issues like maternity, childcare, disability.

Codes\\Excellence

No 0.1323 28

1 JS 07/10/2024 13:53

Traditionally, you either monitor outputs or process. There are different orientations so there is a challenge when you try to do both. The ethos is good but nailing down how you get there is much more complicated. You could be performing well in terms of the process but not meeting expectations for outputs and is that okay?

2 JS 20/08/2024 09:51

Problems with measuring excellence.
Hard to quantify meaning of excellence in academia.
Excellence R us article.
'Excellence' has no intrinsic meaning in academia.
The hyper-competition that arises from the performance of excellence is completely at odds with qualities of good research.

3 JS 07/10/2024 14:00

Excellence: the best you can without fraud; apply the research method; collaborative, encouraging conversation, communal influence on excellence and performance.
Learn a lot through communication and collaboration.
Excellence varies on individual level and college level.

4 JS 07/10/2024 14:00

The term "excellence" has lost its meaning through overuse; there is no real consensus on what it actually means.

5 JS 20/08/2024 09:55

Excellent research moves discipline forward, new, exciting does not have to be robust, reliable.
Excellent research must hit certain targets - for example, it must be reproducible.

6 JS 07/10/2024 14:01

Excellence can be built on practices and values as opposed to outcomes.

7 JS 20/08/2024 09:57

Framework for approach can put you in the best position for future success - working in an excellent way but not necessarily always achieving an excellent outcome.

8 JS 07/10/2024 14:03

Excellence is an annoying word to define. Rigor, transparency, quality...
No conclusion really.

9 JS 07/10/2024 14:04

In science, quality and transparency.
Boring stuff can be more important for fundamental knowledge than other (exciting) things.
We don't know now what might be useful then.
Funding has cut down for "pure" funding to fund "applied" funding.
Need to try things that we don't know - high risk, high reward science.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				10	JS	07/10/2024 14:04
<p>Societal excellence – need to define why is now the best time to do it; why is it urgent. Some people do things for the sake of doing it. If there is a finite amount of money, and growing number of curious people, it's important to gauge what is the most important. There is some funding on high-risk, high-reward science direct to early career research. ARIA [Advanced Research + Invention Agency] funding. If research takes money from taxpayer, it can't be done just because it's fun, it needs to have value. Is importance and excellence the same thing? Impact is not a great word because we don't always know what has impact now.</p>						
				11	JS	07/10/2024 14:39
<p>Excellence is more about the closest to research quality, being state of the art, being inventive. Working with researchers some of them have better results and working prototypes and research outcomes, experimental data, etc. It makes our work easier - how to deliver things from idea to implementation.</p>						
				12	JS	07/10/2024 14:56
<p>Trustworthiness might be problematic.</p>						
				13	JS	07/10/2024 14:56
<p>It's always a risk.</p>						
				14	JS	07/10/2024 14:57
<p>Excellence depends on what you're looking for.</p>						
				15	JS	07/10/2024 14:57
<p>Demonstrate excellence.</p>						
				16	JS	07/10/2024 14:57
<p>I would not use the word [excellence] at all, I would focus on qualities.</p>						
				17	JS	07/10/2024 14:57
<p>How do you feel about excellence being a value?</p>						
				18	JS	07/10/2024 14:58
<p>I think about it when the annual review conversation comes about.</p>						
				19	JS	07/10/2024 14:59
<p>When it is used to compare people.</p>						
				20	JS	07/10/2024 14:59
<p>Hubris and excellence.</p>						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				21	JS	07/10/2024 14:59
Excellence is a tent value.						
				22	JS	07/10/2024 14:59
Change name of REF and take out the excellence.						
				23	JS	07/10/2024 15:00
Excellences (plural) - various qualities.						
				24	JS	07/10/2024 15:00
Excellence is being weaponised.						
				25	JS	07/10/2024 15:01
Even that [soundness and integrity] underplays other aspects that might be important such as creativity and leadership.						
				26	JS	07/10/2024 15:01
We're looking for robustness of the research.						
				27	JS	07/10/2024 15:02
People might not agree with excellence.						
				28	JS	07/10/2024 15:02
Everybody in science thinks there is a ground truth.						

Codes\\Expectations

	Yes	0.0388	3			
				1	JS	07/10/2024 13:54
Continuing on from the point about publishing negative results. Negative citations can also be fruitful in terms of finding new perspectives and correcting their papers. So we always encourage authors to look beyond the citations. So unless the paper is using fake data, negative citations shouldn't lead to poor quality science.						
				2	JS	07/10/2024 13:58
Going back to bibliometrics. Funders, publishers, governments, institutions should be using bibliometrics responsibly. Responsible use of metrics is already in place at Imperial. HR for job descriptions. University rankings. We work with a lot of commercial partners and data providers, we should consider their use of responsible metrics as part of the tender process. Also in hiring, if one applicant mentions a publication in a high impact factor journal as a shorthand for "excellence", this should be interrogated further in terms of what are the strengths of the publications in terms of their research quality.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 07/10/2024 14:35

Metrics is how much money you got in, not how much you added value to the Imperial ecosystem and students.

Codes\\Expectations\Metrics

No 0.0388 3

1 JS 07/10/2024 13:54

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2 JS 07/10/2024 13:58

Going back to bibliometrics. Funders, publishers, governments, institutions should be using bibliometrics responsibly. Responsible use of metrics is already in place at Imperial. HR for job descriptions. University rankings. We work with a lot of commercial partners and data providers, we should consider their use of responsible metrics as part of the tender process. Also in hiring, if one applicant mentions a publication in a high impact factor journal as a shorthand for "excellence", this should be interrogated further in terms of what are the strengths of the publications in terms of their research quality.

3 JS 07/10/2024 14:35

Metrics is how much money you got in, not how much you added value to the Imperial ecosystem and students.

Codes\\Open Research

Yes 0.0072 2

1 JS 07/10/2024 14:36

You can only publish in Open Research journals if you have money to do it.

2 JS 07/10/2024 14:36

Develop hardware/software to publish and share openly.
Incentivise internally at the community level for Open Science.

Codes\\Practical recommendations

Yes 0.0407 9

1 JS 07/10/2024 13:56

To recognise anything beyond metrics regarding what Imperial could be doing to embed what I am going to call 'holistic excellence'.

2 JS 07/10/2024 13:56

You take a multi-pronged approach and define this in contracts, values, annual review conversations, promotional guidelines, seed funding which promotes projects on those bases, rather than one hammer that comes down to establish "excellence".

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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3 JS 20/08/2024 09:59

Incentives for open access - REF open access polices have had the biggest impact on open research.

4 JS 07/10/2024 14:33

What practical steps could help to shift the focus towards excellence, quality and reliability?

5 JS 07/10/2024 14:33

Career pathways – how to translate across sector? It isn't easy.

6 JS 07/10/2024 14:34

Continued professional development – people aren't able to move up.
Permeant role but can't be a PI.
PIs aren't managers, aren't trained to be managers and do not always train their students.

7 JS 07/10/2024 14:34

There are many courses, but there are no incentive for PIs to take them.
You should be training scientist; there are no metrics to care for training.

8 JS 07/10/2024 14:34

They are paid to manage, it is all about prioritising it.

9 JS 07/10/2024 15:06

Recruitment cannot be made by one person, you do need a team.

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition

No 0.0407 9

1 JS 07/10/2024 13:56

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2 JS 07/10/2024 13:56

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9 JS 07/10/2024 15:06

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Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality

No 0.0203 3

1 JS 20/08/2024 09:09

What facets are necessary for the highest quality research?
-Collaboration and co-creation
-Freedom of enquiry
-Freedom from bullying, harassment, mismanagement
-Recruitment from the broadest pools of talent
-Commitment to career development
-Reward or risk taking
-An environment that values research integrity and Open Research practices

2 JS 20/08/2024 09:57

Science is a team sport.
Good leadership can encourage openness, no fear, safe space, good relationships, social aspects.

3 JS 20/08/2024 09:59

Now dropping weight of research output and upping weight of research culture.

Codes\\Research culture

No 0.0296 6

1 JS 07/10/2024 13:53

I liked that Stephen recognised risk-taking as one of the principles in good science practice alongside learning from failure and publishing null results.

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	20/08/2024 09:59
Research culture is more institutional as opposed to driving change in the individual.						
				3	JS	07/10/2024 14:36
How do we breed excellence at Imperial?						
				4	JS	07/10/2024 14:36
Train the trainer. PI doesn't pay interest to the lab so no one cares.						
				5	JS	07/10/2024 14:36
Drive culture change: it is necessary to link funding to research culture change.						
				6	JS	07/10/2024 14:37
Spend a lot of time and money where there is no trickledown. Imperial has relaunched the strategy and vision: ICL does science for humanity. However, no trickledown. On a website in a nice font. Many aspects of the research culture exist only on paper, and they are not felt in practice at the cultural level. It takes time but there will be slow turn over.						
Codes\\Transparency						
	No	0.0289	6			
				1	JS	20/08/2024 09:56
Transparency, practical aspects - data management plans, collaboration plans.						
				2	JS	07/10/2024 14:09
Is transparency a mark of excellence? Is rigour?						
				3	JS	07/10/2024 14:10
Is it Nature, is it Cell etc? Nature does make you put the data in now.						
				4	JS	07/10/2024 14:10
People think it's excellent because it's Nature, not because the research was conducted transparently. Excellence is where it comes from – it's better coming from Imperial than from a university you haven't heard of.						
				5	JS	07/10/2024 14:10
Sector based – if you have great impact within that small sphere. How can you compare that to impact on curing something like HIV. Publishing in different language - doesn't mean it's less excellent.						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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				6	JS	07/10/2024 14:10
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Does this actually happen? Are there many that actually aren't translated?
Could never find a paper or journal that didn't have an English translation.
